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MAVIN DAVID S. CATBAGAN

**LAUGHING MATTERS: UNDERSTANDING HUMOR IN SELECTED ASEAN
COUNTRIES AND STAND-UP COMEDIANS THROUGH TEXTUAL ANALYSIS OF
ONLINE COMEDY VIDEOS DURING CRISIS**

Thesis Adviser:

DR. GRACE JAVIER ALFONSO
Faculty of Management and Development Studies

12 September 2022

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DR. GRACE J. ALFONSO
Chair, Thesis Committee

4 October 2022

(Date)

DR. JOEFF B. SANTARITA
Member, Thesis Committee

5 October 2022

(Date)

PROF. ROLANDO G. TALAMPAS
Member, Thesis Committee

5 October 2022

(Date)

DR. JOANE V. SERRANO

Dean

Faculty of Management and Development Studies

13 October 2022

(Date)

Biographical Sketch

The author obtained his bachelor's degree in Landscape Architecture at the University of the Philippines Diliman in April 2012, and became a registered and licensed Landscape Architect in March 2013. Since graduation, he is currently working for the Office of the Campus Architect, an in-house planning and implementing agency mandated to serve the infrastructure requirements and development of the University from where he obtained his undergraduate degree.

Outside his daytime job, he is trying to pursue communication and a bit of performing arts through podcast and stand-up comedy, as a hobby, leading to the following study relevant to this graduate course.

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Dedication:

All professional and aspiring stand-up comedians here in the Philippines and the rest of the ASEAN region who entertain people to show that laughing matters.

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Abstract

Recently, ASEAN as a region faced another crisis since the Asian Financial Crisis in 1997, which is the COVID-19 pandemic. There were several reports regarding the response in the member-state level wherein efforts are still “to each of its own” mentality as member-states resort to different approaches ranging from proactive ones to “draconian” ones (IID, 2020), and the need to maintain their relationships with the superpowers amid the pandemic (Wangkiat, 2022), while there were some regarding ordinary people coping with the situation mostly in the socio-economic aspect (Morgan and Trinh, 2021). More than ninety percent (90%) have felt that the pandemic has influenced their lives and three of the top five ways in coping with stress brought about by the pandemic is related to spending more time on their smartphones either through playing games, communicating through social media, or watching videos (Ito, 2020). In line with promoting shared culture and giving respect to it by recognition of its unity in diversity, the proposed study mainly focuses on understanding an interesting topic such as humor through stand-up comedy in the context of selected ASEAN member-states during a time of crisis faced by the region, particularly the COVID-19 pandemic. From the analyses on both the stand-up comedians as performers in the video and the audiences both live and online through social media it was found out that humor in selected ASEAN member-states during a period of crisis are “glocal” -- global in approach yet local in context, both a *venue* and an avenue for development, and a creative space for (virtual) ASEAN community-building.

Keywords: Stand-up comedy, Textual Analysis, Crisis

Chapter I

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

Humor is a communicative activity (Lynch, 2002 in Ojha and Holmes, 2010, p. 279) and a "phenomenon that provides tension relief, help people integrate socially, and can be used to control people" (Miller, 1996; Morreall, 1991 in Ojha and Holmes, 2010, p. 279). It can be observed anytime and anywhere, thus described as "omnipresent" (Ojha and Holmes, 2010, p. 279), such as in a workplace that help "alleviate stress, to improve creative vision, and to bond" (Kreps, Herndon, & Arneson, 1993 in Ojha and Holmes, 2010, p. 279). That inspired the author to try observational stand-up comedy in virtual meeting rooms wherein originally-written comedy materials are being performed mostly in virtual meeting rooms and once in a live audience at the time that quarantine restrictions during the COVID-19 pandemic were eased. In romantic relationships, humor plays a "critical role in attraction" (Bressler and Balshine, 2006 in Anderson and DiTunnariello, 2016, p.1513) and in maintaining an existing relationship through aggressive humor (Anderson and DiTunnariello, 2016). In the medical field particularly in rehabilitation of those who face addiction, laughter, in a study through conversational analysis, became a "flexible device for preventing or resolving a possible risk of confrontation" (Arminen and Halonen, 2007, p. 484).

In parallel with the impact on the use of humor discussed above in certain fields such as professional types in the workplace, romantic relationships between two people, and the medical field, the Association of Southeast Asian Nations or ASEAN also employs approaches that provide tension relief, aid in integration, and maintain harmony at the member-state level. Marred by initial conflicts by Southeast Asian

states brought about by their newly-achieved status of independence and with colonial experience still fresh in their memories, which lead to failures in the formation of organizations that preceded ASEAN (Tarling, 2007 and Keling et al, 2011), consensus and non-interference became the considered language of the Association of Southeast Asian Nations diplomacy (Villanueva and Manalo, 2017).

ASEAN member-states consider consensus as the “best and most pragmatic”, or practical strategy for the “long-term survival” of the association in the “choppy waters of the international environment“ (Luqman, 2019, 9th para.) due to the following reasons: first, member-states have their needs served through a dialogue-friendly environment without their national sovereignty felt compromised (Luqman, 2019, 10th para). Then, consensus is seen as being supportive of the diversity of the member-states, and these also have “enjoyed relative peace” after the Cold War by “including consensus as part of the formula” (Luqman, 2019, 11th para.). Lastly, it promotes equality as consensus makes the voices of smaller member-states to be as important as the more “prominent” member states in decision-making (Luqman, 2019, 12th para).

However, there are criticisms regarding the practice of non-intervention and consensus decision-making as it is considered a disadvantage of the region especially when addressing sensitive issues such as territorial disputes, and internal affairs that affect life and death situations caused by armed conflict and human rights violations. While ASEAN has been effective in their traditional “ASEAN Way,” in forging partnerships in the economic aspect, it has been observed that the association might lose credibility internationally and might lose appeal to at least some its members if there is no willingness to modify this kind of approach into a more *interventionary* one (Henderson, 1999 p.76 through Weber, 2009, p.16). During the 1990s, ASEAN have

made modifications to their approach such as “consensus minus” wherein a decision can be made without consensus provided that the member-states who did not make a consensus are unaffected (Henderson, 1999 p.48 through Weber, 2009, p. 16), and in 1998, which is “enhanced cooperation” where member-states could comment on their fellow member-states’ local activities if it affects regional concerns, but still without intervention from ASEAN (Narine, 2002, p.168 through Weber, 2009, p.16).

Aside from strengths and weaknesses of the practice of non-intervention and consensus-based decision-making of ASEAN that led to its maintenance of harmony among members, it is said that this harmony can only be felt at the level of member-states particularly the state leaders. Furthermore, this harmony was the result of the interests of these leaders being protected due to the prevailing practice of non-intervention and consensus-based decision making.

Forty years after its foundation, ASEAN, following the declaration of Bali Concorde II geared towards a "people-centered ASEAN" by beginning a process of transformation through the ASEAN Charter (Morada, 2008). Aside from the Charter which supposedly aimed at transforming ASEAN into a people-centric organization, the idea of transitioning from an organization to community was being materialized. The creation of three pillars with one of which is the Social-Cultural Community (SCC) Pillar aims to promote "greater political, economic, and social-cultural cooperation among the ten member states" and to be a space for addressing issues and promoting shared culture in support of building a people-centric community (ASEAN SCC Blueprint 2007).

Recently, ASEAN as a region faced another crisis since the Asian Financial Crisis in 1997, which is the COVID-19 pandemic. There were several reports regarding the response in the member-state level wherein efforts are still “to each of its own”

mentality as member-states resort to different approaches ranging from proactive ones such as in Singapore and Vietnam, to "draconian" ones wherein politicians and former military people take over as in the Philippines and Cambodia (IID, 2020) and the need to maintain their relationships with the superpowers amid the pandemic (Wangkiat, 2022). Then, there were some reports regarding ordinary people coping with the situation mostly in the socio-economic aspect (Morgan and Trinh, 2021). While most reports on ordinary people are either on the socio-economic and medical aspect, there are also on the socio-cultural aspect such as the report by Yuko Ito (2020), managing director of Hakuodo Institute of Life and Living ASEAN or HILL ASEAN, regarding how people are coping during the height of the pandemic. It was found out that more than ninety percent (90%) have felt that the pandemic has influenced their lives and three of the top five ways in coping with stress brought about by the pandemic is related to spending more time on their smartphones either through playing games, communicating through social media, or watching videos. In line with promoting shared culture and giving respect to it by recognition of its unity in diversity, the proposed study mainly focuses on understanding an interesting topic such as humor through stand-up comedy in the context of selected ASEAN member-states during a time of crisis faced by the region, particularly the COVID-19 pandemic.

Everything that is funny or with humor is rooted with comedy: from writing sitcoms, screenplays, and songs, into graphics such as in cartoons, advertisement, even writing for range of people from politicians to manufacturers, and performing onstage (Carter, 2001). If everyone has got something to sell, comedy "sells its best" (Carter, 2001, p. 20). That is why the focus in understanding humor is limited to stand-up comedy through the videos of the selected stand-up comedians from selected ASEAN member-states during the time of the COVID-19 pandemic.

Statement of the Problem

The intent of the proposed study is to learn about humor in selected ASEAN member-states through online stand-up comedy videos, published in social media sites. Specifically, the context from the performers and its viewers will be explored to emerge themes that will give understanding of humor of selected ASEAN member-states during a period of crisis.

With that, the overall question for the proposed research is, what does humor mean in the context of people in selected ASEAN member-states during a time of crisis? Through online comedy videos of original content by selected ASEAN stand-up comedians, here are more detailed inquiries that will bring development in the proposed study: what do the written materials and their delivery by the performers in the video mean in the context of humor? On the other hand, what do the viewers' reactions mean in terms of humor?

Objectives of the Study

The proposed study aims to:

1. Analyze the comedy videos published online during the chosen period of the pandemic, through the written materials and delivery by the performers.
2. Analyze the comments and reactions of the audiences both live and online in social media.
3. Generate meaning about the humor in selected ASEAN member countries based on the analyses on the performers and the audiences.

Scope and Delimitation

The chosen period for this study was the initial stages of the pandemic wherein vaccines are still under development, social mobility and physical contact are limited thus staying at home was the only option during this period, particularly from March 2020 to the beginning of third quarter of 2021. The observable drastic changes from the old norm prior to this pandemic are the reason for choosing this period of the pandemic.

There are plenty of social media platforms right now that let users watch a variety of videos. Most of these videos range from educational, informative on current events, and entertaining ones. For this study, one type of social media platform was given focus. The criteria for choosing such were the following: the greatest number of users in the ASEAN region, most accessible or user-friendly, and can display comprehensive details about a content particularly reactions represented by graphic symbols, and space to enter comments regarding the featured content. These features of the chosen social media platform should be present at the pre-vaccine period of the pandemic, which is from 2020 up to 2021.

For the study, four ASEAN member-states, two from the mainland and another two from the maritime ASEAN member-states have been chosen. The criteria for the selection of the ASEAN member-states of study were the following: number of active users of the chosen social media platform from ASEAN, the daily average time spent on social media, and the number of stand-up comedians who are active during the chosen period of the pandemic.

Two famous stand-up comedians from each chosen ASEAN member-state, particularly their recorded performance published in accessible streaming sites, became the focus of the study. The chosen performers are those who are actively

performing in the stand-up comedy industry during the chosen period and employs the observational type of stand-up comedy wherein the stand-up comedians write and act out something funny based on their everyday observation as opposed to other comedians in live performances where they pick on audiences as part of the material.

Each video should contain a complete structure of jokes, as explained by Judy Carter (2001), which is the set-up and the funny part. It does not necessarily have to be as long as a comedy special that usually runs an hour or more. If the video was a recorded live performance held prior to the pandemic but was uploaded during the chosen period of it, then it should also contain the following: a live venue whether it was recorded on a theater, comedy bar with stage, or a studio that was set up with a stage and seats with or without round tables or any setup equivalent to a theater or a comedy bar, and a live audience, who should be mostly are locals, with audible reactions. If the video itself was made during the chosen period, then the performer itself is already enough for the study as the reactions and comments from viewers online will be included in the textual analysis.

Definition of Terms

Stand-up Comedy - form of talk and implies a context that allows reaction, participation and engagement from the audiences whom the comedian is speaking (Brodie 2008) with the intention of making them laugh (Double 2005 p.18 in Hattingh 2018). The type of stand-up comedy that will be in focus is the observational type wherein the stand-up comedians write and act out something funny based on their everyday observation as opposed to other comedians in live performances where they pick on audiences as part of the material.

Stand-up Comedy Videos - videos published in free streaming sites and social media such as YouTube, and Facebook. These videos shall contain the following: the performer, and the audiences (if the videos were made through a locked-in video shoot).

Performer - pertains to the stand-up comedian featured in the videos for study. These stand-up comedians perform in solo acts, sort of doing speeches or monologues.

Audiences/Viewers - pertains to the audiences watching the performer who may be featured in the videos and those who viewed the videos via online. Audiences are not part of the act or performance, but they give reactions during it such as laughter, applause when they are part of the live audience, or reaction buttons and comment boxes found in social media platforms for online viewers.

Significance of the Study

As ASEAN is gearing itself towards a "people-centered ASEAN" (Morada, 2008), by the creation of three pillars, particularly the Socio-Cultural Community Pillar, this study has brought about the diversity of the culture of the ASEAN people particularly in the time when the regional community is challenged by a crisis thus giving respect to it by exploring breakthrough and interesting topics such as humor that may be deemed acceptable to ASEAN as an organization.

Chapter II

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Introduction

The following literature review consists of understanding humor in general, stand-up comedy from the West where it originated, stand-up comedy in Asia, and stand-up comedy in selected ASEAN countries. These studies discussed humor and stand-up comedy in different contexts, and even though there are already country and theme-specific studies of stand-up comedy in the ASEAN, the proposed study featuring online comedy videos by featured stand-up comedians in the ASEAN during a time of crisis would contribute in adding depth to cultural studies of the region in terms of humor through stand-up comedy.

Understanding Humor

Humor is based on incongruity and not the other way around as Jerry Farber (2007, p.68) has discussed in building the theory of humor because not all "instances of incongruity are not funny" such as brainteasers, logic problems, and puzzles. Furthermore, there are other incongruities that inspire other emotions such as fear and disgust (Farber, 2007, p.68). In building the theory of humor without stating these exceptions, the term "link" was used to cover the broad range of connection of incongruous elements that would build humor or to make it funny. It was discussed that one element, labeled as A is the "social norm" or any statement that is part of or accepted by the norm, and another element, labeled as B "counters, defy, or circumvent the A" (Farber, 2007, p.69). During the discussion, it is noted that for the link to inspire humor, the A is not entirely replaced by B but only countered, undermined, or circumvented by way of "playing off" against each other.

A more specific example to explain the A and the B can be described as the "setup" and the "funny" as discussed in the Comedy Bible by Judy Carter (2001), a veteran stand-up comedian. This is the structure of a joke or comedy material. The setup contains the serious part consisting of the attitude, topic, and premise, as these elements of the setup have a "ring of truth and honesty" (Carter, 2001, p.66). The role of the setup is to capture the attention of the audiences before making them laugh through what is funny. The topic is the subject, the attitude is the description of the topic (something weird, stupid, scary, or hard), and the premise is the "spin, slant, point-of-view, or observation" that answers the "attitude + topic" or what exactly is hard, weird, stupid, or scary about the topic through an insight and not mere description (Carter, 2001, p.67). An example would be "Do you know what's weird in relationships? You never meet someone when you really want to" (Carter, 2001, p.68). The attitude-topic is "weird in relationships" and the premise or insight is "you never meet someone when you really want to." After the setup, comes the funny part or the act-out. In this part, what the comedian wanted to specify from the general thought coming from the setup is being performed, instead of being just talked about (Carter, 2001, p.71). From the structure, the A is still present as the general thought from the setup and the B as the funny part would play around the A (and not replace it) by being specific through the act-out.

From the structure of a joke or comedy material that is based on incongruity comes its perception of the material by the audiences on the context of humor. Jerry Farber (2007) discussed the classification of humor that acknowledges the above-mentioned situation. The first two categories presented were based in the Superiority Theory: Derisive and Empathic Humor. The difference is that derisive humor is about laughing at others failures making our own failures superior to them. This usually is

applicable to people higher than the perceiver such as politicians, celebrities wherein the perceiver usually says "at least I'm not that bad" (Farber, 2007, p.78) or as worse as "serves you right." Empathic humor, on the other hand, is about laughing with others, usually those people the perceiver could relate to such as common employees, students wherein the perceiver usually says "Oh my God, that's me!" (Farber, 2007, p.78). Next category is the counter-restriction humor wherein the A corresponds to an internalized restriction on thought, feeling, or behavior and the B corresponds to the evasion or defiance of that restriction (Farber, 2007, p.78). Derisive type of humor may relate with this category as the "target is usually someone or something that it is not proper to be making fun of" (Farber, 2007, p.79) such as people in higher positions, institutions, group of people based on race, gender, and other physical and mental features.

Jason Rutter (1997) on the other hand, introduced a more integrated approach through the classical theories of humor which are Superiority, Incongruity, and Relief for his dissertation on stand-up comedy as an interaction. Though generally jokes are based on Incongruity as above-mentioned in the discussion by Jerry Farber (2007), there are different views of incongruity, and one of which is Superiority. Also known as disparagement (Suls 1977, McGhee & Duffey 1983, Zillman 1983 in Rutter, 1997, p.9), putdown (Zillman and Stocking 1976 in Rutter 1997, p.9) and deprecatory humor (Davies 1991a in Rutter, 1997, p.9), superiority theory suggests that humor is "essentially if not ubiquitously, aggressive" and of "ridicule, the ludicrous, and the grotesque" (Rutter, 1997, p.9). It requires those who laugh and appreciate a joke view themselves as better than the objects of humor through the joke or comedy material (Rutter, 1997, p.9). Though this kind of humor is directed against those who we may perceive as inferior to ourselves (Aristotle 1977 in Rutter, 1997, p.9), such ridicule,

which is considered deformation, is forbidden by law (Ethics, Book IV, Chapter 8, p. 168 in Rutter, 1997, p.9). So, for it to become socially responsible in joking, the object of humor must have “some small evil” wherein it is somehow “deserving the derision and scorn of the joker” (Descartes, Article 178 in Rutter, 1997, p.10). Others call it “sudden glory” wherein laughter is the result of “an abrupt recognition of meaning or status” (Leviathan, 1651/1974 in Rutter, 1997, p.11), while others view it as “social gesture” that emphasizes failures or mistakes (termed as deviants by Rutter, 1997, p.11) into improvement or correction. This type of humor may be present in political jokes in particular how member-states in the government level respond to the pandemic and social jokes wherein they joke about not practicing health protocols such as improper wearing of face masks.

The next type of humor discussed by Rutter (1997) is based on Relief Theory. This tends to be based on “variations of what might be called the 'head-of-steam principle' wherein “something, whether it be ‘psychic energy’ (Freud, 1905/1976 in Rutter, 1997, p.13) or “nerve force” (Spencer, 1911 in Rutter, 1997, p.13) builds up within a person’s system and having no more useful purpose, must be released (Rutter, 1997, p.13). It assumes that this “build-up of surplus energy is inefficient if not detrimental to physical or psychosocial well-being” which is why a “spontaneous release is necessary rather than a slow dissipation” (Rutter, 1997, p.13). While this tends to be theories on laughter than humor, and it clings to the medical aspect as it argues that laughter provides health benefits, it is still relevant to the study in contextualizing humor through the online reactions of the viewers of the videos made by stand-up comedians.

Stand-up Comedy in the West

The following journals introduce stand-up comedy and its developments from the countries where it started, United States and Canada. It was discussed in these articles how stand-up comedy is more than entertainment as it also affects the society particularly the sensitive issues revolving around it.

This is a dissertation focusing on stand-up comedy and it was the chosen study by the author because even if “comic performances have fulfilled an important social function” throughout the history of civilization, it has not “attracted the serious academic inquiry one might expect” (Jenkins, 2015, p.6). The objective was to bring into discussion that stand-up comedy performances are “a vital part of modern American intellectual and social life and are enmeshed in ongoing processes of progressive social change” (Jenkins 2015, p.7). It was found out through “critical examination of the construction and performances of the comic persona, close analysis of the comic routine as an aesthetic text, and examination of social dramas” and generated discourses to determine their contribution to social change, that the comedians featured in the study could be a “potent mediator, transgressive initiator or a subversive healer” and the study itself contributes to various fields such as communication, sociology, performance studies and post-colonialism (Jenkins 2015, pp.184-186).

Russell Peters is a stand-up comedian who is a Canadian citizen and of South Asian descent. His set of jokes are mostly stereotypes of most races residing in Canada, both minorities and dominant ones: a style in stand-up that is usually observed in its place of origin, in North America. This paper explores the hypothesis on comedy in general being a safe space for “racialized discourse” (Hirji, 2009, p.582) with focus on Russell Peters and his race-based jokes. It was found out that comedy

in whatever type (stand-up, film, or television) has a potential for a public space or sphere, but not entirely a safe one for the above-mentioned discourse because such as in the case of Peters, his jokes may be laughed and appreciated by audiences of different races, but this appreciation and approval may also bring negative-effects such as “reinforcement of racist beliefs, insult to minority groups, and the marginalization of talk about race” (Hirji, 2009, p.583). Even though Peters have stated that his purpose is to make the people laugh, one should realize the fact stated in the study that comedy and any form of communication has risks wherein a specific reception of a particular message is not guaranteed (Hall 1980, Morley 1980 cited in Hirji, 2009, p.583): some may not get the joke, leading to misinterpretations from both the subject of the joke who might get offended and people of bigotry who have its usual racial beliefs getting validated. Aside from this main finding, it was discovered that the reception of a joke and the performance of the comedian depends on various factors such as race, position or role, and personal cultural experiences of both the performer and the audience.

As observed in the two studies, these are in the context of the understanding the brand of humor that is performed by the comedians, reacted by the audiences in the West particularly Canada and North America. Though these studies contribute to the knowledge of stand-up comedy and humor in general, further studies must be conducted to understand these concepts in the context of selected ASEAN countries where the scene is present, through the use of videos from a chosen social media platform, which is the main purpose of this study.

Stand-up Comedy in Asia

The following articles support the evidence that stand-up comedy, a culture based in Europe and America, has penetrated other continents such as Asia. In fact,

it is considered as the new potential venue for stand-up comedy wherein it discusses the comparison between the content of the jokes in the featured Vietnamese comedian and his counterparts from the countries of origin of stand-up comedy. It was mentioned that the compared to the ones in America and Europe wherein comedians poke fun on people of different races thus racist jokes, Asian comedians tend to joke on topics such as family traditions and other social issues but making themselves the butt of the joke by sharing the experiences related to it such as dating, etc. (Le, quoted by Nguyen-Owku, 2017, 3rd para.) due to the embedded Confucian and Buddhist traditions which value politeness and respect (McGraw, quoted by Nguyen-Owku, 2017, 5th para.). In other words, if the joke was directly pertained to the audience, they might get offended that is why the comedians in Asia tend to “take a stab at themselves” thus describing Asia in terms of comedy as “still in the slapstick phase” (Le, quoted by Nguyen-Owku, 2017 6th para.).

Not only developed countries such as North America, Europe and Canada are becoming venues for stand-up comedy but also to developing countries such as India as well. As in situations in developing countries, freedom of speech is also challenged in India particularly when it comes to criticisms against the government (Nüske, 2018). Given this situation, stand-up comedians, especially the Hindi-speaking comedians who use their set of jokes as form of resistance against the shift of leadership in the government receive lack of support from those in power through censorship that leads to limited reach to lower caste and worse, receive numerous death threats and hate statements (Nüske, 2018). English-speaking Indian comedians experience nearly the same as in terms of reach, their content is accessed by middle and upper caste who can afford internet connection despite the censorship in free radio and television compared to the target audiences of the Hindi-speaking ones who can't afford enough

to have an internet connection (Nüske, 2018). This study is relevant as it tackles the socio-political angle of stand-up comedy at the point of view of those in authority and power.

Again, these are the same case as in the previous studies of stand-up comedy and humor in the West. Though these studies focus on Asia, the diverse culture of the continent though there are some commonalities due to the mobility of influences during the early trade do not necessarily can support the context of understanding humor in the selected ASEAN countries during a time of crisis.

Stand-up Comedy in ASEAN

Lia Afidah and Ribut Wahyudi (2014) have helped discovered the evolution of comedy in Indonesia through its stand-up comedy by analyzing the dynamics of the performer, the audiences, and the relationship of the two, through a framework based on developing studies particularly the conversation analysis on the opening and closing styles of three Indonesian comedians on a typical performance in a stand-up comedy show that were transcribed using videos of their performances available on a famous streaming video site, YouTube. It was found out that the opening and closing styles of the sample of three comedians have some similarities with Rutter's pattern, which is derived from the proposed seven moves in a conventional stand-up comedy by Jason Rutter (1997 in Afidah and Wahyudi, 2014).

From the opening and closing styles of some Indonesian stand-up comedians, the discussion shifts into the contents of the jokes itself. In the case of Malaysia as studied by Helen Tan and Onn, et al. (2018) wherein a comparison was made of the text structures and use of politeness strategies of Malaysian ethnic and political stand-up comedies. It was found out that most ethnic comedies are using the clarity

approach to prevent generalization among ethnic groups while ambiguity was used on most political comedies to prevent persecution from existing censorship laws.

Research Gap

From the related literature, the existing theories on humor may be utilized in analyzing selected stand-up online comedy videos to understand it in the context of the scene in selected ASEAN countries in the time of the pre-vaccine period of the pandemic. Though there are featured studies on stand-up comedy in ASEAN countries such as in Malaysia and Indonesia as discussed above, the opening and closing styles in the case of the study in Indonesia, and focusing on certain types of jokes such as political and ethnic ones featured in Malaysia contributed in initial understanding of humor through stand-up comedy in ASEAN but for this study it will focus on a certain period particularly a period of crisis.

Chapter III

METHODOLOGY

Research Framework

The online comedy videos paved the way, and are not the sole sources in understanding humor in selected ASEAN member-states during a period of crisis as the activities involved around these videos such as composition and production by the stand-up comedians, the reception and reaction by the audiences both live and online through social media, and the socio-cultural and socio-political context behind these activities became the significant and necessary factors.

Research Design

Research design refers to the "structure of inquiry" wherein it is a logical matter rather than a logistical one (De Vaus, 2001, p.16). Since the study involved understanding humor through online comedy videos by stand-up comedians from selected ASEAN member-states, a type of research design under the flexible method research (Anastas, 1999), particularly the case study design became appropriate as flexible method research is "aimed at generating in-depth understandings of people and events in context as they naturally occur" (Anastas, 1999, p.73) and case study design is defined as an "empirical inquiry that investigates a contemporary

phenomenon within its real-life context, especially when the boundaries of phenomenon and context are not clearly evident" (Yin, 1994, p. 13 in Anastas, 1999, p.94). Since it focuses on a single unit (Gilgun, 1994; Patton, 1990; Ruckdeschel, Earnshaw, & Firrek, 1994 in Anastas, 1999, p.93), and it can be a group of people (Anastas, 1999), the comedians and the audiences both live and online performing and watching stand-up comedy respectively from selected ASEAN member-states would represent the single unit.

Research Method: Introduction to Textual Analysis

Textual analysis is "an educated guess at some of the most likely interpretations that might be made of that text" (Mckee, 2001, p.3). To discover likely interpretations of a text, one thing is important: context (Mckee, 2001, p.11). Compared against other methods such as audience research and content analysis, textual analysis is applicable in the proposed study because the main goal is to find context through interpretation of the text compared to audience research which produces more text rather than interpretation, and to content analysis wherein it is replicable and quantitative but it is no more objective or unchallengeable than other forms of textual analysis and still relies on the interpretation of texts (Mckee, 2001).

Assumptions

Jason Rutter (1997) and Jerry Farber (2007) both discussed the classical theories of humor such as Incongruity, Superiority, and Relief that will be discussed in the review of related literature later on. Based on the understanding of these theories and existing reports regarding the situation of the region, organization, and its member-states, assumptions could be developed for this study. First is relevant to the member-states response at the government level with the pandemic. As cited in reports by media outlets such as IID (2020) and Rappler (2020), most responses by

the government are reactive while few are proactive during the initial stage of the crisis, such as Vietnam and Singapore. While most of them were perceived as reactive by ordinary people, these respective governments claim that their decision-making and its implementation are effective and efficient. Some people react through serious commentaries, while others such as artists, particularly critical stand-up comedians, use their talents to creatively call out the loopholes of the response which the member-states at the government level claim effective and well-thought out. Consequently, ordinary citizens viewing these content appreciate and laugh at these with the inference that it is based on a hybrid of superiority through derision, and relief because the object of humor has some “small evil” as discussed above, which can be represented by the government claiming that their responses are effective though the effectiveness could not be reflected in the feedback of the recipients of these responses, and relief because someone has addressed these issues in a creative and funny way. The study did not use medical measurements regarding relief but used their comments in social media as part of the textual analysis.

From the government as objects of humor in political jokes related to the pandemic, ordinary people may become objects of humor particularly their practices in health protocols such as improper wearing of protective gears and unsanitary practices. As opposed to political jokes, social jokes like this, which is also laughed and appreciated by its viewers may be of superiority through empathy and also relief because the aim for making fun of the improper practice may be for correction, or social gesture as discussed by Bergson (in Rutter, 1997) that emphasizes deviants such as these for improvement or correction. Again, the comments and reactions of the viewers for this joke will be used as part of the textual analysis that will be also discussed in the methodology.

Lastly, there might be videos of live comedy performances from not-so-distant past particularly months or days before the pandemic lockdown that were uploaded during the lockdown itself. For these videos, there might be themes of relief brought about the nostalgia of being in a live performance in front of a stand-up comedian, or nostalgia of the topics being brought about in comedy materials before the pandemic happened. All of the objects of study, from the comedy materials, how it was delivered, and the reactions of the viewers will be analyzed and contextualized in a comprehensive manner, which will be discussed in the methodology. From these findings integrated with comprehensive discussion, themes could emerge on what could be said about the humor of ASEAN people from selected member-states, which should be given emphasis and respected as part of the culture of a region, in a certain period of crisis.

Research Procedure: Transcription of Stand-Up Comedy Videos

In the study by Jason Rutter (1997) of stand-up comedy as an interaction, it was discussed that stand-up is like a conversation between comedian and the audience. That is why the use of Conversation Analysis (CA) and its findings can be generalized to it. Even though it is "simplified in form," it is considered a conversation as stand-up comedy "still involves of taking of turns between performer and audience to build up the flow of the performance and are organized to a large extent" in parallel with the rules for the organization of conversation by Sacks, Schegloff, and Jefferson (1974 in Rutter, 1997, p.44) wherein any conversation with rules governing turn-taking, it is "fairly safe" to assume that "forms of interaction other than natural conversation that display these rules can be contained as a sub-category of conversation" (discussed by Rutter, 1997, p.92). Also, stand-up comedy is as same as conversation in terms of "collaborative production" (Atkinson, Cuff and Lee, 1978, p. 136 in Rutter,

1997, p.92) wherein it is "made possible by the active involvement of those make up the interaction" such as "people attending a comedy venue are co-oriented towards stand-up comedy" (Rutter, 1997, p.92). Though CA is originally designed as a tool for analysis of naturally-occurring conversations, its application to stand-up is "in no way deviant when held against the broader history of discipline" as it is also used in others such as political speechmaking and televised interviews (Atkinson, 1984, Heritage and Greatbatch, 1986 and 1990, Clayman, 1988, 1992, and 1993, in Rutter, 1997). These projects have the same talk parameters that have the same structures as stand-up comedy (Rutter, 1997, p.92). CA is "specifically important" in studying stand-up comedy as it helps overcome some of the limitations of previous studies on joking, laughter, and stand-up comedy (Rutter, 1997, p.92). It studies the impure, stresses live context, based on mutual knowledge, and stresses on sequential organization (Rutter, 1997, p.94). CA is also useful in its "insistence on the audio or video recording of source material and then its close transcription" as it recognizes "vital differences between the spoken word and written language rather than seeing the former as a debasement of the latter that views it as distinct" and create a "valid and reliable representation" of real-life conversation experience (Rutter, 1997, p.96). It does not only document what was said but how it was said, and it will not put readers "at a major disadvantage" should they have no access to the live talk or recording of it (Rutter, 1997, p.96) or in the case of this proposed study, it will help to save time in separately accessing the videos while reading this study.

Those discussed above are the reasons why conversation analysis will be part of the textual analysis of stand-up comedy videos. In this manner, the system of transcription that will be applied is based on previous studies on stand-up comedy particularly from the study by Ian Brodie (2008) regarding stand-up comedy as a genre

of intimacy. This is applicable to the study as Brodie (2008, p.164) used this to "indicate a variety of audience responses and to demonstrate performance rhythm." Also, this system would be less complicated to understand for the future readers of this thesis. Before proceeding with the transcription of the videos, there will be an introduction to the letters and symbols to be used alongside the performances that were transcribed into words. The introduction was written as such:

For the transcription of the performance, the system developed by Ian Brodie (2008, p.164) in his study of stand-up comedy as a genre of intimacy was applied as it had goals to "indicate a variety of audience responses and to demonstrate performance rhythm." Bracketed letters ([L]) will indicate a reaction of the audience. The following are the letters and their corresponding reactions:

A = Applause

Aw = Awwing (a sound of disappointment, sadness or regret)

B = Boos

C = Cheers

H = Hissing

L = Laughter

O = Oooing (a sound of recognition of a taboo topic)

S = Silence

W = Whooping

Colons (:) indicate simultaneous reactions occurring and while an arrow (--->) indicates a transition from one reaction after another. Words within angle brackets indicate recognizable words from the audience ([<yeah!]), words within exclamation points indicate a reaction from a single audience member, and a symbol for male or female indicate a gendered reaction. Line breaks occur at prolonged pauses, audience

interruptions, or to indicate the "cadence of the line" (Brodie, 2008). Italicized words are specifically emphasized, underlined words indicate that the reaction of the audience is sustained but the performer is taking over or during the reactions, and ellipses indicate false starts. Curly brackets indicate performer's gestures, facial expressions and other non-verbal cues ({eyes open wide while his face is directed towards the audience}), and words in quotation indicate the tone or accent. Ellipses in brackets on their own line indicate a non-transcribed section (Brodie, 2008).

That is how the introduction would be written prior to the transcription and analysis itself. To further understand how this works before proceeding to the transcription of videos during data collection and analysis, here is a sample from the same study by Ian Brodie (2008) of a transcribed performance from Chris Rock, who is a famous actor and comedian, and its short analysis:

Alright

Things are going alright

I can not complain

Doing my *special*

Doing a new *movie*

Got a new *TV show*

Successful black man [A:C]

So you know, you know what's next right?

White Girl. [L---->B]

Got to get a white girl

Can not be a successful black man without a white girl [L]

They won't even let you buy a mansion without a white girl

"Here's a million dollars." {nasal} "Where's your white girl?" [L]

"We *have zoning restrictions.*" [L]

You know what's funny? You know what's funny? If you're black and you go out with a white girl, everything that goes wrong in your life people blame it on the white girl [L]

Everything. It's like "Yo man, I heard Chris got hit by a bus."

"*Fucking around them white girls.*" [L]

"Yeah. I hear Chris broke his leg." "White girl." [L]

"*That's what he gets.*"

People are bugged, man. There's like, you know, there's white girls who only go out with black guys. There's black girls who only go out with white guys. I *met* a black girl like that. Did *not date black men*. I said "Girl, how come you don't date no black men?" She said, "No reason."

"*No reason.*"

No reason?

So I punched her in the face. [L]

Now she got a reason [L] (Rock, 1994 in Brodie, 2008)

In this performance, Rock "anticipates and builds into the text the interaction with the audience, and the audience not only recognizes his 'successful black man claim' but praises it and reaffirms it." Do note the shift from laughter following the "got to get a white girl" to "good-natured dissent" in that the audience actively sending "boos" to him. Of the entire routine, "only the final bit about punching the woman approximates a joke inasmuch as it has a pattern of set-up and punch line that would not require else to repeat, and can be easily amended to different contexts (Brodie, 2008).

The transcription discussed above was applicable for live performances of videos of not-so-distant period before the pandemic that were uploaded during the chosen period but for the online video that were made during the pandemic, only the comedy material, particularly the verbal and non-verbal cues from the performer, and the online reactions and comments of the viewers were documented and contextualized. The language chosen in the transcription and documentation of the videos and comments from social media is English and if there are performances and comments that used ASEAN member-state languages, these have been translated using Google Translate and the translation to English feature in Facebook not only

because it is the "most important language to learn for the increasingly mobile community, official language of the business and scientific world, (Schütz, 2005 in Rao, 2018), and facilitates the international mobility of young researchers" (Graddol, 2006 in Rao, 2018), but also because the transcription would be easily read and understood alongside its analysis.

The full transcription is available in Appendix A, but excerpts of these along with analysis is in the main part, and afterwards, these were collated through a matrix that will serve as a summary of what has been discussed in the course of this thesis. The matrix looked like this:

ASEAN Member-State	Stand-Up Comedian	Written Material and Performance	Summary of Reactions and Comments
Member-State 1	Comedian 1		
	Comedian 2		
Member-State 2	Comedian 1		
	Comedian 2		
Member-State 3	Comedian 1		
	Comedian 2		
Member-State 4	Comedian 1		
	Comedian 2		

Chapter IV

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

Selection of Social Media Platform and ASEAN Member-States

Fig.1. Social Media Platforms Used (GWI, Q1 2021, in Kemp, 2021)

Fig.2. Average Daily Time Spent Using the Internet (GWI, Q3 2020 in Kemp, 2021)

One of the criteria for the selection of ASEAN member-states to be studied is the average of the time spent daily using the internet. In the presentation by Simon Kemp (2021), CEO of Kepios and chief analyst for DataReportal, companies that are studying social media users, he discussed first the overall average daily time spent by people aged sixteen (16) to sixty-four (64) years old in a survey conducted in the third quarter of 2020 and published in January 2021. It can be observed that five of the ASEAN member-states spent above the worldwide average with the Philippines leading with an average use of ten (10) hours and fifty-six (56) minutes, followed by Malaysia with nine (9) hours and seventeen (17) minutes of daily average use, then Indonesia with eight (8) hours and fifty-two (52) minutes, followed closely by Thailand with eight (8) hours and forty-four (44) minutes and lastly followed by Singapore with eight (8) hours and seven (7) minutes. Other member-states particularly Vietnam as seen in the report clocked below the world's average daily time spent in the internet with six (6) hours and forty-seven (47) minutes as compared with the worldwide average of six (6) hours and fifty-four (54) minutes.

Q3 2020														
ASEAN Member States	Total Active Social Media Users (in M)	Social Media Users Percentage of Total Population (in %)	Annual Change in the Number of Users (in %)	Mobile Phone Users (in M)	Average Daily Time Users Aged 16-64 Spent in Internet	Average Time Users Aged 16-64 Spent in Social Media	Online Content Activities		Most Used Social Media Platforms		Mobile Application with the Most Number of Active Users	Percentage of Mobile Phone Users (in %)	Facebook Users in Any Mobile Phone (in %)	Top Youtube Search Queries
Myanmar	29	53.1	31.8	28.94	no data	no data	no data		no data		no data	99.8	99.8	Myanmar, Song, Music, Movies, DJ
Laos	3.6	49.1	16.1	3.58	no data	no data	no data		no data		no data	99.5	99.5	Karaoke, Tiktok, Doraemon, Tony TV
Cambodia	12	71.3	23.7	11.89	no data	no data	no data		no data		no data	99.1	99.1	Song, Remix, Tiktok, Remix 2020, Khmer Song
Brunei	0.435	99	7.3	0.432	no data	no data	no data		no data		no data	99.3	99.3	Song, Lagu, Karaoke, Upin Ipin, Upin
Vietnam	72	73.7	10.8	71.14	6H 47M	2H 21M	Watch Videos (97%)		Youtube, Facebook		Facebook	98.8	98.8	Phim, Nhac, Remix, Karaoke, Tiktok
Thailand	55	78.7	5.8	54.62	8H 44M	2H 48M	Watch Videos (99%)		Youtube, Facebook		Facebook	99.3	99.3	BTS, Blackpink
Philippines	89	80.7	21.9	87.84	10H 56M	4H 15M	Watch Videos (94%)		Youtube, Facebook		Facebook	98.7	98.7	Song, Movie, Tiktok, Movies, Karaoke
Malaysia	28	86	7.7	27.83	9H 17M	3H 1M	Watch Videos (98.1%)		Youtube, WhatsApp		WhatsApp (Facebook)	99.4	99.4	Movie, Lagu, Songs, Song, Malaysia
Indonesia	170	61.8	6.3	168.5	8H 52M	3H 14M	Watch Videos (98.5%)		Youtube, WhatsApp		WhatsApp (Facebook)	99.1	99.1	Lagu, DJ, Film, Cover, Karaoke
Singapore	4.96	84.4	4.3	4.9	8H 07M	2H 17M	Watch Videos (95.9%)		Youtube, WhatsApp		WhatsApp (Facebook)	98.8	98.8	Songs, Singapore, Music, Baby, Roblox

Table 1: Internet and Social Media Users in Q3 2020

Q3 2021-early 2022														
ASEAN Member States	Total Active Social Media Users (in M)	Social Media Users Percentage of Total Population (in %)	Annual Change in the Number of Users (in %)	Mobile Phone Users (in M)	Average Daily Time Users Aged 16-64 Spent in Internet	Average Time Users Aged 16-64 Spent in Social Media	Main Reasons For Using The Internet	Most Watched Online Video Content	Favorite Social Media Platforms	Types of Social Media Accounts Followed	Mobile Application with the Most Number of Active Users	Percentage of Mobile Phone Users (in %)	Facebook Users in Any Mobile Phone (in %)	Top Youtube Search Queries
Myanmar	20.75	53.1	31.8	28.94	no data	no data	no data	no data	no data		no data	99.8	99.8	Myanmar, Song, Music, Mahar, DJ
Laos	3.8	51.1	5.6	3.58	no data	no data	no data	no data	no data		no data	99.5	99.5	Karaoke, Tiktok, Doraemon, Tony TV
Cambodia	12.6	73.9	5	11.89	no data	no data	no data	no data	no data		no data	98.9	98.9	Song, Remix, Tiktok, Remix 2021, ABC
Brunei	0.565	116.5	18.7	0.432	no data	no data	no data	no data	no data		no data	99.2	99.2	Lagu, Karaoke, Upin Ipin, Tiktok, Baby
Vietnam	76.95	78.1	6.9	71.14	6H 38M	2H 28M	Staying In Touch with Friends and Family (1st), Watching Videos (4th)	Comedy/Viral/Meme (6th)	Facebook	People You Know (1st), Actors/Comedians/Performers (2nd)	Facebook	98.8	98.8	Karaoke, Nhac, GAY, GAY TV MEDIA, MA
Thailand	56.85	81.2	3.4	54.62	9H 06M	2H 59M	Finding Information (1st), Watching Videos (3rd)	Comedy/Viral/Meme (3rd)	Facebook	People You Know (1st), Actors/Comedians/Performers (3rd)	Facebook	96.2	99.3	BTS, Blackpink
Philippines	92.05	82.4	3.4	87.84	10H 27M	4H 06M	Finding Information (1st), Watching Videos (4th)	Comedy/Viral/Meme (3rd)	Facebook	People You Know (1st), Actors/Comedians/Performers (2nd)	Facebook	98.7	98.7	Song, Movie, Tiktok, Movies, Karaoke
Malaysia	30.25	91.7	8	27.83	9H 10M	3H 2M	Finding Information (1st), Watching Videos (5th)	Comedy/Viral/Meme (3rd)	WhatsApp, Facebook	People You Know (1st), Actors/Comedians/Performers (2nd)	WhatsApp (Facebook)	99.4	99.4	Movie, Lagu, Song, Remix, DJ
Indonesia	191.4	68.9	12.6	168.5	8H 36M	3H 17M	Finding Information (1st), Watching Videos (6th)	Comedy/Viral/Meme (3rd)	WhatsApp, Instagram, Facebook	People You Know (1st), Memes (2nd), Actors/Comedians/Performers (4th)	WhatsApp (Facebook)	99.1	99.1	Lagu, DJ, Film, Karaoke, Tiktok
Singapore	5.3	89.5	6.9	4.9	7H 29M	2H 31M	Finding Information (1st), Watching Videos (5th)	Comedy/Viral/Meme (3rd)	WhatsApp, Facebook	People You Know (1st), Actors/Comedians/Performers (4th) Entertainment and Memes (5th)	WhatsApp (Facebook)	98.8	98.8	Songs, Singapore, Music, Baby, Roblox

Table 2: Internet and Social Media Users from Q3 2021-2022

Other criteria for the selection of social media platform and ASEAN member-states that should be studied in relevance to the thesis are number of active users in social media, the most preferred social media application, top reasons for using the internet and social media, their interest on comedy videos, and what they usually search on other video streaming platforms. Though the study focuses on comedy videos, it would be significant to present the top searches on other video streaming platforms during the chosen period that would open for future studies regarding ASEAN people in the context of the internet and social media during the time of the pandemic.

In order to delimit the study without developing any bias based on assumptions, it would be appropriate to collate earlier studies on each ASEAN member-state regarding internet and social media usage during the chosen period. Simon Kemp published country-specific reports (2021 and 2022) that covered the period of third quarter of 2020 up to the third quarter of 2021. Please do note that the report published during 2020 covered the period before the pandemic thus it is not relevant in the study. From the report published in 2021 containing the data of internet and social media users during the third quarter of 2020 (see Table 1 above), six (6) out of ten (10) ASEAN member-states have more detailed data, which are Vietnam, Thailand, the Philippines, Malaysia, Indonesia, and Singapore, compared to the remaining four member-states. Though it also has significant details such as number of active social media users and the percentages versus each total population, the more detailed reports from the 6 ASEAN member-states present a comprehensive picture of what people are actually doing during their time with the internet and social media and how long do they spend time with it. Generally, people from all ASEAN member-states search music videos both from foreign and local artists, Karaoke, a kind of music video with lyrics flashed on the screen so that the viewers could sing with it, and viral videos in YouTube, one of the most preferred free video streaming platform. In the more detailed reports from the 6 ASEAN member-states, almost all users choose to watch online videos. Social media too can stream videos, such as the most preferred social media platform as seen in the report, which is Facebook. This platform is more interactive than YouTube as one can express one's reaction through choosing and then clicking or pressing emojis or graphical representation of what the audience feel about the video, should one opt to not give comment regarding the viewed material.

The report published in 2022 (see Table 2 above) gave a more comprehensive detail compared to what was published during the previous year especially in the case of the 6 ASEAN member-states as the reports do not only contain the active social media users and its percentage when compared to the total population of each member-state but also other details such as reasons for using the internet, what kind of videos most people watch, and the type of social media accounts people follow mostly in Facebook.

Watching videos remain one of the top five (5) reasons for using the internet in the case of Vietnam, Thailand, the Philippines, Malaysia, and Singapore. However in what type of videos most people watch, the results varied compared to the results showing the top 5 reasons for using the internet. Thailand, the Philippines, Indonesia, Malaysia, and Singapore placed comedy, viral and meme videos as the third (3rd) most watched videos and in social media, accounts actors, comedians, and performers, together with accounts by entertainment shows and memes are a few of the most followed accounts.

Featured Comedians and their Videos

Note: Full text version of the videos are located in Appendix A though this was reminded in every video description below. Italicized words in paragraphs aligned center are the excerpts of the videos to support the following analyses.

Annie Yang (Indonesia)

Annie Yang Video: This is a recorded performance of a stand-up comedian from Indonesia but with Chinese descend, Annie Yang. In her set, she talks about online dating by starting to introduce herself through her family background (See full text version in Appendix A)

Annie Yang Video Analysis

Annie Yang from Indonesia, picked an aspect of her personal life and played it with her issues on dating and on conspiracy theories about the COVID-19 virus such as that the vaccine made to fight the virus has microchips, which were allegedly developed by Bill Gates (Ullah et.al., 2021).

Yeah, and at that time, when you have a near-dead experience, you just kind of like thinking about your life, your life just like flashes in front of you and then when at that moment, when my sister (is) choking me, I, I realized like you know, I'm sorry. I'm kind of like emotional every time I talk about my family. So that time, I realized that...I like being choked [gradual L]. So, you know right every time I have sex with a guy, and I, I asked him to choke me and I was like "this is what you got? [few people L] this is what you called 'choking'? [L---->A] My sister can do it better!" [L and A together]

The serious part was she was allegedly physically abused by her sister through choking and the funny part was she felt that the choking by someone whom she has having sex with was not that hard enough compared to what her sister has done to her.

Tinder is, Tinder is an app. You can download it for free, right? It's an app for you to choose someone you want to ahh...fuck [few people L] It's basically a fuck app. [one person giggled] But I don't know if you know this but do you know that there's this such thing as Tinder Surprise. And you don't know right? Like I will tell you this: Tinder surprise...is when you match with someone you decided to meet with them...when you met with them, they look nothing like their profile. [small L]

Then she shifted to her take on online dating mobile applications such as Tinder wherein she mentioned it as a "fuck app" or where you could meet someone just to

have sex with, and most of the pictures used for their profile are not exactly the same or totally different with how they look in real life.

I was like, "Thank God, it he's not a 'Tinder Surprise'. [two people L] Oh, he's fit, He's good looking, I bet he has a huge dick so, so he was there. He enters the restaurant, he approached me...And I swear to God in my life, I never have anyone say these words to me. It feels magical, it feels amazing. You know like when he arrived like he approached me. He looked at me in my eyes and then he said, "so you are one of those people who believe in Corona, yeah?" {giggled a bit} What the fuck! And conspiracy theories?! Really?! {continues being funny about what she had told} [some people L]...Like, you know but I was at that time I was naive. No. Like, I was horny. [two people L] I was like, thinking, "you know what Annie? It doesn't matter what the size is, the most important thing is how he used it." Right? I was such a fool. [few people L] And so I was there laying you know. Just kind of like "make it quick..." He did [L--->C] Uh and then...I shit you not, right? Like and then when he just like thrust his hip like that, right? And then just kind of like his breath getting raggedy and then he shouts like "COVID vaccine has microchip!" [few people L] And I was like "what the fuck!" I had so many questions, one, like, "did he shout out every conspiracy theories every time he's about to come? [L] Or he's thinking about COVID vaccine when he...when he like five seconds he's inside me [L]

She built this up that she was fortunate to meet someone who is good looking both in the picture and in real life, but the funny or playful part is that the guy happened to be one of those who believe in conspiracy theories about COVID-19 virus. It could not be verified whether it really happened to her as interviews are not included in the study, but what should be focused here is how serious situations and issues were creatively put together to make it humorous.

Reggie Hasibuan (Indonesia)

Reggie Hasibuan Video: This is also a recorded performance of another stand-up comedian from Indonesia, Reggie Hasibuan, who calls himself the first English-speaking Indonesian stand-up comedian, in front of a live audience at the time of the pandemic, as can be noted in the title of the video, "Stand-up Asia! Bali, featuring Reggie Hasibuan. How COVID-19 is nothing compared to all viruses that are already in Bali..." (See full text version in Appendix A)

Reggie Hasibuan Video Analysis

*Om swastiastu!...or if you're hiding from your parents in Java, then
"Assalamualaikum"! [L] Some call them Indo girls, some call them local girls, I call
them Only Fans content creator! [women only L]*

The comedy set of Reggie Hasibuan could be relatable to the audience since it revolves around the culture of Bali from its traditional greeting such as *Om swastiastu*, which can be traced to Hindu traditions which is a "prayer for salvation, a word of thanksgiving, and a greeting" (Nurhadi et al, 2020, p.63). From where this greeting was discussed, it was also studied that the future motives of using this greeting were "self-existence and tolerance" while past motives from it were due to "internal encouragement, the spirit of nationality, a sense of nationalism, and the principle of neutrality" (Nurhadi et al, 2020, p.63). The experience of saying this inclined towards positive and pleasant experiences that are "feeling valued, getting new political relations, good treatment, sympathy and growing solidarity between people" (Nurhadi et al, 2020, p.63). Though Reggie mentioned that if the audiences are "hiding from their parents in Java, the greeting should be '*Assalamualaikum*'." in which the audience laughed. The context here is that the dominant religion in Java is Islam, with its history of its dominance in an article by van der Kroef (1961). Then he turned his

attention to the women wherein despite they are called "Indo or local girls," he would still call them "OnlyFans content creator," to which the women laughed. OnlyFans is a mobile application or a website that serves as an internet content subscription service, wherein a content creator, through live streaming videos, can earn money from users as audiences, or "fans" who subscribe to their content on a monthly basis (Jankowicz, 2020, 5th para.). In the context of Indonesia, this became popular among sex workers amid draconian Pornography Law that made women earn "pretty good money" during the pandemic ("Ronny" in an interview by Azwar, 2021).

Ladies and gentlemen! My name is Reggie Hasibuan and I am the first English-speaking comedian from this country! [C] And it's not easy you know, becoming comedian because I got stereotype(d) all the time. I was in Singapore and you know I also addressed my nation, like "Indonesiaa! make some noiiiise!" And the only applause I got were from the dishwashers [L] Even there, they were applauding awkwardly [L] They were like: {acting out the dishwashers by clapping slowly and softly with a facial expression equivalent of someone confused} [L] {then still acting out as dishwasher talking to another} "Bro...bro...bro, indo bro, indo bro!" [L--->C--->L] {then shifted to fellow dishwasher as if replying} "oh yeah! what is he doing on stage? [L] He should be here with us washing dishes! [L] Very not appropriate!...Not appropriate!" [L] (When) I was in Malaysia, the same thing! They asked me, "hey! where are you from?" I answered honestly, "Indonesia!" {then he shifted to the one who is asking as he replied} "Ohhh! Indon! {laughing mockingly} Wash my caar! Clean my toileets! Nurse my dying grandmaa!" [L] Look, I am mistaken for a maid! I am not a maid! I am a comedian! You know what is the difference between a comedian and a maid? Maid makes more money! [L]

Then he shifted to his experience of racial discrimination even by his fellow Indonesians by playing something out of his observed expression from Indonesians in a restaurant whom he acted out by clapping slowly and looking confused and imagined conversations by Indonesians stating that Reggie should step down the stage and join them washing the dishes. He then shared another experience wherein a Malaysian allegedly mistaken him as a maid and told him to wash the dishes, the car, and clean the house after learning that he was an Indonesian. The funny part was while he was initially stating that there is a big difference between a maid and a comedian, that big difference that he was really talking about is the maid earning more than a comedian.

But after travelling here and there, now I'm in Bali, ladies and gentlemen! [C]...And Bali is crazy! You guys are crazy coz' you don't give a shit about COVID! {shrieks in awe} [C] And I understand because you guys got more important problems to take care of! [L] yeah!...like Herpes, Syphilis, Gonorrhoea, Chlamydia, AIDS! [continuous L] I understand, I understand, yeah! when COVID comes hahaha!...Take a number! [L]...I think...I think...when COVID first hit Bali, she had to give respect to the more senior diseases already in the island [L] So COVID be like {started acting out as if COVID is introducing oneself in a flirty manner} "Hello! I'm newww! I'm Corona, call me Rona!" {then winked} [L] And AIDS be like "Holy shit! I've used to be the hotshot but look at me now! [L] All right....rookie, rookie...newbie...over here...You're new...you're big deal I know you're lethal...yeah yeah...but to where do we play here in Bali is that we are territorial. [L] All right? [L] So the places where the people are fucking, you leave them to me. [L] So you leave Canggu alone [L] and put ah...{he burst in small laughter thus breaking his act then returned to it} [then L] However...there is one place in Bali where the people are not fucking as much and they still deserve to die...so Ubud is yours. [L] We all can reduce those vegan." [L]

Then he shifted to greeting the audiences as he was warmly welcomed in Bali, but again played it by saying that this part in Indonesia doesn't care about COVID due to the attendance of the live show amid the pandemic. Then dug deeper by saying that he understands this because of the other problems they take care of such as AIDS and other sexually transmitted diseases or STDs. In the context of Bali, the high infections of these STDs are due to hygiene practices and the activities by sex workers (Reed, et.al. 2001, p.46). Reggie made another funny part by stating that the virus are "territorial" and the districts where "fucking is high" such as in Canggu would be for the STDs and the COVID-19 would be in Ubud, where "people is not fucking as much by still they deserve to die" because they are vegan. In tourist articles and video blogs, Canggu and Ubud are considered rivals in tourism as these are the two of the most visited places in Bali (LukeLifeCharms, 2020). The difference is that Canggu is for those who seek night life, beaches, international establishments whereas Ubud is for those who seek local cultures with a vibe inclined to nature compared to Canggu which developments are towards modernization as explained in pros and cons of staying in these two places by tourist vlogger named LukeLifeCharms (2020).

Nigel Ng (Malaysia)

Nigel Ng Video # 1: A Tiktok video posted in Facebook. Published in the first of April, widely known as April Fools' Day when jokes and pranks are traditionally done, Nigel announced that he lost his sense of taste and smell, which apparently is also one of the symptoms of COVID-19 during the initial stages of the pandemic. (See full text version in Appendix A)

Nigel Ng Video # 1 Analysis

British food is known for its reputation that is "used to be plainness: vegetables and meat without the sauces except for the ubiquitous brown gravy, fish and chips---

the first convenience food---and an endless variety of desserts and puddings...the rule of thumb behind much English thinking about food seems to have been that everyone knew how to cook a joint of meat or a chop, that elaborate sauces were meant to disguise poor quality and the real proof that hosts loved their guests was manifest in the traditional tarts, pies and confections often elaborately decorated with whipped cream, flaked chocolate, hundreds and thousands of glace fruits and nuts." (Jones, 2003, pp.210-211). Nigel, born and raised in Kuala Lumpur but currently based in London (Thomas, 2021), played with this by making the notable symptoms of being infected with COVID-19, which are the loss of taste and smell as the setup and this reputation of British food as the funny part.

Nigel Ng Video # 2: An old video of Nigel's performance with live audiences that was re-published on social media during the time of the pandemic about Asian parents' non-belief on allergies.

Nigel Ng Video # 2 Analysis

Nigel reposted this video as to reminisce that this became viral during the previous year. Most reactions chosen in the video posted was the laughing face reaction and most comments from the viewers could relate to the situation where the beliefs of their parents, even if it were not true, shall still govern, such as in the case of the set of Nigel wherein his parents don't believe in allergies.

For street food? If you eat a peanut and die, we just pack our shit and {acts out riding a bicycle} cycle away! [L] {then acts out as his father} "Oh shit, leave the chopsticks, let's go son!" [L] {Then he shifted back as himself} "Why is he on the floor daddy? {shifted back as his father} "He's just taking a nap, man!" [L] "Who gives a fuck?" [L] {shifted back as himself as narrator} Asian parents don't even believe in food allergies, man. [few L] right? My parents don't believe in that shit. You tell parents

you have a peanut allergy they'll be like {acting out as a typical Asian parent} "no, no, no, no, no, no such thing" [few L] "They're only strong people {pointing one side of the audience to draw division}, and then there are weak people {pointing to the opposite side}" [L] "How can you be a man if a peanut fucks you up?" [L] "If peanut kill my son, I have no son, alright?" [L]..."walk it off, pussy!" [L] "And what the fuck is gluten?" [L]

More than the case of allergies, it can be observed that the playful or funny part is the stereotypical image of Asian parenting or "tiger parenting", which is "excessively controlling, harsh and demanding unquestioning obedience with little to no concern for the child's needs, wishes, or emotional being" (Juang, 2013). However, studies focused on Chinese American, Mainland Chinese, Korean American, and Hmong American families (Cheah et al 2013, Kim et al 2013, Way et al 2013, Choi et al, 2013, Lamborn et al, 2013, Supple et al, 2013, mentioned in Juang, 2013, 4th para.) showed otherwise as collectively, these studies show that "although tiger parenting exists among Asian-heritage families, it is not common and it is not linked to the best child outcomes. Asian-heritage parenting has variation of being beyond strict, controlling, and demanding high academic achievement of their children" (Juang, 2013, 4th para.). These studies also show that they are "warm, supportive, and loving toward their children" (Juang, 2013, 4th para.).

Nigel Ng Video # 3: This is the first impression of Nigel as a fictional character, Uncle Roger, a middle-aged Cantonese uncle who worked in real estate, and was initially conceptualized by his fellow comedian, Evelyn Mok (Thomas, 2021). Since then, he reviews different kinds of food, mostly Asian and their equivalents in other parts of the world, as this fictional character. (See full text version in Appendix A)

Nigel Ng Video # 3 Analysis

Nigel: *{as Uncle Roger} My name is Uncle Roger. Today, I will review white people's favorite type of rice. {shows a product in front of the camera} Uncle Ben's Instant Microwave bullshit! This flavor is spicy Mexican. {looking at the package} I think it's OK. {looks at the camera} Uncle Roger like spicy and Uncle Roger loove Mexicans. {looking at the product again then faces the camera} But why is this rice in pouch? Asians we don't buy rice in pouch. {then shows off a sack filled with rice} We always buy the big sacks. 10 kilos. So nice, so big. You slap (it), so satisfying. {slaps the sack} Sometimes I sleep next to the rice {caressing the sack like a pillow} after my wife left. {made a sigh then next scene, he holds the product for review again}*

Nigel played with the culture of eating rice in the context of the western countries and in the context of Asians. First, it can be observed in the quantity of rice taken that the western version is contained in pouch while for Asians, as portrayed, rice are contained in sacks. Viewers who have profiles identified from ASEAN countries commented that their rice bag is twice the size of what Nigel has shown and what they buy is twice the weight that Nigel mentioned. Do note that rice is the dominant staple of Southeast Asia, which adapts to different ecological niches (Esterik, 2008). Viewers could also relate through comments to the microwaveable rice of the western version that it also "tastes awful." His jokes on Uncle Roger being left by his ex-wife has a ring of truth to it as Nigel told a fellow content creator that he was divorced (Thomas, 2021).

Nigel Ng Video # 4: Nigel as Uncle Roger explains how to cook rice using rice cooker. This is the first video of him as Uncle Roger that garnered more than a million views. (See full text version in Appendix A)

Nigel Ng Video # 4 Analysis

Proper Asian use(s) rice cooker. {shows off a rice cooker and opens the lid then cut to scene that a rice is poured onto the rice bowl} Step one: pour the rice in the rice bowl. {cut scene to rice was shown being washed} Step two: wash the rice {cut scene to using finger to measure water level} Step three: use finger to measure water. {cut scene to Nigel putting back the rice bowl to the cooker} Now put it back in rice cooker and press play {he pressed a button to start the rice cooker and a starting tune played similar to the Alphabet song signaling the start of its operation, then cut scene to Nigel waiting for the cooker to finish} Let rice cooker handle the cooking. Now you have time to think about your sad life, {camera zooms to Nigel} why do people you love always leave you {made a sigh then video turned black and white while this scene was done, then cut scene to another tune played from the cooker signaling that it is done} Now rice is ready, open the rice cooker, and fluff the rice. {camera focuses on the rice bowl while Nigel is mixing the rice} Oh my God so nice so satisfying...better than sex.

Still related with the culture of rice in the context of Asians, Nigel as Uncle Roger made an instructional video of how to cook rice using rice cooker in an informative yet humorous manner such as using of finger to measure water level, then shifted to thinking about one's sad life while letting the rice cooker "handle the cooking" and mixing the rice which he as Uncle Roger considers more satisfying than sex. Viewers of Asian profile commented that they relate with the process of cooking rice while those from western countries, were amazed with the technique when they tried it for the first time.

Nigel Ng Video # 5: Nigel as Uncle Roger continues to review of different foods in a comical manner, mostly of Asian, done by other people outside Asia such as this

video of his review of a famous cuisine from Thailand which is Thai Green Curry that was done by a British chef, Jamie Oliver. It is a split screen setup of the original video of Jamie Oliver creating the said cuisine alongside the comment by Nigel playing as Uncle Roger. This is one of the videos that garnered most number of views compared to his other videos as Uncle Roger with ten million (10M) views in the social media platform, Facebook. (See full text version in Appendix A)

Nigel Ng Video # 5 Analysis

Jamie Oliver is known for having been "criticized for his interpretation of various dishes, including his take on the West African dish Jollof rice in 2014 and Jamaican jerk rice in 2018" (Mathew, 2022, 2nd para.) and in 2020 was regularly criticized by Nigel Ng as Uncle Roger starting with the "all wrong" egg fried rice (Mathew, 2022, 3rd para.) and then the above-featured video criticizing his interpretation of Thai Green Curry as it is allegedly far from being authentic.

"A pinch of salt, lid on, top medium heat, happy days." {then Nigel reacts as the screen splits again} No no no not happy day, no. You don't have rice cooker. It's sad day for Uncle Roger. {back to Jamie's video explaining he will make a paste while peeling a thumb-sized piece of ginger, using his thumb as reference, Nigel was shown again briefly, shaking his head} Haiyaa, ginger wrong! use Galangal! Galangal! {repeated with echo} Nobody use ginger for Thai green curry. Nobody! {back to Jamie's video putting the ginger to food processor, intently replaying the scene, then Nigel reacted first with a sigh}

Aside from the usual tirades, it can be also observed that Nigel is familiar with the authentic ingredients of Thai Green Curry as he mentioned to use Galangal instead of Ginger. Viewers identified themselves as Thai commented that it is their first time to see a Thai Green Curry served with mushrooms, which garnered laugh reactions

as well, aside from the video itself. Recently, Jamie Oliver hired "cultural appropriation specialists" to make sure he would not commit past mistakes by offending people of certain cultures (Mathew, 2022).

Harith Iskander (Malaysia)

Harith Iskander Video # 1: Harith acts as a journalist at the White House interviewing then US President Donald Trump regarding the COVID-19. He is not actually interviewing the President, he edits the video clip from a press conference as if the President is answering the questions from Harith as a journalist. (See full text version in Appendix A)

Harith Iskander Video # 1 Analysis

Harith: *{cutting again} Could you say that again please?*

Trump: *{that part replayed again but with a fuller version} "...the germ has gotten so brilliant, that the antibiotic can't keep up with it, and the constantly trying to come up with a new...people would go to a hospital and they catch, they go for a heart operation, that's no problem..." {cut scene to Harith is shown taking notes then returned to the video} "...but they end up dying from...from...problems...you know the problems I'm talking about?"*

Harith: *No! No...I don't know the problem that you're talking about.*

Trump: *{video played again} "ah...there's a whole genius to it. We are fighting not only as a hidden, it's very smart, okay? it's invisible. and it's hidden. But it's...it's very smart."*

Harith: *So, it's invisible, it's hidden, and it's very smart...everything you are not.*

Thank you very much Mr. President!

Trump: *{just audio being played as outro} "I want to find a friendly reporter!"*

The original video of former US President Donald Trump inserted by Harith was a press conference wherein Trump "confused the viral disease with a bacterial infection which could be treated with antibiotics" (report by Cockburn of Independent UK, 2020, 1st para.). Most reactions in the video are laughing face reactions while comments are mixed ranging from bashing Harith and supporting the ridicule on Trump.

Harith Iskander Video # 2: Harith again acts as the journalist as same as the first video interviewing US President Donald Trump but this time about another issue during the pandemic which is the use of masks. Same setup as the first video was executed in this sketch. (See full text version in Appendix A)

Harith Iskander Video # 2 Analysis

Trump: *{his interview video being played} "You know you can use a scarf. A scarf is everybody...ah a lot of people have {the error tone of a computer operating system was played while Harith was shown wearing a scarf while writing to what Trump says} scarfs and you can use a scarf. Scarf would be very good. And I, my feeling is that people wanted to do it, they certainly no harm to it {then same tone was played while Harith was shown wearing another scarf this time it's sort of a Niqab for Muslim girls} and ah, I would say that you do it but use a scarf if you want {Harith was shown again wearing another type while the tone of a dial-up connection process was being played} you know rather than going out in getting a mask or whatever, we'll making millions and millions of masks {Harith was then shown wearing a Spiderman mask while a funny tune was played} but we wanted to go to ahh hospitals and one of the things that Dr. Fauci told me today is that we don't want them competing, we don't want everybody competing with the hospitals where you really need them {a cricket sound was played while Harith was shown wearing a Captain America mask} so you*

can use scarfs, you can use something else to cover your face. Doesn't have to be a mask {Harith was shown using a women's bra as a mask while the tune of a sci-fi drama series was being played} but it's not ideal at least for, or a period of time. I mean eventually you not gonna want to do that, you not gonna have to do that, this is going to be...gone. It'll be gone. Hopefully gone for a long time."

Harith: *{in sarcasm} Gone for a long time, Mr. President? Well, we wish you all the best. Oh. You mean the Corona Virus? Of course, of course {then looks at the camera}*

Same format as video # 1 but this time former US President Donald Trump was asked regarding shortage of face masks and "suggested that it's possible to use scarves instead" (in a report by Sprunt, 2020, 1st para.). In the above-quoted fact-checking report, the CDC website does say that face mask may be reserved for health care workers and that people who fall in the category of needing a mask at home "may need to improvise by using a scarf or bandana" (Sprunt, 2020, 1st para.). Again, the dominating reactions for this video is the laughing face while comments were mixed but more of in support for Harith.

Harith Iskander Video # 3: Harith acts as a deputy minister and says something in the context of the recent cigarette (called rokok in Malaysian) vs alcohol (spelled in the page as alkohol) ban. (See full text version in Appendix A)

Harith Iskander Video # 3 Analysis

The National Security Council of Malaysia declared that alcoholic beverages and cigarettes are both non-essential but only cigarettes are allowed to be sold during the period of the lockdown or what they call in Malaysia as Movement Control Order or MCO period to "cater to the needs of those with a smoking addiction" as per announcement by Deputy Domestic Trade and Consumer Affairs Minister Datuk Rosol

Wahid as documented in an article by Amar Shah Mohsen (2021, 5th-7th para.). He added that "we can't stop its sale, otherwise there will be problems. Only smokers will understand. Without cigarettes, it will be a huge burden for them" (in Mohsen 2021, 11th para.) It was also mentioned in the article that Malaysia collected RM3.94B in sin tax from cigarettes and tobacco compared to RM1.92B from alcoholic beverages in 2017.

*Apa dia? (Malay for "what is that?") Alcohol? Ahh. Alcohol categorized by the National Security Council (MKN) as non-essential. Therefore...banned! Ahh. Tak boleh jual (Malay for "can't sell" or "not allowed to sell")...is banned. Kenot! Kenot! (Cannot). Lagi pun (Malay for "even though") alcohol is no good for the SOP, because when people the drinking drinking, then they come out, suddenly, they love-love everybody. They see their friend, they want to hug the friend {acting out a hugging movement} "I love you brother...ooh you are like my brudder!" Tak boleh! (Malay for "can not!") Patah S.O.P.! (Malay for "S.O.P. is broken/foiled") The SOP is broken! Tak boleh! One meter! Must keep away! (talking about social distancing) hah. Any other question? {same gesture as the first question was done} Um? Cigarette? Rokok? Ah. Rokok is also non-essential. Tapi (Malay for "but") boleh jual (Malay for "can sell" or "allowed to sell") Ahh. Why? Because it's essential to the cigarette addict! Ahaaa...You don't know, if you are not a smoker...you will understand. Do you smoke? Ah, you don't smoke! Where you from? Ah. Perlis. No wonder, lah! Haha! You don't know, cigarette addict. They must get the cigarette. If they don't get, it will be a problem. Tak dapat rokok, (Malay for "can't smoke"; he is telling if the addict could not smoke,) suddenly, like {acting out as if the addict is shivering to a fever} Geram je *bunyi moto (Malay for "sounding like a motorcycle") Tak boleh! We must look after our addicted rakyat! We must take care of them. Lagi*

pun if you have no cigarette...then the rakyat? What happen to them? Hah, what will happen? They will turn to heroin! Macam mana tu? Macam mana tu? (Malay for "How is that?")...

...Ah...{talking to a fictional person asking} apa dia? Do I smoke? Eh...it's not about me...it's not about me...I'm not important myself. It's about the rakyat. The rakyat we must look after them. Ah..so I think...macam ni (Malay for "like this")...kalau apa apa...if there is nothing else, I nak pergi roko...roko...roko...zen {about to take out a cigarette in his pocket but opted to mention that he will go to a Japanese restaurant} My friend's restaurant.

The playful or funny part that Harith did was telling first that smokers might turn to heroin, another addictive substance should they stop smoking, and then acting out as if he is a closet cigarette addict, giving a hint to the viewers that the said policy was allegedly self-serving. Comments from viewers are mixed from serious insights regarding the matter and being entertained with how Harith played with the issue.

Harith Iskander Video # 4: Harith plays the same role but this time called this "Minister of Explanation" as translated from the word "Menteri Explanasi" in the description video and the context here is about a Deputy Minister or Timbalan Menteri in Malay as written in the video description who "allegedly" did an online Nikah ceremony in a virtual setup particularly through a video call from a Masjid in Golok, Thailand (Iskander, 2021). It is further explained in the video description that the not only is the Nikah not recognized by Malaysian authorities, but even Thai Muslim authorities don't sanction it (Iskander, 2021). (See full text version in Appendix A)

Harith Iskander Video # 4 Analysis

As mentioned above, a Deputy Minister or Timbalan Menteri "allegedly" did an online Nikah ceremony in a virtual setup particularly through a video call from a Masjid

in Golok, Thailand (Iskander, 2021). It is further explained in the video description that the not only is the Nikah not recognized by Malaysian authorities, but even Thai Muslim authorities don't sanction it (Iskander, 2021). The Narathiwat Islamic Council in Thailand denied that a Malaysian politician with a 'Datuk' title had his marriage to his third wife solemnized (*akad nikah*) online despite unofficial reports and a video showing the online ceremony that became viral on social media platforms (report by Abdullah, 2021). The Spanish Fly that was fondly mentioned by Harith was about the health minister of Malaysia "mistook the deadly Spanish Flu of 1918 for 'Spanish Fly' during a health talk at Universiti Putra Malaysia" (from a report by Danial Martinus, 2021, 1st para.). It was mentioned in the same article that Spanish Fly is a popular aphrodisiac, which then gave a clear picture of the reason for ridicule by internet and social media users.

But I repeat it, it shouldn't have happened. What? Why Nikah right now during this time when the entire country is struggling, orang yang tak da makan, tak da nasi, and why Nikah in the first place? Ini you kena salahkan Spanish Fly. (Malay for, "it's your fault, Spanish Fly").

Harith played as the Minister getting involved with the incident by playing with the official statement of the Minister that it was a private matter (Free Malaysia Today, 2021) through stating the difference of online, or using the internet, and on-line, or using the phone, and then blaming it on the Spanish Fly. Comments from the viewers are mostly of entertained and contributing to the content such as one said that the career of the comedians are in danger because politicians in Malaysia are getting funnier without trying hard.

Harith Iskander Video # 5: Harith again plays as the Minister of Explanation as he comment regarding the issue of prohibiting one taking a video during the vaccination process. (See full text version in Appendix A)

Harith Iskander Video # 5 Analysis

The public was not allowed to record themselves when receiving the vaccine jab, and only allowed to take photographs at an allocated photo booth in the vaccination center or PPV after the process. From the same article, two days after during an evening meeting, it was approved by Science, Technology, and Innovation Minister Khairy Jamaluddin that people are "now allowed to record and take pictures as proof they have received a full vaccine jab", and the "showing of syringe filled with the right quantity of vaccine by medical officers will also continue" (in a report by Yusof and Krishnan, 2021, 1st-3rd para.). Since the decision was made later in the day,

Menteri petang-cakap lain? ("Why, confused? What is that 'confused'? Why do Deputy Minister said something in the morning then the Minister said something another in the afternoon?" in Malay) This is not Kompusing! The reason the Timbalan Menteri said one thing in the morning and the Menteri said another thing in the afternoon, (is) if you don't want to take a video selfie selfie, you go vaccine in the morning! If you want to take a video selfie selfie, you vaccine in the afternoon! Apa yang kompuse?! {laughs in jest} Tak...boleh...senang aje...("Not...can...it's fun" in Malay)

Harith acting out as a Minister played with the news announcing that those who want to take pictures or video of themselves should be vaccinated in the afternoon while those who are not into taking pictures or video should be vaccinated in the morning. Comments range from serious insights about the matter to contributing funny comments to the content.

Harith Iskander Video # 6: Harith again plays as the "Minister of Explanation" and this time the issue is about the Minister who resigned along with the rest of the cabinet yet assures to the public that he will continue to serve Malaysia (Iskander, 2021). (See full text version in Appendix A)

Harith Iskander Video # 6 Analysis

Malaysian Prime Minister Muhyiddin Yassin stepped down on his post along with his cabinet after "months of political turmoil culminated in the loss of his majority, but his resignation is likely to open another chapter of instability in the absence of any obvious successor." However, since there is no successor yet, the king of Malaysia, Al-Sultan Abdullah, appointed Muhyiddin as the "caretaker prime minister" until a replacement is found but without a definite timeline because the King believed that the election is not the best option amid pandemic. (in a report by Chu, Latiff and Lee, 2021, 1st, 3rd and 4th para.).

Harith: ...Jadi mulai sekarang kita semua tak da kerja ("So from now on, we all can't work" in Malay) Apa dia? ("What's that" in Malay) Oooh. ya ya. Kecuali the PM. Dia dapat kerjabaru. ("He got a new job" in Malay). Kalau dulu, dia PM...sekarang dia, care-taker PM ("In the past he is the PM...now, he is care-taker PM" in Malay). Tapi for me, Menteri yang biasa. no job, tak da kerja. ("But for me, the Minister, as usual, no job, no job." in Malay). Jadi ("So" in Malay), if anything happens, don't ask me. I wasn't there. It wasn't me. Ahh. Apa dia? What am I going to do now that I resign? Ooohhh...you donno...you donno...I am going to terus berkhidmat untuk Malaysia ("continue to serve for Malaysia" in Malay). I want to make sure that Malaysia is No. 1! That is why I download the Pop-Cat-Klick. Ahh...Dengan ("With" in Malay) popcatclick, we must make sure Malaysia is No. 1. We must beat Thailand and

Taiwan! Don't disturb me. I got very many thing to do. {then acting as if getting busy with Popcatclick in his phone}

Harith acted out as the former prime minister and played with this fact by promising to make Malaysia number one...in popcat.click, a game wherein it will count the number of clicks of an image of a cat with a mouth that can be animated through clicks, per users per country. The author also tried this game and upon research of the site, Hong Kong remains top of the most number of clicks consisting of 121.9B. The Philippines garnered as per the date of access, 2.6B clicks (PopCat, 2022).

Chris Raufeisen (Thailand)

Chris Raufeisen Video: Chris Raufeisen is a Thai and American stand-up comedian living in Bangkok and is also a producer of live comedy shows, a podcast, and comedy artwork, as posted in his official Facebook page. (Raufeisen, n.d.). In this video he gives funny comments on some of the interesting items while shopping in Thailand. (See full text version in Appendix A)

Chris Raufeisen Video Analysis

Ayt, moving on, there is a bag I came across at the flea market, this is a Dasida bag. {a picture of the mentioned bag was shown next, same format} Uhm, this bag is a gold mine. Dasida is the fuckin holy trinity of random Asian knockoff bullshit, ok? You got your Adidas letters rearranged to say... "Dasida," with two Pumas on top, jumpin' towards a Converse All-Star...and underneath it says "Success For Everything" And it even comes with straps, so you can like, you know, handle your failure.

Southeast Asia is the fastest rising destination in the world when it comes to counterfeit goods as there were 66 intercepted shipments in 2014 to 299 in 2018, and in 2019, it was "expected to show around over 400 counterfeit goods shipments destined for Southeast Asia" with the Philippines, Indonesia, Thailand, and Vietnam as the biggest

destination markets, and with Singapore being the largest of all over the last 5 years probably due to being the "largest transshipment port in the world and a well-known node in global illicit trade" (The Economist Intelligence Unit 2018 in Redfearn, 2020, 4th para.). This is probably one of the reasons why there were a lot of interesting items featured by the comedian found in flea markets where Chris is currently based.

Ahh, next up, we got an exciting collaboration between Under Armour and Dickie's!

{a photo of boxers with a logo of Under Armour and Dickies put together, was shown} Alright, nothing says "I'm athletic, blue collar and an immigrant" more than these boxers. These are perfect if you are...wanna like play football, and when you're done, you can cut the grass on the field, or if you wanna like run a forty-yard dash at a Home Depot, alright, or low-key these are perfect for sneaking into America. Also, perfect for tailgating an Oakland Raiders game and fighting in a Wendy's parking lot later at night...at least for testing, boys. Oversized Free Bird Gangster T-Shirt, switchblade, not included.

The brands Under Armour and Dickie's mentioned has separate cultural contexts regarding to what the comedian said about being "athletic, blue-collar, and immigrant". Under Armour is the "originator of performance apparel-sportswear engineered to keep athletes cool, dry, and light throughout the course of a game, practice, or workout," and invested to gain high brand recognition from both professional athletes and local communities through aggressive marketing and advertising (Tighe, 2022, 2nd para.). Dickie's has this reputation of one of the world's biggest workwear manufacturers and then became a piece of gang wear popular in Los Angeles predominantly worn by Crips and Crip-affiliates, though the signature khaki colored chinos were neutral so other gang members belonging to Latin gangs (Cruz, 2015, 2nd para.).

Last on our shit list today is ah...Odioos {a photo of a product showing a distorted classic logo of Adidas with the words Odioos} If you wanna dress like the handyman at a Filipino prison, this Odioos is for you. Clearly, a ripoff of Adidas with the four leaves and two stripes. Uhm, Adidas stands for "All Day I Dream About Sports." I wonder what Odioos could stand for..."Our Dog Is Out Of Semen"... "Oriental Devils in Obscure Off brain Shorts"...or maybe uhm "One Day I'll Own Original Sportswear"...perfect.

The popularity of foreign fashion and athletic brands subjected to counterfeit (or an attempt of these thereof) that were featured in the video of Chris can be linked to the "athleisure" as prevalent theme of fashion in ASEAN wherein consumers also care about looking good during their workouts, making sports and styles become inseparable (Yuen, 2018, 15th para.).

Chris Wright (Thailand)

Chris Wright Video: This is one of Chris Wright's instructional videos on English speaking for Thai people infused with humorous scenes to make learning it interesting. (See full text version in Appendix A)

Chris Wright Video Analysis

Boss: *Don't forget guys, it is good online etiquette to turn on your cameras. {Chris then explains in Thai the meaning of "etiquette", and it entails making eye contact regardless if meetings are held face to face or online}*

Boss: *Remember, you need to have manners at this company.*

Office Lady: *Yes, I have many man! {Chris then explains in Thai that "etiquette" and "manners" have the same meaning}*

Chris Wright, aside from being a comedian, is also an English teacher serving for Thai people. In this case, it talks about what to do and say during online meetings,

especially during the time of pandemic wherein social gatherings, may it be for pleasure or for business are not allowed to prevent the spread of the virus.

Lady at the background: *Michael! Why didn't you flush the toilet?*

Boss: *{yelling at her} Not right now! I'm in a professional meeting!*

Lady at the background: *Why didn't you flush the toilet? {then the boss went to her resulting to his real attire being shown consisting of coat, tie, and shorts}*

Boss: *Can't you see I'm talking to my employees!*

Lady: *You're not wearing any pants!*

Boss: *{pushing the lady out} We'll talk about this later! {then returning to the meeting} Some people! Am I right?!*

While this is purely intended to be an instructional video on how to speak in English during online meetings, humor is used to make it interesting such as the point of the boss to his employees for being professional, but the funny part is he himself is not professional on how he wears his business attire and how he also acts at home.

Alex Calleja (the Philippines)

Alex Calleja Video # 1: Alex reminded everyone of maintaining proper hygiene with the specific ways instructed by the government at the height of the pandemic. During the video, he demonstrated the time spent in washing should be as long as singing the traditional "Happy Birthday" song, but with a twist...again (See full text version in Appendix A)

Alex Calleja Video # 1 Analysis

Alex: *{situated himself in front of a faucet; talking in front of a camera} Guys, ngayong panahon ng may Corona Virus, sabi ng mga eksperto, dapat proper washing, 20 seconds, at sabayan mo ng "Happy Birthday" {pertaining to the traditional song}, kaya gagawin natin 'yan {then proceeds with the washing by*

*opening the faucet to apply soap and water then closing the faucet to save water, then starts singing "Happy Birthday" in a faster than traditional tempo of the song; after singing it twice, the camera focused on the dishes as he is done washing and proceeds to speak again in an instructional manner}*Ayan, tapos na yung isang plato.

Ngayon naman, susunod na plato

Most comedy materials by Alex are related to his life as a married man and a father, and this time, he made a play between the recommended practice of proper hygiene by the Department of Health in the Philippines of washing at least 20 seconds while singing the "Happy Birthday" song in traditional tempo that serves as a guide if one has done washing for 20 seconds (Department of Health Philippines, 2020), and the washing of dishes, a household chore usually done by a wife, was considered funny as it is in the social stigma that men should not be subordinate to their wives (Migliaccio, 2001 in Iso, 2017).

Alex Calleja Video # 2: Alex shoots a basketball lesson (pun not intended). Since most of the time people are staying at home due to the pandemic, even activities such as physical exercises are done at home. Alex capitalized this by doing a parody of a typical basketball instructional video. One of the episodes that will be featured in the study is his lesson on stealing the ball. (See full text version in Appendix A)

Alex Calleja Video # 2 Analysis

***Alex:** {sported a basketball outfit} Hello there! I am Alex Calleja and welcome to Basketball 101! I am here with my assistant, Rico, and today, I am going to teach you how to steal the ball. Watch and learn! Let's go!*

{already in position, Rico is dribbling the ball, and Alex plays defense} I am playing defense! And this is how you steal the ball! {Rico stopped dribbling to secure the ball,

then Alex held out a bolo knife, then Rico ran away without the ball, resulting to Alex getting the ball} And that's how you steal the ball!

The setup here is that he as a basketball coach who is expected to do an instructional video that will teach how to steal a ball from an opponent in a manner that is allowed by the traditional rules of basketball. The funny part is that his approach is likened to a criminal robbing money from a victim as shown in how he held out a deadly weapon through a form of a bolo knife. In the Philippines, a person involved in robbery usually holds out a large knife or a gun threatening the victim to be harmed or killed if any valuable possession of the victim would not be surrendered to the robber (in the case of *People of the Philippines vs. Doinog and Cortez*, 2000 in LawPhil Project, 2000). Alex further emphasized that it was a criminal act by capping it off through stating that the next lesson would be escaping from prison or being jailed.

Alex Calleja Video # 3: Alex was starting to sing "Di Niyo Ba Naririnig?" a famous Filipino protest song with music based from "Do You Hear the People Sing?", one of the songs from the musical *Les Miserables* but with a twist. (See full text version in Appendix A)

Alex Calleja Video # 3 Analysis

A voice of a woman: *{yells from afar; not in video} Hoy! Kanina pa kita tinatawag eh! Maglalaba ka pa! Di mo ba naririnig?*

Alex: *{unfazed; continued singing after the woman yelled} Di niyo ba naririnig? Tinig ng misis kong galit! {turns out that the woman is his wife}*

This is another take of Alex for the "under-de-saya" culture but making it relevant with the times through a revival of the said protest song that was originally sung by famous artists and celebrities of that period following the non-renewal of the franchise of one of the biggest broadcasting network in the Philippines, ABS-CBN, and

the government response during the height of the pandemic. The protest against the alleged injustice and incompetence of the government to ABS-CBN and the people affected by the shutdown of the station with the situation worsened by the pandemic can be funnily used in describing their wives by husbands who are "under-de-saya" as portrayed by Alex.

Alex Calleja Video # 4: A comedy sketch where Alex plays a father having lunch with his son played by a child actor. In the scene, Alex asserts himself of his position as the head of the house, but there is a twist in the end (See full text version in Appendix A)

Alex Calleja Video # 4 Analysis

Alex: *{slammed the utensils and talking in a loud manner as if rehearsing something} "Ayoko na! Sawang-sawa na ako!" {then shift to another camera angle as if Alex is talking to the camera}"Ikaw na lang lagi nasusunod sa bahay na 'to! Tatay ako! Pa'no naman yung desisyon ko?! Sobra na! {then posed to continue eating}*

Son: *Daddy! Ang tapang mo ah! {Alex nods in agreement then a message tone alert plays hinting that someone sent a message to Alex's phone} O ayan nag-text si*

Mommy, pauwi na raw siya! Sabihin mo ulit yung mga sinabi mo kanina ah?

Alex: *{suddenly shifted into a worried voice} Hindi anak, nagpapractice lang ako habang wala yung mommy mo. Naglalabas lang ako ng sama ng loob. Yung mga narinig mo, atin-atin lang yun. Wag mo sasabihin ah? Nako, kumain ka na, kumain ka na. {becoming more worried} Maghuhugas pa ako ng plato pagtapos mo. Atin lang yun! Ito naman. {son looks at the camera mocking Alex}*

The setup here is the assertion of Alex as a father of his position in the house but the funny part here is that this is limited during the absence of his wife inside the

house. When he learned that his wife is already coming home through a message on the phone, the real situation of his position revealed when he said to his son that his assertion was just a practice, he was venting out on his son, and telling his son to finish his food as he will do the dishes afterwards. This is a take to an old joke on husbands being subservient to their wives, fondly called as "under-de-saya", a Tagalog-English term for being subordinate to their wives symbolized by "saya," a traditional Filipino garment by ladies during the Spanish colonial period (Farlex Dictionary of Idioms. 2015)

Alex Calleja Video # 5: Alex made a joke on the issue on whether he owns a certain Ford Everest because the context is that the official distributor of this vehicle mistakenly sends him a safety recall report in 2019 (VISOR, 2019) during the time that the manufacturer conducted a recall on this particular model due to a possible defect. He already cleared that the letter was sent by mistake and he jokingly stated that his wife is getting angry at him thinking that he owns a new vehicle without her consent and might be parked in someone else's house and probably of another woman (Instagram post, 2019, in VISOR, 2019). Two years after, he made a twist with the issue through this video. (See full text version in Appendix A)

Alex Calleja Video # 5 Analysis

Alex: *{in formal suite} Marami nagtatanong sa akin, {then impersonate the questions}"Alex, may Ford Everest ka ba? Alex, nasan yung Ford Everest mo?" 'Sus! Lumang joke na yun! {chuckles} Hindi totoo 'yon! {then positions himself with a real Ford Everest in the background}Ako, magkaka-Ford Everest?! Wala 'yon! Huwag niyo ng intindihin yon, kalimutan niyo na yun! {saying this while approaching to the driver's door}O dito muna ako ah {pointing to the vehicle then going near to*

the driver's door} Ford Everest? {mockingly laughs and shaking his head while opening the door and eventually riding the vehicle}

The usual structure of the joke could be observed here as the setup is that he denies ownership of a certain vehicle that most people according to him, are claiming that he has one. Then the funny part starts with showing the said vehicle in his background and ending it with eventually riding the vehicle but continues to deny ownership of it. Even those who are not familiar with cars will get the joke as the car shown in the video has markings that will prove the identity of it such as emblem of the logo of the manufacturer Ford, and the engravement of the model name at the trunk opener which is Everest.

James Caraan (the Philippines)

James Caraan Video # 1: Published in March 16, 2021. It shows a split-screen setup similar to interviews in news programs shown in television networks wherein the interviewee is unable to come to the studio. James plays a role of a reporter trying to interview a government official responsible for managing government responses on the pandemic. Instead of an actual interview answering the questions of the reporter, a video posted in an application called Tiktok, by the said official was played while the reporter is asking questions located at the screen of the interviewee. (See full text version Appendix A)

James Caraan Video #1 Analysis

James (as reporter): *{in the studio, as seen in using a logo of a broadcasting company as his background} Secretary Nograles on the line. Thank you for coming secretary. Secretary what's wrong with your neck? {while saying this, the video on the interviewee side shows the said official dancing using his neck with the caption stating "Ano ang Pilipinas Kontra Gutom?" which primarily introduces a government*

program in fighting hunger during the pandemic}Hello Secretary? Sec...Uh....Can you hear me? Sir? Sir, why are you not blinking? Please blink sir, Please! {while these being said, the official on the interviewee side continues to dance while his eyes are not blinking, as mentioned on purpose by the comedian playing as a reporter...

It can be seen that the video made by James Caraan intends to make fun on the original video made by Cabinet Secretary Karlo Nograles, an official tasked to manage government inter-agency responses during the height of the pandemic. This video became an issue because many people think that there are other better actions to do than posting an infomercial while doing dance moves in Tiktok. One of the comments tagged as most relevant and given a "like" reaction symbolized by a thumb-up emoji said in Filipino that there are no more sensible people working for the government and most of them are crazy, pertaining to the one ridiculed in the video. Another comment joined in the ridicule saying that "Yeye Bonel", one of the hit novelty songs in the country was a favorite. This song has the same dance steps as seen doing by the official in the video.

James Caraan Video # 2: James plays as a denier of the COVID-19 virus. Almost more than a year after the lockdown due to the pandemic, there were still a number of people allegedly believing that the virus is a hoax and/or a made-up type of virus by a group of people particularly those who own large companies and corporations. In social media, it was said that the people support this logic are the same people who believe in superstitious beliefs such as the one that will be mentioned in the following monologue (See full text version in Appendix A)

James Caraan Video # 2 Analysis

James as Denier: {jeering and talking in as fast manner as rapping while getting close to the camera and a text caption labelling him as COVID Deniers} Huwag kayong magpapaniwala diyan sa COVID na yan, gusto lang kumita ng mga doktor diyan sa COVID na yan e. Huwag kayong magpapaniwala diyan, meron bang pulubi atsaka taong-grasa na nagkaroon na ng COVID? Wala di ba? Wala! {Then caption changes thus labelling him as "same person} Ay, masakit tyan mo? Nako, usog yan! Halika, lawayan natin! {then flashes out his tongue to apply saliva onto his hands so that he could apply it to a stomach ache}

Although the Philippines is not found in the top countries where people believe that COVID-19 is a myth, but Indonesia is, landing at the third spot in terms of online population (YouGov, 2022 and Armstrong, 2022, in Baclig, 2022) there are myths about COVID-19 that are popular among social media users in the Philippines. Such examples are masks can cause hypercapnia, or a build-up of Carbon Dioxide in the bloodstream, COVID-19 is a hoax and linked to 5G technology, drinking methanol, ethanol, or bleach could cure COVID-19, vaccine is rushed, and vaccine can alter DNA (Baclig, 2022). This issue was given a humorous parallel approach wherein those who believe in these conspiracy theories might be also those people who believe in those healing techniques not backed by scientific studies such as applying saliva to a stomach ache as acted out by the comedian.

James Caraan Video # 3: James plays two roles: a teacher and a student. The teacher is teaching the student the correct term for community pantry, a program initiated by an activist as a private citizen, wherein people are free to take as much supplies as they need or share with others whatever they could (in a report by Suazo,

2021). The result of the "teaching" by the teacher turned otherwise (See full text version in Appendix A)

James Caraan Video # 3 Analysis

James as Teacher: "Community Pantry"

James as Student {wearing a wig}: "Communist Party"

The context here is that even programs run by activists as private citizens that supplement government response in fighting hunger during the pandemic are getting accused as communist activities or what is known as "red-tagging" where personalities, usually critics of the government, and their activities are allegedly linked to communist groups by the Philippine government (in a report by Rubio, 2022). The community pantry paused its operations due to the red-tagging of the activity (in a report by Mercado, 2021). Critics of this said response by the government say that the community pantry exposes the shortcomings of the government response to the pandemic in terms of fighting hunger thus resulting to red-tagging. A comment considered most relevant in the page expressed admiration towards the video because it tackles that even good deeds are subjected to politicking in the Philippines.

James Caraan Video # 4: James plays three roles: an arbitrator receiving complains, a talking egg tray, and a talking eco-bag made out of cloth. The two items complained on how they were hoarded and abused by those who went to a community pantry to get supplies for free. (See full text version in Appendix A)

James Caraan Video # 4 Analysis

Arbitrator: *Sige po ibablotter na yan. Ikaw naman? Eco-bag ka lang ah. Wala ka namang problema ah. (This is noted and we shall file a blotter. How about you?*

You're just an eco-bag. It seems you have nothing to complain)

James as Eco-bag: *{wearing an eco-bag on his head, crying heavily} Anong wala?! Ako po yung siningit nila sa puwet! Mga hayop kayo! Ambaboy niyo! {afterwards the photo of the hoarder who hid an eco-bag in between her buttocks was shown}*

As same as the other videos, it was intended to make fun on social and political issues during the pandemic. The context here is that there were people as recipients of the community pantry getting for themselves more than enough in particular getting the whole tray of egg and trying to hide it in an eco-bag that is located in an unusual manner, which is in between the buttocks (in a report by Bagaoisan, 2021), and as shown in the video as background. How hoarding was tackled in a funny and creative manner through creating a point-of-view from items such as an egg tray and an eco-bag as observed in the reactions and comments of the viewers can be considered the highlight and take in this video.

James as Arbitrator: *{in plain clothes} Okay. Anu pong reklamo nila? Bakit po sila nandito? (Ok. What is their complaint? What brings you here?)*

James as Talking Egg Tray: *{wearing an egg tray costume on his head, crying} Ako po yung isang tray na ninakaw nila. Nila Maritess. Gusto ko lang po magreklamo na ang dami nilang ginawa sa akin. Prinito, Nilaga, higit sa lahat, binati! Baboy na baboy na po ako sa sarili ko!*

Please take note that the word "*bat*" in the context of eggs is beating them but it is also a slang word for male masturbation.

James Caraan Video # 5: James plays as Satan. The context here is also in line with the alleged red-tagging of the community pantry wherein a general as a spokesperson of an agency called NTF-ELCAC or National Task Force to End Local Communist Armed Conflict, and is also involved with the incident added a statement that the initiative of the pantry is likened to Satan's apple, offered by the snake to Eve,

(in a report by Sadongdong, 2021). This was criticized as "unjust and unnecessary" by social media users including artists such as Juan Miguel Severo and historian, Kristoffer Pasion (report by Madarang, 2021, 14th-16th para.). As with the other issues, the video made by James was intended to make fun out of it (See full text version in Appendix A)

James Caraan Video # 5 Analysis

James as Satan: *{used a video filter of a devil as his costume} Hey, hey, hey! It's your boy, Sataan! At babasagin ko na po ang katahimikan ko dahil mukhang nabuking na tayo ng NTF-ELCAC! At kahit nabuking na ako, huwag niyong kakalimutan ang pinakamahalaga kong turo. Ito ay ang tumulong ayon sa kakayahan, kumuha ayon sa pangangailangan! Tumulong tayo sa mga mahihirap, tumulong tayo sa nagugutom! Maghasik tayo ng tulong ito ang pinaka-gusto ko sa lahat! {then ending it with a devil-like laugh}*

The statement of the general that is considered "unjust and unnecessary" and also may be considered absurd by critics was also responded with absurdity in a funny manner such as this wherein Satan, is spreading a message of kindness and acts of charity, a total opposite of how Satan is usually portrayed.

James Caraan Video # 6: James plays as vlogger Nas Daily. This garnered the most number of views during his stint as content creator during the time of the pandemic and this video made him considered as a social media influencer and "internet sensation" aside from being a comedian, as he was interviewed while featuring this parody video in line with the plan of the government of imposing taxes on social media content creators (video interview by Remitio, 2021). This is just beside the point as the focus would be on the impersonation of James as the vlogger Nas Daily and its context of making it and the reactions by his viewers mostly from the

Philippines. In the video, James impersonated not only Nas Daily as the host but also the manner of how a typical video of the vlogger is shown, which has subtitles that are exactly the same with what the host is talking about. Here are the lines said in the video (See full text version in Appendix A)

James Caraan Video # 6 Analysis

James as Nas Daily: *{clad in plain black shirt just as Nas is usually wearing and speaking the same way as Nas; all that he will say has subtitles}...Philippines, how can you forgive me? {"forgive me" in yellow}I know, I know! {second "I know" in all capital letters and in yellow; mentioned with emphasis} I will just say "adowbow" {"adowbow" in all capital letters and in yellow} and I think you can forgive me! {"forgive me" in yellow} And I will just put "Philippines" {"Philippines" in all capital letters and in yellow} in my title so you will forgive me! {"forgive me" in yellow} And there you have it, you forgave me in just...one minute! {"one minute" spelled as "1 minute" and in yellow}*

The context in the impersonation of Nas Daily during that time was that he was accused of "profiting and exploiting" the local culture in the Philippines as in the case of tattoo artist Apo Whang Od (Palicas, 2021, in an interview by Paje, 2021, 5th para.). However even before the rift between Nas, also known as Nusseir Yassin in real life, and the above-mentioned personalities, netizens express their sentiment against the Palestinian-Israeli vlogger regarding "Pinoy-baiting" wherein it is an online market strategy that capitalizes on "Pinoy pride" and targets Filipino viewers with content about the country (Paje, 2021, 2nd para.). The impersonation video by James was intended not only to create a funny perspective on the issue but also tackles how Nas Daily allegedly capitalizes the Filipino viewers and what exactly are the ones that the Filipino viewers fall for as documented in how James as Nas Daily will say the word

"adobo" which is one of the famous dishes in the Philippines, in a foreign accent that parallels to the recognition that Filipinos long for from international content creators. The video garnered mix reactions. Most were amused with the impersonation as seen in the majority of the "laugh" reactions represented by a laughing emoticon by the viewers while few were offended as observed in the comments that resulted to trolling of the video publisher and the number of "angry" reactions represented by an emoticon with enjoined eyebrows and reddish facial color.

Matrix of the Featured Comedians, Videos and Audience Comments

(See Appendix B for screenshots of actual reactions and comments):

ASEAN State	Comedian	Written Material and Performance	Audience Reaction	Types of Comments	Outcomes (based on written comments)
Indonesia	Annie Yang	Using mobile dating applications and conspiracy theories during COVID-19	Live audiences laughed at her jokes and shared sentiments especially on the part where she was belittled by her date	-no textual comments recorded-	empathy on the comedian based on audible reactions
	Reggie Hasibuan	About being Indonesian, Bali tourism, and COVID-19 being territorial	Live audiences laughed at his jokes even to gender-specific ones	-no textual comments recorded-	empathy on the comedian based on audible reactions
Malaysia	Nigel Ng	Asian stereotypes and culture but focused more on food	Online viewers of both Asian and Western profile could relate to his jokes	joke upon a joke, plain commentaries among viewers and comedian	empathy and derision for both the object of laughter and the comedian
	Harith Iskander	Former US President Trump's comments on COVID-19, current issues in Malaysia involving the government and its policies during the pandemic	Mixed comments and reactions ranging from bashing the comedian, contributing to the ridicule, giving serious insights, to	joke upon a joke, plain commentaries among viewers and comedian	empathy and derision for both the object of laughter and the comedian

			appreciating his humor		
Thailand	Chris Raufeisen	Interesting things found in Asian flea markets	Most reactions are the laughing face ones and only one comment from a foreigner repeating one of the funny lines	plain commentary-emphasizing one of the comedian's lines	empathy for the objects of laughter
	Chris Wright	English speaking and maintaining professionalism in online meetings	Most reactions appreciate the comedian and the video, and learn from it	joke upon a joke, plain commentaries among viewers and comedian	empathy for the object of laughter and new understanding since the video is mostly for educational purposes
Philippines	Alex Calleja	Current local issues mixed with his personal ones such as his role in the family	Mixed comments and reactions ranging from bashing the comedian, contributing to the ridicule, to appreciating his humor	joke upon a joke, plain commentaries regarding the videos	empathy and derision for both the objects of laughter and the comedian
	James Caraan	Issues during COVID-19 Pandemic and in the Philippines such as government response, belief in conspiracy theories on COVID-19, and Nas Daily Controversy	Mixed comments and reactions ranging from bashing the comedian, contributing to the ridicule, to appreciating his humor	joke upon a joke, plain commentaries among viewers and comedian	empathy and derision for both the objects of laughter and the comedian

Emerging Themes

Glocal: Global in Approach, Local in Content

Humor as seen from the online videos of selected stand-up comedians from selected ASEAN member-states can be described as "glocal," or a fusion of "global" and "local" wherein the style of their joke-telling is the same observational type of

comedy employed by comedians in other parts of the world thus "global" yet "local" due to the use of issues that their respective countries and their personal lives face during the pandemic as comedy material. The featured comedians, though different in content, use the same style as what Judy Carter (2001, p.66) have recommended wherein the set-up has a "ring of truth" and were represented by a personal detail about the comedian as the cases of Annie Yang in her "near-death" experience due to choking by her sister and the fear of "Tinder Surprise" wherein the profile picture of a person is totally different from what one looks like in real life; Reggie Hasibuan's experiences of discrimination as an Indonesian, and the case of Alex Calleja in his daily experiences as a husband and father. The set-up can also be a specific subject or interesting items such as food and its culture in the case of Nigel Ng, what to do in a virtual meeting in the case of Chris Wright, and interesting brand names caused by counterfeiting of original ones that are found in flea markets in the case of Chris Raufeisen. Lastly, the set-up was also represented by general knowledge of a place in the case of Reggie Hasibuan, and current events with some foreign and more on local particularly the news regarding response on the COVID-19 pandemic as in the cases of almost all comedians except for Chris Raufeisen.

The funny part of each set-up were as follows: in Annie Yang's case, she became so much used to being choked that she can take lightly the choking that her date is doing while having sexual intercourse, and on the "Tinder Surprise", she did experience a "Tinder Surprise" not on the real appearance of her date but on the real attitude of it, which turned out to be a believer of conspiracy theories on COVID-19. Reggie Hasibuan acted out what his fellow Indonesian and a random Malaysian think of a typical Indonesian and then initially insisted that there is a big difference between a maid and a comedian which turned out to be a maid earns more than a comedian.

Alex Calleja acted out as the head of the house as seen in the videos but the twist is that he is only brave when his wife is not around, and also how he did household chores. In the cases of Nigel Ng and Chris Raufeisen, their videos are formatted as commentary videos to a specific topic, and the funny part are the commentaries themselves. Nigel featured some instructional videos but with commentaries on the side, and featured a cooking video with commentaries on the side too. Same goes with Chris Raufeisen wherein he introduced an interesting product first then stating his commentaries as well. In the case of Chris Wright, the funny part are the mistakes usually done caused by misunderstandings in the English language during a virtual meeting while the commentary by Chris Wright as an English teacher is the serious and educational part.

Almost all stand-up comedians used parodies and commentaries as their funny parts when it comes to general knowledge and current events regarding news on how COVID-19 affected their countries in terms of response, activities, and policies. Reggie Hasibuan acted out as the AIDS, STD, and COVID-19 virus after saying that the viruses in Bali are "territorial." James Caraan acted out several characters such as news reporter, teacher, student, a famous vlogger, items hoarded from a community pantry such as egg tray and "eco-bag", and even Satan based on the local news regarding the pandemic. Harith Iskander acted out as different ministers in the Malaysian government who faced issues during the pandemic. Nigel Ng acted out as himself being a suspected case of an infection of COVID-19 virus because he can't taste his food well but it turned out that what he was eating was British food.

(A) Venue for Development

Despite the disruption brought about by the pandemic, the online stand-up comedy videos posted in the chosen social media brought developments in socio-

cultural aspect towards the side of the viewers and socio-economic aspect in the side of the performers. As read through textual comments by viewers in Facebook, these range from appreciating the comedian, contributing to the funny or playful parts of the videos, giving trivial information regarding the set-up or the "serious part," tagging their friends who may relate to the content, to bashing the comedian.

In the case of Indonesia where the videos posted are of recorded live performances during the pandemic, the study relied on the recorded reactions of the audiences in the venue. It can be observed from the videos from Indonesia that some jokes are gender-specific as either only the male or female audiences laugh at the set of the comedians. Such example is the joke of Reggie Hasibuan about referring "Indo girls" as "OnlyFans content creator" wherein only female audiences laughed at it and the joke of Annie Yang about online dating using Tinder and the "Tinder Surprise" wherein only male audiences laughed at these.

For the current events and the COVID-19 pandemic wherein a certain person, group of people, or an institution reported as allegedly abusive or have done wrong such as the Malaysian ministers acted out by Harith Iskandar, giving persona to an egg tray and cloth bag also known as "eco-bag" and a fictional Satan by James Caraan to create a joke on the people who hoarded in the community pantry and those people allegedly accusing the organization of community pantries as act of the devil, respectively, that were used as comedy materials, most of the comments from the viewers can be observed as expression of derision to the target of the joke ranging from contribution to the ridicule by either extending the funny part or creating their own funny part, to serious opinion regarding the possible outcomes of the issues used in the comedy material. On the other hand, there can be also observed expressions of derision to the comedians as mentioned earlier regarding the bashing and empathy

on the target of the joke that most likely came from their supporters. Comments showing expressions of empathy for those who could relate to the social effects of the alleged abuse, confusion, and oppression by these certain people and institutions, and the natural effects brought about by the pandemic were also observed and documented. Furthermore, looking back at the Relief Theory wherein “something whether it be ‘psychic energy’ (Freud, 1905 and 1976 in Rutter, 1997, p.13) or ‘nerve force’ (Spencer, 1911 in Rutter, 1997, p.13), builds up within a person’s system and having no more useful purpose, must be released (Rutter, 1997, p.13) and taking the comments as bases, it can be observed that the viewers had a feeling of relief due to having someone through the stand-up comedians somehow indirectly address the issues that the viewers themselves could not express on their own, through the videos that then in turn, they have expressed it through their comments.

For special topics such as food, interesting items found in flea markets, English-speaking etiquette in virtual meetings, and some of the personal details that were used as comedy materials, comments also range from expression of derision to both the target of the joke and the comedian such as the case of Nigel Ng, to expression of empathy as they could relate to the target of the joke, who were the comedians themselves in the case of Alex Calleja regarding his role as husband and father, and Nigel Ng, acting out as the fictional Uncle Roger in his instructional-commentary on how to cook rice "the Asian Way." In the video of Chris Raufeisen, the commenter repeated to highlight the funny part of the comedian regarding a specific alleged counterfeit item found in flea market. Aside from humorous and serious comments from these subjects, others share their personal experiences regarding the matter that in turn became additional information to those reading the comments, such as in the case of the comments in Chris Wright's video.

These were observations in the side of the live audiences in the case of Indonesia, and online viewers in the remaining selected ASEAN member-states. For the side of the comedians, there were developments in their talent and their career despite the given situation. During the course of research, since their content in social media pages are arranged according to what is recently published then followed by those published earlier, it can be observed that they have opened live comedy shows recently when the restrictions were eased as in the case of most comedians, and they have also attracted more listeners to their podcasts and followers in their social media accounts.

The impact through comments and reactions brought about by watching the online stand-up comedy videos published during the pandemic that was observed and documented could develop this understanding that humor through the online stand-up comedy videos during the time of crisis in the form of pandemic, despite the limitations of face-to-face social gatherings and discussions, became both an avenue and a venue for development in social interaction among social media users and the stand-up comedians, further information for social media users in general, and in promotion of career development among the featured stand-up comedians towards the new norm.

Humor as Creative Space for (Virtual) ASEAN Community-Building

A community can be "safe to say is to be distinguished from a city" or any type of development, or "from such groups as a trade-union, lodge, a church, a school" and "may happen to coincide with any of these but usually does not, and need not" as it is a "local grouping of people who share a number of important interests and activities, and who are more concerned about those things which they have in common than about those wherein they differ" (Queens, 1923, p.382). Though the context of the

object of laughter may be "to each of its own" due to localized issues faced by each member-state and its people during the pandemic, there are shared interest and activity among the stand-up comedians as performers and the people as audiences and social media users. It can be observed that there is a shared interest on being entertained through stand-up comedy and while they were entertained as met by the objectives of the performer of making them laugh, and as seen in the reactions chosen that were represented by the emoticons or icons showing emotions in the social media platform of study, there is a shared activity among the audiences and performers as well through the comments made though different types such as commentary on the joke, either joke upon a joke or a plain reaction about it, and commentary on a comment by the viewer.

Despite the different shared sentiments, either for or against the featured comedians, their written material and videos, the target of the joke or the object of laughter, and the commentaries from fellow viewers, the shared activities from watching the video to developing interactions that created an engagement with an outcome of the feeling of entertainment, empathy and derision to certain issues, individual or group of people through comments in social media, have made humor through stand-up comedy videos become a potential creative space for community-building.

CHAPTER V

RECOMMENDATIONS OF THE STUDY

Conclusion

The pandemic definitely effected change in the world in all aspects: economic, political, social, and cultural. Since the prevention of spread the COVID-19 virus requires minimal physical interaction, people relied on technology to continue with their lives in getting what they need such as food and other necessities, and what they want such as entertainment. Humor penetrated during this time of crisis by use of technology particularly creation and release of stand-up comedy videos in social media platforms such as Facebook, with the styles being used by the featured stand-up comedians in selected ASEAN member-states being parallel with those from stand-up comedians from other parts of the world yet using local and personal context, and cultures as comedy materials, thus the development of understanding that humor through these online stand-up comedy videos as "glocal" due to global in approach, and local in content, in the side of the stand-up comedians as the sender and content creator.

For the receiving end, through the comments and reactions of the social media users and those who attended the live performances in the case of Indonesia, humor through the online stand-up comedy videos became both an avenue and a venue for development of interaction and various emotions such as derision, empathy, and relief among social media users and stand-up comedians as the author of the posted videos, development of additional information for social media users in general who have accessed and viewed the videos including the comments and reactions of fellow users, and development of talent and promotion of the featured stand-up comedians.

ASEAN, through its Socio-Cultural Community (SCC) Blueprint aims and serves to be a space for addressing issues and promoting shared culture in line with building a people-centric community (ASEAN SCC Blueprint 2007) as seen in the creative approach in promoting culture by its people (Cohen 2014) and as discussed in the Meta-Nation State Framework by Dr. Sylvano Mahiwo (2014). However, the status quo of a “top-down” approach in dealing with culture by ASEAN Member States (Lindsay 1995) have been discussed as a step back to the goal of the organization. The online stand-up comedy videos by professional stand-up comedians during the period of the COVID-19 crisis, together with the outcome of engagement through reaction and commentaries by both viewers and some replies by the comedians in social media and live performances, has shown that these can be a creative space for building a people-centric community, either virtual or physical, that the organization has been gearing towards. Hopefully through this understanding of humor in the form of online stand-up comedy videos by stand-up comedians from selected ASEAN member-states would not only contribute to the field of Aseanology but also would recognize that the diverse culture in the region, one of which is humor through stand-up comedy, is thriving as observed through the lens of selected ASEAN member-states in the study regardless of a selected period of time.

Recommendations

This study is recommended to the fields of social sciences, communication, and performing arts focusing on the ASEAN region, and for those who have ample timeframe, further research can be done relevant to this study such as limiting its study on a single video to give focus on the social media accounts who gave comments and reactions regarding the video whether if these accounts are real, fake or considered a "troll" account wherein one is paid to make a comment or reactions in social media as instructed by someone whose goal is to either defame someone or increase engagement for monetary purposes. One can also give focus to the stand-up comedian who posted these videos by interviewing them regarding relevant information about themselves with respect to their content such as religious preference, political stance, and personal life provided that the ethics of research with regards to human subjects are being observed. Having recommended those, this study could be one of those that would help initiate people-centric studies on the field of Aseanology as the region as an organization has been aiming for.

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Appendices

APPENDIX A

Text Versions of the Comedy Videos

Annie Yang (Indonesia)

Annie: I do experience a near death experience once in my life. So, uhm, my sister tried to kill me [small L] Well, {chuckled a bit} I'm not saying like she's so entitled, she's pretentious, that she's so annoying that it's killing me, no. It's more like she punched me in the face and choked me to death. [one person L softly] Like, I don't know. Like, you know like I know my family is messed up. My family is fucked up you know. My family is so fucked up that I probably am the best outcome from that family [gradual L]. Yeah, and at that time, when you have a near-dead experience, you just kind of like thinking about your life, your life just like flashes in front of you and then when at that moment, when my sister (is) choking me, I, I realized like you know, I'm sorry. I'm kind of like emotional every time I talk about my family. So that time, I realized that...I like being choked [gradual L]. So, you know right every time I have sex with a guy, and I, I asked him to choke me and I was like "this is what you got? [few people L] this is what you called 'choking'? [L---->A] My sister can do it better!" [L and A together] But, ah..haha, hey I came here with a date. [few men C], ah...he's nice....uh...he looks all right...he don't....he didn't talk too much which is perfect, [few L] right? But sadly he cannot stay and watch me perform because I think he feels like awkward because it's our first meeting. You know I met him online...Yeah I met him on this app...Uh not Tinder. The other one...Go Jack. [L] You know, it's the only app that guarantee your date has its own vehicles [L--->A]. You know he pick you up and he drop you off. So chivalry is not dead yet. And then he also had a, a job [one person L] yeah. uh but like okay. So cheers. If you are on Tinder make some noise! [few C] All right, it's it's like ten percent (10%) of you and the rest of you are fuckin' liar. [L] Yeah like okay so if

you don't know {making quotation marks in the air while saying "don't know"} Tinder is, Tinder is an app. You can download it for free, right? It's an app for you to choose someone you want to ahh...fuck [few people L] It's basically a fuck app. [one person giggled] But I don't know if you know this but do you know that there's this such thing as Tinder Surprise. And you don't know right? Like I will tell you this: Tinder surprise...is when you match with someone you decided to meet with them...when you met with them, they look nothing like their profile. [small L] Camera guy. What's your name?

Camera Guy: David

Annie: David! Alright. So if you are in Tinder, you match with someone you date. (and then) looks nothing like their profile. Won't you spend a night them?

David: Nope.

Annie: {shocked} "No?!" You shallow motherfucker! [L] Being a woman right and on dating area I have my fair share of weird date...one time when I was...when I went to Bali, I met with this guy and then I, uh, we decided to have dinner...and then I was...I arrived first at the restaurant and I was there wearing mask, health protocol and all of that you know, and then he arrived...and once he entered the restaurant, I was like, "Thank God, it he's not a 'Tinder Surprise'." [two people L] Oh, he's fit, He's good looking, I bet he has a huge dick so, so he was there. He enters the restaurant, he approached me...And I swear to God in my life, I *never* have anyone say these words to me. It feels magical, it feels amazing. You know like when he arrived like he approached me. He looked at me in my eyes and then he said, "so you are one of those people who believe in Corona, yeah?" {giggled a bit} What the fuck! And conspiracy theories?! Really?! {continues being funny about what she had told} [some people L] at that...you guys know a Disney movie "Inside Out" right like where this feeling inside your head how it works, I can feel like anger, disbelief, disappointment,

just like all negative emotions just popping out one by one but they cannot do anything because horny {adjective that is used as noun} is taking over control [L] And then horny that bitch was like "yeah let's turn off the brain because we're not going to use this anytime soon." So whole night wrong. Right? I (am) sitting there, I laugh at his jokes, right? And then, then one time...and then one day he asks me, what do you do for fun? And I was like "I do comedy." And then he laugh(ed). He said "you're joking. Women can('t) do comedy, women are not funny" [B] Motherfucker! A sexist too! [one person L] You know, and then like, "cut to the scene where I was on my knees." So, {then acted out the time she was down on her knees} [some L--->A---->C] {still on her knees, facing the audience} So, I was on my knees right and I was like "you know what, this is it. this is what I've been waiting for." Right? Like he better have a really big dick and it's like once I unzip his pen(is), he's going to hit me in the face, give me concussion-kind of dick right? But, when I was like on my knees I was like, "where's the rest of it? This is it?! This is what I've been waiting for?!" Like, you know but I was at that time I was naive. No. Like, I was horny. [two people L] I was like, thinking, "you know what Annie? It doesn't matter what the size is, the most important thing is how he used it." Right? I was such a fool. [few people L] And so I was there laying you know. Just kind of like "make it quick..." He did [L--->C] Uh and then...I shit you not, right? Like and then when he just like thrust his hip like that, right? And then just kind of like his breath getting raggedy and then he shouts like "COVID vaccine has microchip!" [few people L] And I was like "what the fuck!" I had so many questions, one, like, "did he shout out every conspiracy theories every time he's about to come?" [L] Or he's thinking about COVID vaccine when he...when he like five seconds he's inside me [L]

Reggie Hasibuan (Indonesia)

Reggie: {standing on stage in front of a live audience} ...also I see a lot of Indos here, {then shouted} Indos! make some noiiiise! [C] yeaahh! My sisters and brothers! All right, I see a lot of Indo sisters, hello Indo sisteerrrs! [C women only] *Selamat malam* (good night or good evening)! *Om swastiastu* (a Balinese greeting that means, "Hope you got a lot of blessing from The God, has a lot of happiness, hopefully, you are in a good condition for the gift of Sang Hyang Widhi")!...or if you're hiding from your parents in Java, then "*Assalamualaikum*" (a traditional Islam greeting that means "peace be with you")! [L] Some call them Indo girls, some call them local girls, I call them Only Fans content creator! [women only L] Ladies and gentlemen! My name is Reggie Hasibuan and I am the first English-speaking comedian from this country! [C] And it's not easy you know, becoming comedian because I got stereotype(d) all the time. I was in Singapore and you know I also addressed my nation, like "Indonesiaa! make some noiiiise!" And the only applause I got were from the dishwashers [L] Even there, they were applauding awkwardly [L] They were like: {acting out the dishwashers by clapping slowly and softly with a facial expression equivalent of someone confused} [L] {then still acting out as dishwasher talking to another} "Bro...bro...bro, indo bro, indo bro!" [L--->C---->L] {then shifted to fellow dishwasher as if replying} "oh yeah! what is he doing on stage? [L] He should be here with us washing dishes! [L] Very not appropriate!...Not appropriate!" [L] (When) I was in Malaysia, the same thing! They asked me, "hey! where are you from?" I answered honestly, "Indonesia!" {then he shifted to the one who is asking as he replied} "Ohhh! Indon! {laughing mockingly} Wash my caar! Clean my toileets! Nurse my dying grandmaa!" [L] Look, I am mistaken for a maid! I am not a maid! I am a comedian! You know what is the difference between a comedian and a maid? Maid makes more money! [L] But after travelling here and there, now I'm in Bali, ladies and gentlemen! [C]...And Bali is crazy! You guys are crazy

coz' you don't give a shit about COVID! {shrieks in awe} [C] And I understand because you guys got more important problems to take care of! [L] yeah!...like Herpes, Syphilis, Gonorrhea, Chlamydia, AIDS! [continuous L] I understand, I understand, yeah! when COVID comes hahaha!...Take a number! [L]...I think...I think...when COVID first hit Bali, she had to give respect to the more senior diseases already in the island [L] So COVID be like {started acting out as if COVID is introducing oneself in a flirty manner} "Hello! I'm newww! I'm Corona, call me Rona!" {then winked} [L] And AIDS be like "Holy shit! I've used to be the hotshot but look at me now! [L] All right....rookie, rookie...newbie...over here...You're new...you're big deal I know you're lethal...yeah yeah...but to where do we play here in Bali is that we are territorial. [L] All right? [L] So the places where the people are fucking, you leave them to me. [L] So you leave Canggu alone [L] and put ah...{he burst in small laughter thus breaking his act then returned to it} [then L] However...there is one place in Bali where the people are not fucking as much and they still deserve to die...so Ubud is yours. [L] We all can reduce those vegan." [L]

Nigel Ng (Malaysia)

Video # 1

Nigel: {looking worried while a caption in Tiktok format was shown that he himself wrote} "Apparently, loss of taste and smell is an early symptom of COVID-19" {then a new set of caption that he also wrote followed while still looking worried} "Starting to get worried cause I couldn't taste any flavor in my lunch earlier." {after a few moments, from dominantly-bass background music, it shifted to a clearer one with treble but with the same music, and the video background has a disco lights effect while Nigel is dancing as if rejoicing because of the next caption that was written this way:} "Turns

out, it's just British food. {at the end of this caption, an emoji or emoticon equivalent to a laughing expression was flashed}"

Video # 2

Nigel: I went to a Malaysian restaurant a few days ago down in Chinatown, right? I order my food and then the waiter asked me if I had any food allergies. [few L] That's not what we do back home! [L] For street food? If you eat a peanut and die, we just pack our shit and {acts out riding a bicycle} cycle away! [L] {then acts out as his father} "Oh shit, leave the chopsticks, let's go son!" [L] {Then he shifted back as himself} "Why is he on the floor daddy? {shifted back as his father} "He's just taking a nap, man!" [L] "Who gives a fuck?" [L] {shifted back as himself as narrator} Asian parents don't even believe in food allergies, man. [few L] right? My parents don't believe in that shit. You tell parents you have a peanut allergy they'll be like {acting out as a typical Asian parent} "no, no, no, no, no, no such thing" [few L] "They're only strong people {pointing one side of the audience to draw division}, and then there are weak people {pointing to the opposite side}" [L] "How can you be a man if a peanut fucks you up?" [L] "If peanut kill my son, I have no son, alright?" [L]..."walk it off, pussy!" [L] "And what the fuck is gluten?" [L] {shifted back as narrator} Had to tell my parents I had hay fever last summer, and that's the closest I felt to coming out of the closet. [L] {acts out as if he was talking to his mom} "I have something important to say mom...trees make me sneeze, [L] please don't Sharpie me off the family photos!" {acted out as if marking something in a picture using a pen} [L] {acted out as someone looking at the said picture} "Who's that dark figure?" {then acted out as his parents answering the question} "Oh we don't talk about him anymore." [L] "He needs Benadryl." [L] "Summer fucked him up." [L] {shifted back as narrator} My dad doesn't believe in antibiotics

either, man. He thinks it's cheating, your body has to learn how to fend for itself. I'm like, "that's not how chlamydia works, dad." [L] "I can't just walk that off, okay?" [L]

Video # 3

Nigel: {as Uncle Roger} My name is Uncle Roger. Today, I will review white people's favorite type of rice. {shows a product in front of the camera} Uncle Ben's Instant Microwave bullshit! This flavor is spicy Mexican. {looking at the package} I think it's OK. {looks at the camera} Uncle Roger like spicy and Uncle Roger loove Mexicans. {looking at the product again then faces the camera} But why is this rice in pouch? Asians we don't buy rice in pouch. {then shows off a sack filled with rice} We always buy the big sacks. 10 kilos. So nice, so big. You slap (it), so satisfying. {slaps the sack} Sometimes I sleep next to the rice {caressing the sack like a pillow} after my wife left. {made a sigh then next scene, he holds the product for review again} Now I have to cook the rice. {he put the whole pouch into the microwave oven to heat, then after heating, he took it out} Ow! Ow! So hot! Haiya...{his remarkable expression as Uncle Roger} (I) burn my hand! {cut scene to the rice was already in a plate} Done cooking, gonna have taste test. {puts some rice in the spoon and gets it close to the camera}. It looks pretty disgusting {blows it to cool down then tastes it} Ugh! {spits the food} Horrible! Horrible! No flavor, no taste, no spicy, no Mexican! My unborn baby cook better rice than this! So horrible, taste like sad.

Video # 4

Nigel: {as Uncle Roger} Hallo! It's Uncle Roger. Since my last video, many people asking me, how to make rice? Today I show you the "Asian Way." Uncle Roger have many white friend tell me, they use saucepan. {shows off a saucepan} Saucepan?! Haiyaa {his notable reaction again} World War Two is over! Use technology! Proper Asian use(s) rice cooker. {shows off a rice cooker and opens the lid then cut to scene

that a rice is poured onto the rice bowl} Step one: pour the rice in the rice bowl. {cut scene to rice was shown being washed} Step two: wash the rice {cut scene to using finger to measure water level} Step three: use finger to measure water. {cut scene to Nigel putting back the rice bowl to the cooker} Now put it back in rice cooker and press play {he pressed a button to start the rice cooker and a starting tune played similar to the Alphabet song signaling the start of its operation, then cut scene to Nigel waiting for the cooker to finish} Let rice cooker handle the cooking. Now you have time to think about your sad life, {camera zooms to Nigel} why do people you love always leave you {made a sigh then video turned black and white while this scene was done, then cut scene to another tune played from the cooker signaling that it is done} Now rice is ready, open the rice cooker, and fluff the rice. {camera focuses on the rice bowl while Nigel is mixing the rice} Oh my God so nice so satisfying...better than sex.

Video # 5

(Note: some parts of the video might not be included as it is long; only the parts where it is considered the setup and the funny part will be documented)

Nigel: {as Uncle Roger} No, no, no {showing disapproval to how the recipe was mixed as shown on the other side of the screen}{Jamie's voice was played saying} "I like this a lot" {then Nigel is crying in shame} This (is) not how you make green curry haiyaaa (his trademark expression) {repeated what he said} This not how you make green curry haiyaaa. {then the multi-colored screen used by television stations with the bleeping sound was briefly shown to cut the introduction then cut to scene focusing on Nigel} Mr Chili Jam a.k.a. Jamie Olive Oil. {then Jamie's picture was shown with a caption of how Uncle Roger called him} He disappoint Uncle Roger's so many time now. How his Thai green curry chicken gonna be? {the orig video of Jamie was shown, Jamie is speaking} "Guys, we're gonna make green curry, it's delicious, fragrant. My

family love it. We gonna go one cup of rice. That's enough for four people" {screen splitted to show Nigel expressing disapproval, video of Jamie paused to let Nigel speak} One cup of rice for four people? Is your whole family just baby bird? {a picture of baby birds was shown} Haiyaa. That like five grain(s) of rice each. You starving your children, Jamie. 8 second in, already make mistake. he (is) the Usain Bolt of fucking up. {Jamie's video shown again and he is pouring two cups of water and claiming to be a perfect equation for the perfect fluffy rice} "A pinch of salt, lid on, top medium heat, happy days." {then Nigel reacts as the screen splits again} No no no not happy day, no. You don't have rice cooker. It's sad day for Uncle Roger. {back to Jamie's video explaining he will make a paste while peeling a thumb-sized piece of ginger, using his thumb as reference, Nigel was shown again briefly, shaking his head} Haiyaa, ginger wrong! use Galangal! Galangal! {repeated with echo} Nobody use ginger for Thai green curry. Nobody! {back to Jamie's video putting the ginger to food processor, intently replaying the scene, then Nigel reacted first with a sigh} Food processor...Jamie I thought you have pestle and mortar, when you making the Malaysian fish video {that video was shown briefly on the side} I see you have pestle and mortar, where is it? Use your pestle and mortar, where is it? Niece and nephew (how Nigel as Uncle Roger addresses his viewers and followers), food processor, not replacement for pestle and mortar because food processor just slice shit up, (while) pestle and mortar can do Uncle Roger favorite thing: pounding {intro of George Michael's Careless Whisper being played} Pounding bring out all the flavor. Maybe that('s) why Auntie Helen (Uncle Roger's ex-wife) pound so many other people {back to Jamie's green curry video, showing the lemongrass as next ingredient, hitting it to a table then Nigel reacts} No no no no. Stop spanking. Spanking not gonna do anything, you gonna throw it all in food processor anyway, it's spinning at 9000 RPM.

If you spank harder than food processor, then I feel bad for Mrs. Oliver (pertaining to Jamie's wife). {a famous introduction music for a pornographic site was played briefly} Sorry, Jamie's children. {back to Jamie's video now showing the lemongrass being split and put in the processor and garlic, then 6 leaves of Kaffir lime to which Nigel both approves, next is cumin, but Nigel barely agrees, while Jamie was slicing, the video was edited to focus on a running woman behind the door then Nigel reacted to it} Wait! Who's that? See I think that Jamie's wife running away from spanking {back to Jamie's video, he used 3 chilis to which Nigel reacts} What? Three? Just three chili for you(r) curry? Haiyaa...Uncle Roger making Thai green curry for 4 people, I gonna use like 20 or 30 chili, But he use 3? That's less than 1 chili per person. Why even bother with the chili? This not gonna be curry, this gonna be smoothie! Haiyaa. Not enough chili. Uncle Roger predict your curry not even gonna have green color. Keep watching video, see if Uncle Roger prediction correct. {replaying the chili seeds removed} Also, why (are) you deseeding the chili? Why? Uncle Roger realize this is white people favorite thing. They liked throwing out seeds of chili. Seed is where all the flavor is. Don't be pussy, eat your chili seed, haiyaa. Jamie, don't take the seed out, you got five children you have more than enough seed. {Jamie was shown mixing the paste and frying the chicken to which Nigel reacts} Metal spoon on non-stick pan, that's not even the biggest crime in this picture. You're not supposed to fry chicken like this for green curry haiyaa. you need to mix the chicken with the paste and then stir fry it together. Jamie Oliver haven't get one thing right so far. You just making chicken stir-fry now and earlier you make smoothie {a picture of a chicken stir fry then a green smoothie was shown alongside} He making every other food except green curry! What crazy thing he gonna do next? {Jamie showing gathering mushrooms to which Nigel reacts} What? Nobody put mushroom in curry! {pretending to be crying in shame then

returned to Jamie's video showing the amount of mushrooms}400 grams? First he uses three chilis then 400 grams of mushroom? Now he is making mushroom soup haiyaaa {said this in disappointment} Too much mushroom? Who gonna eat this much mushroom in one meal? Jamie, just because you put in Enoki mushroom, it don't make this dish any more Asian. This curry is so white, it's about to book spa holiday. {back to Jamie's video showing the chicken being pushed to one side for the mushrooms, Nigel reacts} Don't push to one side, throw it out and start over. {Huge chunks of mushroom being shown included in the pan} Look at that mushroom, that big ass piece of mushroom. Who want(s) to eat that in your curry? You're just eating green curry than just one big blob of mushroom get in your mouth {acting out as if a mushroom have hit him} And when you cook mushroom all the water from the mushroom come out, so this dish not even gonna taste like green curry. It gonna taste like mushrooms sweat! Haiyaa (with reverb effect). {then back to Jamie's video, the chicken and mushroom were mixed together then the paste is being put in the pan to which Nigel reacts} No, no, no, no! {crying} Uncle Roger is so upset, I put my legs down from chair. This (is) not how you make green curry haiya. You don't just wack it in like it's soy sauce. (In the) green curry you cook the coconut milk, pour the green paste in, and then you boil until the fat coming to surface {while this being said, the correct process was shown} Beautiful green fat. Not just throwing random shit in pan. {Nigel shakes his head while the video shifted to black and white with raining effect while a gloomy music is being played as background}This is worse than his egg fried rice video. Where did you learn how to make Thai green curry? From Kay's cooking channel is it {then a picture of a certain Kay was shown}? Haiyaa. {replayed Jamie's remark that cooking is fast} Don't brag that it's fast. It's easy to be fast if every step (is) wrong. {Jamie's video being shown again where the coconut milk was mixed late and next is

a mangetout to which Nigel reacts} (You) put in so much. Remember, 3 chili, 3, and 200 grams of the worst vegetable ever, mangetout. If vegetable taste like sad, Mangetout taste like terror.{Nigel crying then cut scene to commenting again} Is this what British people think green curry is? Is this what they eating? {Back to Jamie's video remarking to play with the green curry and make it your own version to which Nigel reacts} Don't make it your own. Make it Thai, please. {then Jamie puts fish sauce in the video} No. Fish sauce. Wrong brand. Everybody buy fish sauce, you buy the squid brand, not this bullshit brand {referring to what Jamie used; then back to Jamie where lime and basil are used} Wrong again, nobody used lime, wrong again, Thai basil just use a pluck, just pluck, don't slice. How many things can he get wrong in one video, haiya. I can't even put my leg back up on chair ever again. {after showing the finishing touches of the recipe, Nigel reacts} Niece and nephew, does this look Thai green curry to you? Uncle Roger put on screen (to) show you side-by-side, Haiyaa, this doesn't look like green curry at all {referring to Jamie's on the right of the screen} See, this curry don't even look green. he didn't use enough green chili. What is this mangetout mushroom bullshit? {camera focusing on the mangetout and mushrooms} If your curry mostly look like mangetout and mushroom, you fucked up. Uncle Roger can't even say haiya anymore. It('s) too much pain. I'd rather have Auntie Helen leave me again. He has no pestle and mortar, but somehow he still crush all my hope(s) and dream(s). {back to video, Jamie used Basmati rice with it to which Nigel reacts} Basmati rice, wrong rice. Use Thai Jasmine rice for Thai green curry. Is he trying to get Guinness world record for most fucked-ups in one cooking video? {Nigel shook his head showing disappointment} {back to video where Jamie tasted it and was impressed with his own cooking to which Nigel reacts} Uncle Roger never hear anyone describe curry as tropical before {Jamie suggested to alternate tofu for chicken in his

video, Nigel reacted} No, don't put tofu. I see before what you do with tofu. Leave tofu alone. {Jamie introducing his own version of Thai green curry, Nigel reacts} He so clueless but confident. Where he get all his confident(ce) from? Regular people have Impostor Syndrome. Jamie have the opposite of that. This Jamie make Uncle Roger cry again. The only thing he get right is the set design. This is pretty. This is old school Victorian English kitchen remind me of simpler times...back when Jamie Oliver can't upload YouTube video

Harith Iskander (Malaysia)

Video # 1

Harith: {acting out like a journalist by holding a pen and paper while asking something to Trump} Excuse me, Mr. President, could you tell us a little bit about the collated work of scientists and researchers are doing with regards to the COVID-19?

Trump: {the interview video is now played} "They developed a drugs, like the antibiotics. You see it?"

Harith: {looking serious in sarcasm} Yes. Yes, I have "seen" {drawing quotation marks on air} an antibiotic. Are you saying that the antibiotic might be the cure for COVID-19?

Trump: {back to the video} "Antibiotics used to solve every problem. Now the biggest problems the world has, is the germ has gotten so brilliant..."

Harith: {cutting the video of Trump} Excuse me?

Trump: {that certain part of his answer being replayed} "...the germ has gotten so brilliant..."

Harith: {cutting again} Could you say that again please?

Trump: {that part replayed again but with a fuller version} "...the germ has gotten so brilliant, that the antibiotic can't keep up with it, and the constantly trying to come up

with a new...people would go to a hospital and they catch, they go for a heart operation, that's no problem..." {cut scene to Harith is shown taking notes then returned to the video} "...but they end up dying from...from...problems...you know the problems I'm talking about?"

Harith: No! No...I don't know the problem that you're talking about.

Trump: {video played again} "ah...there's a whole genius to it. We are fighting not only as a hidden, it's very smart, okay? it's invisible. and it's hidden. But it's...it's very smart."

Harith: So, it's invisible, it's hidden, and it's very smart...everything you are not. Thank you very much Mr. President!

Trump: {just audio being played as outro} "I want to find a friendly reporter!"

Video # 2

Harith: {as the journalist from White House} Mr. President, Mr. President. The N95 respiratory protective device is designed to keep out 95% of particles as small as 0.5 microns. What do you recommend the public use to stay safe?

Trump: {his interview video being played} "You know you can use a scarf. A scarf is everybody...ah a lot of people have {the error tone of a computer operating system was played while Harith was shown wearing a scarf while writing to what Trump says} scarfs and you can use a scarf. Scarf would be very good. And I, my feeling is that people wanted to do it, they certainly no harm to it {then same tone was played while Harith was shown wearing another scarf this time it's sort of a Niqab for Muslim girls} and ah, I would say that you do it but use a scarf if you want {Harith was shown again wearing another type while the tone of a dial-up connection process was being played} you know rather than going out in getting a mask or whatever, we'll making millions and millions of masks {Harith was then shown wearing a Spiderman mask while a funny tune was played} but we wanted to go to ahh hospitals and one of the things

that Dr. Fauci told me today is that we don't want them competing, we don't want everybody competing with the hospitals where you really need them {a cricket sound was played while Harith was shown wearing a Captain America mask} so you can use scarfs, you can use something else to cover your face. Doesn't have to be a mask {Harith was shown using a women's bra as a mask while the tune of a sci-fi drama series was being played} but it's not ideal at least for, or a period of time. I mean eventually you not gonna want to do that, you not gonna have to do that, this is going to be...gone. It'll be gone. Hopefully gone for a long time."

Harith: {in sarcasm} Gone for a long time, Mr. President? Well, we wish you all the best. Oh. You mean the Corona Virus? Of course, of course {then looks at the camera} {an audio only of the last part of Trump's interview was played and a reporter said} "Your attacking our organization!" {as Trump then replied} "Your organization...your organization sucks."

Video # 3

Harith: {as a deputy minister, clears his throat and checks sound of his microphone as if in a press conference} Check...one...two...one...two... *Assalamualaikum* (a traditional Islam greeting meaning "Peace be with you") *Apa khabar semua?* (Malaysian for "how are you guys doing?") Thank you for coming here today. I need to explain the "new" SOP (Standard Operating Procedure usually prescribed by the director of health in Malaysia) hah. Because I know a lot of the *rakyat* (Malay for "people") is *kompuse* (confused). Haah...I don't know why they *kompuse*. (it) is actually very easy...the new SOP is almost the same as the old SOP. And the old SOP was just like the old-new SOP. Ahh. *Senang aje*. (Malay for "it's fun"). So if you have any question, please...ask question {then acting out as if entertaining a question from someone then repeated it for the viewers} *Apa dia?* (Malay for "what is that?") Alcohol?

Ahh. Alcohol categorized by the National Security Council (MKN) as non-essential. Therefore...banned! Ahh. *Tak boleh jual* (Malay for "can't sell" or "not allowed to sell")...is banned. Kenot! Kenot! (Cannot). *Lagi pun* (Malay for "even though") alcohol is no good for the SOP, because when people the drinking drinking, then they come out, suddenly, they love-love everybody. They see their friend, they want to hug the friend {acting out a hugging movement} "I love you brother...ooh you are like my brudder!" *Tak boleh!* (Malay for "can not!") *Patah S.O.P.!* (Malay for "S.O.P. is broken/foiled") The SOP is broken! *Tak boleh!* One meter! Must keep away! (talking about social distancing) hah. Any other question? {same gesture as the first question was done} Um? Cigarette? Rokok? Ah. Rokok is also non-essential. *Tapi* (Malay for "but") *boleh jual* (Malay for "can sell" or "allowed to sell") Ahh. Why? Because it's essential to the cigarette addict! Ahaaa...You don't know, if you are not a smoker...you will understand. Do you smoke? Ah, you don't smoke! Where you from? Ah. Perlis. No wonder, lah! Haha! You don't know, cigarette addict. They must get the cigarette. If they don't get, it will be a problem. *Tak dapat rokok*, (Malay for "can't smoke"; he is telling if the addict could not smoke,) suddenly, like {acting out as if the addict is shivering to a fever} *Geram je *bunyi moto* (Malay for "sounding like a motorcycle") *Tak boleh!* We must look after our addicted rakyat! We must take care of them. *Lagi pun* if you have no cigarette...then the rakyat? What happen to them? Hah, what will happen? They will turn to heroin! *Macam mana tu? Macam mana tu?* (Malay for "How is that?") You know how difficult it is to shoot up heroin {acting out as if injecting heroin} when you are doing Zoom conference? *Susah tu.* (Malay for "that's hard!") *Tengah Zoom-Zoom* (Malay for "at the middle of a Zoom meeting") you have to {acting out as if he hides the heroin by spanking his arms}...*nakikat lagi* (Malay for "tie again") Susah! Kenot! At least dengan rokok boleh (malay for "with cigarettes"), you just light under

the table {acting out the lighting of cigarette under a table} "ahh *senang tu!*" (another Malay for "that's fun!) Ah...{talking to a fictional person asking} *apa dia?* Do I smoke? Eh...it's not about me...it's not about me...I'm not important myself. It's about the *rakyat*. The *rakyat* we must look after them. Ah..so I think...*macam ni* (Malay for "like this")...*kalau apa apa*...if there is nothing else, I *nak pergi* roko...roko...roko...zen {about to take out a cigarette in his pocket but opted to mention that he will go to a Japanese restaurant} My friend's restaurant. I take...not! Take-away from the restaurant because now cannot eat at the restaurant {then gets out of his seat in the press conference setup}

Video # 4

Harith: *Assalamualaikum*. Welcome. Thank you all for coming here. Saya akan jawab soalan anda (Malay for "I will answer your questions"). Will answer your questions. {a photo of a news headline about the above-mentioned issue was flashed in the video} *Apa dia? Komen mengenai timbalan menteri yang Nikah online?* with an Imam in a *Masjid kedai baru di Golok?* (he was "asked" to give comments on the recent news on a deputy minister that "allegedly" did an online Nikah ceremony with an Imam in an Masjid in Golok, a place in Thailand). First of all, *Fitnah!* (Malay for "slander!") Fake news! *Mana ada Masjid yang call itself "Masjid Kedai Baru"* (Malay-English for "Where is this you call 'New Shop Mosque'") Is it a *Kedai?* (Malay for "shop") or a *Masjid?* (local term for "Mosque") How would you feel if I *buka* a *Kedai* and call it "*Masjid Baru?*" (*Buka* is Malay for "open" and *Baru* is "new") Confused *tak* you all? You *nak datang sembahyang ke beli buku?* (Malay for "here, you want to come to prayer, to buy a book") Confuse! Confuse! Ahh. *Tapi, seperti yang dijelaskan oleh the timbalan menteri* (Malay for "but as explained by the Deputy Minister"). This is a private matter {spoken this phrase in Malay before this as "Ini

perkara peribadi} Why you all sibuk-sibuk? Proboke-proboke? The Timbalan Menteri told Sinar Harian and I quote: "*Isu seperti ini sepatutnya tipak tidak berlaku*" (Malay for "Issues like this should not happen") What? Does he mean that the Nikah *sepatutnya tidak berlaku?* (Malay for "should not have happened?") No! The video *sepatutnya tidak berlaku!* Who would be so stupid to break the law...and then video and upload the video online? It should not have happened! Takkan you nak makan durian PKPP atau (Malay for "You don't want to eat durian either in PKPP")...you nak visit your friend for lunch, then upload the video online. It should have happened. You will not do it! Ah. What's that? The timbalan yang dipertua majlis agama Islam wilayah Narathiwat. Abdul Aziz Che Mat menjelaskan pihaknya tidak pernah mengiktiraf . Pernikahan secara dalam talian? (Malay for "the vice president of the provincial religious council in Narathiwat, Abdul Aziz Che Mat, explained that his party had never considered an online wedding?") Haha! This is where he is wrong! *Inibukan secara talian.* (Malay for "this is not online!") Nobody is calling calling "Hallo hallo" This was online...*atas talian...on-the-line..ah...Macam Tinder, Macam Grinder* (Malay for "Just like Tinder, just like Grinder") What is Grinder? {cricket sound playing} I dunno. Anyway, they didn't calling calling. This one is video calling in *norma baru* (Malay for "new norm" or "new normal") haha! But I repeat it, it shouldn't have happened. What? Why Nikah right now during this time when the entire country is struggling, orang yang tak da makan, tak da nasi, and why Nikah in the first place? *Ini you kena salahkan Spanish Fly.* (Malay for, "it's your fault, Spanish Fly").

Video # 5

Harith: *Assalamualaikum.* Thank you all for coming here. I will answer your question. *Apa dia? Kat depan tu?* (Malay for "what is that? That front page?") {a photo of a news headline stating "sorry, can't take pictures, videos" in Malay} My comment? When it

was reported in the morning Timbalan Menteri Ahmad Amzad said "*kerajaan tak dapat memenuhi permintaan orang ramai...merakam gambar atau video ketika disuntik!*" ("The government could not meet the demands of the people of taking a picture or video during vaccination!" in Malay) Kennot! Kennot! You kennot (cannot) take a video...because this will *menggangu* the *kelancaran* ("disturb the smoothness") of the vaccination process. You *tengah dapat* ("are in the middle of a" in Malay) the vaccine you take out the camera then (when) the nurse of the doctor see the camera, they want to {Harith striking a pose} "Angsang-nayo!" ("Annyeonghaseyo", a Korean greeting in Malay accent) Kennot! You will *menggagu! Tak boleh!* Kennot! Bagaimana in the afternoon pulak...petang ("However in the afternoon, again in the evening..." in Malay), {a photo of a headline stating that public can record themselves getting vaccinated} YB Khairy Jamaluddin said you can take the video...in the vaccination process? {Harith acts out as if puzzled} Caaan! *Apa salahnya? Boleh! Bagus! Memang bagus!* ("What's wrong with it? Yes! Good! Good of course!" in Malay) Because you *nak ingat kan?* ("want to remember, right?" in Malay) You want to remember, you want to posting posting IG story. Ah, this one is my prosterity I remember, *boleh, apa salahnya?* Hm? *Kenapa kompuse? Apa yang kompuse kompuse? Kenapa Timbalan Menteri, pagi-cakap sesuatu, Menteri petang-cakap lain?* ("Why, confused? What is that 'confused'? Why do Deputy Minister said something in the morning then the Minister said something another in the afternoon?" in Malay) This is not Kompusing! The reason the Timbalan Menteri said one thing in the morning and the Menteri said another thing in the afternoon, (is) if you don't want to take a video selfie selfie, you go vaccine in the morning! If you want to take a video selfie selfie, you vaccine in the afternoon! *Apa yang kompuse?!* {laughs in jest} *Tak...boleh...senang aje...*("Not...can...it's fun" in Malay)

Chris: {seated with the show as its background, his skin was laden with effects through a shade of red} Ayt, next is a poorly-named candy I found called "semen" {the photo of the product was shown side-by-side with Chris and the product has its name spelled as "semon"}. This is a real thing. You know I remember at lunchtime I used to walk around and collect "semon" {note that he always purposely pronounced it as "semen"} and then I would trade it like "hey I'll trade you that juice box for this bag of "semon," and I'll even thought this weird little Asian candy...and there's million things you can say about this shit...Jesus...too easy tho' {he speaks a bit gibberish then a sound clip of "Okay Asia!" was played}. Ayt, moving on, there is a bag I came across at the flea market, this is a Dasida bag. {a picture of the mentioned bag was shown next, same format} Uhm, this bag is a gold mine. Dasida is the fuckin holy trinity of random Asian knockoff bullshit, ok? You got your Adidas letters rearranged to say... "Dasida," with two Pumas on top, jumpin' towards a Converse All-Star...and underneath it says "Success For Everything" And it even comes with straps, so you can like, you know, handle your failure. This bag is fuckin' stuuupiiiiid! {laughs mockingly}Hahahahaa! {the "Okay Asia!" sound clip was played again to signify transition} This next shirt is all types of "fucked up." Alright, {a t-shirt was flashed next with a printed "HalloFeen" on it} so this is a shirt I saw in a market, uhm so for 60 Baht or for 2 American Dollars, you can buy the spirit...of HalloFeen. All right whatever the fuck that is. Ahh {reading to his tablet}, the shirt reads "Bringing back the old times. Reason for the Season...." and there's a picture of kids dressed up for what is hopefully Halloween, and below that it says, "Check out the Halloween Window Scene, 2415 East 77 Street, Telsa." So, hey listen, if you're in the area, alright, do me a favor, swing by that address and rescue those kids from the base(ment), make sure the "F" in "HalloFeen" doesn't stand for filicide. {a definition of filicide was shown, which means

a person who kill their kids} I would nothin' to do with this shirt. I would not label up my dog with this. Sometimes, dogs wear clothes {pictures showing dogs wearing clothes} I know a dog all right {then a sound clip someone saying "shut the fuck up!" was played} I know as a dog. Like those kids, you probably running in someone's basement right now {a sound clip of a laughter of an evil character was played} bring your shovel. Ahh, next up, we got an exciting collaboration between Under Armour and Diickiee's! {a photo of boxers with a logo of Under Armour and Dickies put together, was shown} Alright, nothing says "I'm athletic, blue collar and an immigrant" more than these boxers. These are perfect if you are...wanna like play football, and when you're done, you can cut the grass on the field, or if you wanna like run a forty-yard dash at a Home Depot, alright, or low-key these are perfect for sneaking into America. Also, perfect for tailgating an Oakland Raiders game and fighting in a Wendy's parking lot later at night...at least for testing, boys. Oversized Free Bird Gangster T-Shirt, switchblade, not included. And this next one's for the ladies. Let me introduce to you to...Abibos. {a photo of the product with the logo of Adidas but with words spelled as "Abibos" was shown} So these are yoga pants. Awesome. Yoga is the official sport of poor flexible people. You see what they did there like a sex change, they reversed the "D"s, {acting out like commanding someone} "You go to that store, and you will gift for me a Abibos yoga pants." Notice that extra stripe, it's like a bar graph or a...your pu__ {somehow inaudible}. You know what's funny, believe it or not, Abibos was actually a name of a saint who spread Orthodox Christianity in the cockiest moundss actually, {then a photo of Abibos of Nekresi was shown} Abibos, of Nekisome shit ahm, Niewtogekekakeest mounds. Kakeest mounds. So whether you're spreading lies, or just wearing them, don't forget, Abibos. Kakeest mounds. So, next up, this is ah, CNAHRL {a jacket with a distorted logo of Chanel then below it, a word is spelled as CNAHRL}. Uhm, it's also

the world's worst ripoff of Chanel. Look closely...that's right...they changed the "C"s to "G"s then uhm, they made it CNAHRL, Uhm, even the people that make fake Chanel shit are fuckin' offended at this hahaha! This is what you get when you have English teachers put neck tattoo. Ok, next up is Pama{a photo showing a product with a Puma logo spelled as Pama}...fuck...a Pama is just Puma on Anarol right? {acts out as if addicted to Anarol} Which is why it's so jumpy ain't it buddy, yeahh. Hahahaha! {then shifted back to normal speaking} A Pama is less athletic Puma, who can't jump that high alright. Looks like he is jumping up trying to squeezes dick into that "A" {photo was focused to a strand near the Puma's legs sticking to the "A" of the letter in the logo then Chris breathes out heavily}. Next up we got Nay-knee or Na or just Nine {photo of a product showing logo of Nike but spelled as Nine}, all right haha. But is also probably the age of the person who made these. Uhm it looks like the soup ladle but instead of serving up soup, it looks like serves up sweatshop worker tears. Uh, Jesus Christ. Uhm, but there's better than this though. This is what happens if you "just do it"...uh in Asia, but ah with little to no money. Last on our shit list today is ah...Odioos {a photo of a product showing a distorted classic logo of Adidas with the words Odioos} If you wanna dress like the handyman at a Filipino prison, this Odioos is for you. Clearly, a ripoff of Adidas with the four leaves and two stripes. Uhm, Adidas stands for "All Day I Dream About Sports." I wonder what Odioos could stand for..."Our Dog Is Out Of Semen"... "Oriental Devils in Obscure Off brain Shorts"...or maybe uhm "One Day I'll Own Original Sportswear"...perfect. Thanks for watchin' OKAY ASIA. We'll be back soon with some more of that random Asian bullshit. This is Chris Raufeisen signing off from Bangkok, Thailand. No condoms.

Chris Wright (Thailand)

Boss: Don't forget guys, it is good online etiquette to turn on your cameras. {Chris then explains in Thai the meaning of "etiquette", and it entails making eye contact regardless if meetings are held face to face or online}

Boss: Remember, you need to have manners at this company.

Office Lady: Yes, I have many man! {Chris then explains in Thai that "etiquette" and "manners" have the same meaning}

Boss: Without further ado, let's begin {then the video output of the office lady labeled "Pumpkin" on the online meeting platform suddenly went to a halt}

Boss: Ah...Miss Pumpkin? Miss Pumpkin? Is there something wrong with your computer?...Uh...hello?

Miss Pumpkin: Sorry boss, *com hang!*

Boss: What? Com Hanks? I only know Tom Hanks.

Miss Pumpkin: {trying to speak in English} My computer has been hanged

Boss: Uh, you want to hang your computer? {Chris then pops out to explain in Thai that she should have said "My computer froze" then the office lady replied to Chris' explanation}

Miss Pumpkin: Ahhh...like Frozen! {talking about an animated movie} Let it go! {then sings the movie them entitled Let It Go} Let it gooo, let it goooo!

Boss:{continued singing the lines} Can't hold it back anymoore {then stops and returns to as himself} ah wait! Professional....manners....{then a cricket sound was played to signify awkwardness}...yeah. {Chris explains in Thai the context of "freeze" or its past tense version "froze" when it comes to computers and screen displays}

Miss Pumpkin: Okay boss, I want to report...ah...ah...{acting as if she doesn't know what to say next}

Boss: Can't you see I'm talking to my employees!

Lady: You're not wearing any pants!

Boss: {pushing the lady out} We'll talk about this later! {then returning to the meeting}
Some people! Am I right?!

Alex Calleja (the Philippines)

Video # 1

Alex: {situated himself in front of a faucet; talking in front of a camera} *Guys, ngayong panahon ng may Corona Virus, sabi ng mga eksperto, dapat proper washing, 20 seconds, at sabayan mo ng "Happy Birthday"* {pertaining to the traditional song}, *kaya gagawin natin 'yan* {then proceeds with the washing by opening the faucet to apply soap and water then closing the faucet to save water, then starts singing "Happy Birthday" in a faster than traditional tempo of the song; after singing it twice, the camera focused on the dishes as he is done washing and proceeds to speak again in an instructional manner} *Ayan, tapos na yung isang plato. Ngayon naman, susunod na plato.* {then repeats the process again of singing the "Happy Birthday" song while washing another plate; it turns out that he applied the recommended hygiene practice for washing hands in washing the dishes}

(Alex: {situated himself in front of a faucet; talking in front of a camera} *Guys, in time of the Corona Virus, experts say practice proper washing, should last 20 seconds, while singing "Happy Birthday"* {pertaining to the traditional song}, *and we will do it* {then proceeds with the washing by opening the faucet to apply soap and water then closing the faucet to save water, then starts singing "Happy Birthday" in a faster than traditional tempo of the song; after singing it twice he is done washing and proceeds to speak again in an instructional manner} *There, I'm done with a plate. Now, on to the next.* {then repeats the process again of singing the "Happy Birthday" song while

washing another plate; it turns out that he applied the recommended hygiene practice for washing hands in washing the dishes))

Video # 2

Alex: {sported a basketball outfit} Hello there! I am Alex Calleja and welcome to Basketball 101! I am here with my assistant, Rico, and today, I am going to teach you how to steal the ball. Watch and learn! Let's go!

{already in position, Rico is dribbling the ball, and Alex plays defense} I am playing defense! And this is how you steal the ball! {Rico stopped dribbling to secure the ball, then Alex held out a bolo knife, then Rico ran away without the ball, resulting to Alex getting the ball} And that's how you steal the ball! Thank you very much, I am Alex Calleja and tomorrow, we'll be back again for Basketball 101 and I am going to teach you how to escape the prison!

Video # 3

Alex: {video is in black and white; he wore a black shirt with a white wall as his background; started singing the first few lines of the song} *Di niyo ba naririnig?*

A voice of a woman: {yells from afar; not in video} *Hoy! Kanina pa kita tinatawag eh! Maglalaba ka pa! Di mo ba naririnig?*

Alex: {unfazed; continued singing after the woman yelled} *Di niyo ba naririnig? Tinig ng misis kong galit!* {turns out that the woman is his wife}

Wife: {still yelling from afar} *Hoooy! Bilisan mo na ha!*

Alex: *Oo! Andyana!* {then scratched his head in annoyance}

(**Alex:** {video is in black and white; he wore a black shirt with a white wall as his background; started singing the first few lines of the song} *Di niyo ba naririnig?*

A voice of a woman: {yells from afar; not in video} Hey! I've been calling you a while ago! You'll have to do the laundry! Aren't you hearing it?

Alex: {unfazed; continued singing after the woman yelled} Aren't you hearing it? It's the voice of my angry wife! {turns out that the woman is his wife}

Wife: {still yelling from afar} Heeyyy! Double time!

Alex: Yes, I'm coming! {then scratched his head in annoyance}

Video # 4

Alex: {slammed the utensils and talking in a loud manner as if rehearsing something} "*Ayoko na! Sawang-sawa na ako!*" {then shift to another camera angle as if Alex is talking to the camera} "*Ikaw na lang lagi nasusunod sa bahay na 'to! Tatay ako! Pa'no naman yung desisyon ko?! Sobra na!*" {then posed to continue eating}

Son: Daddy! *Ang tapang mo ah!* {Alex nods in agreement then a message tone alert plays hinting that someone sent a message to Alex's phone} *O ayan nag-text si Mommy, pauwi na raw siya! Sabihin mo ulit yung mga sinabi mo kanina ah?*

Alex: {suddenly shifted into a worried voice} *Hindi anak, nagpapractice lang ako habang wala yung mommy mo. Naglalabas lang ako ng sama ng loob. Yung mga narinig mo, atin-atin lang yun. Wag mo sasabihin ah? Nako, kumain ka na, kumain ka na.* {becoming more worried} *Maghuhugas pa ako ng plato pagtapos mo. Atin lang yun! Ito naman.* {son looks at the camera mocking Alex}

(Alex: {slammed the utensils and talking in a loud manner as if rehearsing something} "I hate it! I'm fed up" {then shift to another camera angle as if Alex is talking to the camera}"You always want it your way! I'm the father! How about my decision?! It's too much! {then posed to continue eating}

Son: Daddy! You're so brave! {Alex nods in agreement then a message tone alert plays hinting that someone sent a message to Alex's phone} Here, Mommy sent a message that she's coming home! Repeat what you have said earlier ok?

Alex: {suddenly shifted into a worried voice} No son, I'm just practicing while she's away. I'm just venting out. Anything you have heard will be for just between us. Please don't tell her ok? Come on, just eat. {becoming more worried} I'll still wash the plates when you're done. Those are just between us ok?! {son looks at the camera mocking Alex})

Video # 5

Alex: {in formal suite} *Marami nagtatanong sa akin,* {then impersonate the questions}"Alex, may Ford Everest ka ba? Alex, nasan yung Ford Everest mo?" 'Sus! Lumang joke na yun! {chuckles} *Hindi totoo 'yon!* {then positions himself with a real Ford Everest in the background}"Ako, magkaka-Ford Everest?! *Wala 'yon! Huwag niyo ng intindihin yon, kalimutan niyo na yun!* {saying this while approaching to the driver's door}"O dito muna ako ah {pointing to the vehicle then going near to the driver's door} Ford Everest? {mockingly laughs and shaking his head while opening the door and eventually riding the vehicle} (Many were asking, {then impersonate the questions}"Alex, do you have a Ford Everest? Alex, where is your Ford Everest?" Christ! That's an old joke! {chuckles} Not true! {then positions himself with a real Ford Everest in the background}"Me, having a Ford Everest?! That's nothing! don't mind, and forget it! {saying this while approaching to the driver's door} Anyway, I'll just be here {pointing to the vehicle then going near to the driver's door} Ford Everest? Come on! {mockingly laughs and shaking his head while opening the door and eventually riding the vehicle})

James Caraan (the Philippines)

Video # 1

James (as reporter): {in the studio, as seen in using a logo of a broadcasting company as his background} Secretary Nograles on the line. Thank you for coming

secretary. Secretary what's wrong with your neck? {while saying this, the video on the interviewee side shows the said official dancing using his neck with the caption stating "*Ano ang Pilipinas Kontra Gutom?*" which primarily introduces a government program in fighting hunger during the pandemic} Hello Secretary? Sec...Uh....Can you hear me? Sir? Sir, why are you not blinking? Please blink sir, Please! {while these being said, the official on the interviewee side continues to dance while his eyes are not blinking, as mentioned on purpose by the comedian playing as a reporter. While dancing, a caption on the Tiktok video is showing the explanation of the said program wherein it states "*Ito ay samahan ng gobyerno at private sectors na layong wakasan ang involuntary hunger sa bansa. Target nitong i-ahon ang 1 million Pilipino sa kagutuman pagsapit ng 2022.*" It states that the program is composed of public and private sectors aiming to lift 1 million Filipinos from hunger by 2022}

Video # 2

James as Denier: {jeering and talking in as fast manner as rapping while getting close to the camera and a text caption labelling him as COVID Deniers} *Huwag kayong magpapaniwala diyan sa COVID na yan, gusto lang kumita ng mga doktor diyan sa COVID na yan e. Huwag kayong magpapaniwala diyan, meron bang pulubi atsaka taong-grasa na nagkaroon na ng COVID? Wala di ba? Wala!* {Then caption changes thus labelling him as "same person} *Ay, masakit tyan mo? Nako, usog yan! Halika, lawayan natin!* {then flashes out his tongue to apply saliva onto his hands so that he could apply it to a stomach ache} {jeering and talking in as fast manner as rapping while getting close to the camera and a text caption labelling him as COVID Deniers} Don't believe in that COVID, the doctors just wanted to get rich from that virus! Again, don't believe that! Have you seen beggars and homeless people getting it? There's none! {Then caption changes thus labelling him as "same person} Wait, your stomach

aches? That's just 'usog'! Come, I'll apply it with saliva! {then flashes out his tongue to apply saliva onto his hands so that he could apply it to a stomach ache})

Video # 3

Teacher: Okay. Repeat after me. "Community"

Student: Community

Teacher: "Pantry"

Student: Pantry

Teacher: "Community Pantry"

Student: "Communist Party"

Video # 4

James as Arbitrator: {in plain clothes} Okay. Anu pong reklamo nila? Bakit po sila nandito? (Ok. What is their complaint? What brings you here?)

James as Talking Egg Tray: {wearing an egg tray costume on his head, crying} Ako po yung isang tray na ninakaw nila. Nila Maritess. Gusto ko lang po magreklamo na ang dami nilang ginawa sa akin. Prinito, Nilaga, higit sa lahat, binati! Baboy na baboy na po ako sa sarili ko! ({crying} I am that egg tray that they took away...Took away by a certain Maritess. I just want to complain the things that they have done to me. They fried, boiled and worst of all, they beat me! I feel disgusted with myself!)

Arbitrator: Sige po ibablotter na yan. Ikaw naman? Eco-bag ka lang ah. Wala ka namang problema ah. (This is noted and we shall file a blotter. How about you? You're just an eco-bag. It seems you have nothing to complain)

James as Eco-bag: {wearing an eco-bag on his head, crying heavily} Anong wala?! Ako po yung siningit nila sa puwet! Mga hayop kayo! Ambaboy niyo! {afterwards the photo of the hoarder who hid an eco-bag in between her buttocks was shown} (What "nothing?!" I am the one whom they put in between the buttocks! You filthy animals!

{afterwards the photo of the hoarder who hid an eco-bag in between her buttocks was shown})

Video # 5

James as Satan: {used a video filter of a devil as his costume} Hey, hey, hey! It's your boy, Sataan! *At babasagin ko na po ang katahimikan ko dahil mukhang nabuking na tayo ng NTF-ELCAC! At kahit nabuking na ako, huwag niyong kakalimutan ang pinakamahalaga kong turo. Ito ay ang tumulong ayon sa kakayahan, kumuha ayon sa pangangailangan! Tumulong tayo sa mga mahihirap, tumulong tayo sa nagugutom! Maghasik tayo ng tulong ito ang pinaka-gusto ko sa lahat!* {then ending it with a devil-like laugh} ({used a video filter of a devil as his costume} Hey, hey, hey! It's your boy, Sataan! And I will break my silence because it seems that our plan has been found out by the NTF-ELCAC! And even so, don't forget my most important teachings: it is to help within your capacity and to get something within your needs! Help the poor and the hungry! Let us spread help as what I really like the most! {then ending it with a devil-like laugh})

Video # 6

James as Nas Daily: {clad in plain black shirt just as Nas is usually wearing and speaking the same way as Nas; all that he will say has subtitles} Hi! I am Nas Daily! {with subtitles shown and the word Nas Daily in yellow color while the rest are white} Yes! You heard it right! I am Nas Daily! {subtitle same format as previous} And I want to tell you something! That I am very sad right now! {"very sad" in yellow text} Yes! This is my saddest face! {"saddest face" in yellow yet he is smiling} meaning I am so depressed! {"so depressed" in yellow} that my followers have been declining! {"declining" in yellow} because a whole country is against me! {"whole country" in yellow} And did you know what country is that? That...is the Philippines! {"Philippines"

in all capital letters and in yellow; mentioned with exclamation with "surprised facial expression"} Philippines, how can you forgive me? {"forgive me" in yellow}I know, I know! {second "I know" in all capital letters and in yellow; mentioned with emphasis} I will just say "adownbow" {"adownbow" in all capital letters and in yellow} and I think you can forgive me! {"forgive me" in yellow} And I will just put "Philippines" {"Philippines" in all capital letters and in yellow} in my title so you will forgive me! {"forgive me" in yellow} And there you have it, you forgave me in just...one minute! {"one minute" spelled as "1 minute" and in yellow}

APPENDIX B

SCREENSHOTS OF VIDEOS, REACTIONS, AND SOCIAL MEDIA COMMENTS

INDONESIA - ANNIE YANG

INDONESIA – REGGIE HASIBUAN

MALAYSIA – HARITH ISKANDER VIDEO 1

All 🤔 979 🇺🇸 524 🇺🇸 12 🤔 2 🇺🇸 1

MALAYSIA – ISKANDER VIDEO 1: COMMENTS

- So much edited and no originality but just to keep his fan base here entertained during MCO 🤔
- Like Reply 2y
- Author
Harith Iskander
So much editing and no originality 🤔 Sounds like you're reviewing a Jerry Bruckheimer movie
- Like Reply 2y
- Author
Harith Iskander
Probably - it's quite a loss
- Like Reply 2y
- Harith Iskander You are FAKE NEWS!!!
- Like Reply 2y
- Author
Harith Iskander
I KNOW!
- Like Reply 2y
- That was soooo good Harith Iskander!!!!
- Like Reply 2y
- Author
Harith Iskander
Thank you 😊
- Like Reply 2y
- Harith Iskander I think you are no longer permitted into the White House . Your press permit has rescinded ! 🤔
- Like Reply 2y
- Author
Harith Iskander
He did not know the difference between bacteria, virus, antibiotic and vaccine 🤔
- Like Reply 2y
- Author
Harith Iskander
To be honest - neither do I. But I don't do press conferences to the world
- Like Reply 2y
- God bless America. 🇺🇸
- Like Reply 2y
- Author
Harith Iskander
Alhamdulillah 🇺🇸
- Like Reply 2y

MALAYSIA – ISKANDER VIDEO 1: COMMENTS

- This is the first time trump behave to the press. Normally he will said 'i think you are terrible reporter!'
- Like Reply 2y
- Author
Harith Iskander
🤔🤔
- Like Reply 2y
- The virus is definitely smarter than Him! 🤔🤔
- Like Reply 2y
- Author
Harith Iskander
,,,,, many are
- Like Reply 2y
- Antibiotics don't work on viruses .. . Antiviral works
- Like Reply 2y
- Author
Harith Iskander
... now now ... let's not get TOO technical 🤔
- Like Reply 2y
- Frankly I find that all the people in the entertainment business have no choice but to make joke about or ridicule Donald Trump... Well it's not exactly to make people laugh but it's for their survival in the industry. An industry owned by the people who aren't exactly friends with the President. But we know Harith Iskander is different. We hope.
- Like Reply 2y Edited
- Author
Harith Iskander
No idea what you're talking about. I make jokes about my friends as well. Comedy is not about 'protecting your friends' - it's about pointing out the ridiculous.
- Like Reply 2y
- That's not what's scary, ladies and the gentlemen, it's the fact that hundreds and thousands of Americans voted for him and they think that Trump is intelligent
- Like Reply 2y
- Most Relevant is selected, so some replies may have been filtered out
- Author
Harith Iskander
Well ... it's called 'playing to the lowest common denominator'.

MALAYSIA – ISKANDER VIDEO 1: COMMENTS

- The real covidiot 🇺🇸
- Like Reply 2y
- Author
Harith Iskander
There are many he is an original though 🤔
- Like Reply 2y
- Always a good laugh from Potus. 🤔🤔🤔
- Like Reply 2y
- A good one 🤔
- Like Reply 2y
- all hail this guy 🇺🇸
- Like Reply 2y
- foul, harith... picking on mentally challenged like this...
- Like Reply 2y
- Author
Harith Iskander
I apologise 🤔
- Like Reply 2y
- You are brilliant , Harith 🤔
- Like Reply 2y
- He's teaching kindergarten kids of usa
- Like Reply 2y
- Brilliant as always Harith.... 🇺🇸
- OMG.... What an excellent idiot. 🇺🇸
- Like Reply 2y
- Author
Harith Iskander
Pretty fly for a white guy
- Like Reply 2y
- I didnt know the germs has gotten so brilliant, thank u for enlightening us 🤔🤔🤔
- Like Reply 2y Edited
- Author
Harith Iskander
- Like Reply 2y

MALAYSIA – HARITH ISKANDER VIDEO 2

MALAYSIA – ISKANDER VIDEO 2: COMMENTS

Red bra.....your wife one????? 🤔🤔🤔🤔🤔🤔🤔🤔

Like Reply 2y

No job ka harith 🤔🤔🤔...its agoood idea to make sure u r still in this field...

Lame 🤔🤔🤔

Like Reply 2y

Hilarious! 🤔🤔🤔👍

Like Reply 2y

Haha....this is really hilarious! Thank you Harith for making today much livelier! 🤔🤔 I'll vote for President Trump for the best comedian ever!! 🤔🤔🤔

Like Reply 2y

Harith, you are real humorous

Like Reply 2y

Do more interviews....Hahahaha..made our day

Like Reply 2y

You got paid by Democrat ? How's Malaysia ?

Like Reply 2y

Definitely a good idea. Malaysia would definitely remain safest then with the amount of headscarf available

MALAYSIA – ISKANDER VIDEO 2: COMMENTS

Died when you acknowledged him saying "gone for a long time" 🤔🤔

Like Reply 2y Edited

Seriously????? Aku nak tampar muka ni sampai ke bulan. Incompetent POS in history n people DIED bcos of these bunch of 🤔 licking moron supporters.

I wan to use his infamous "You are FIRED" to Trump.....

First u mess with Mexicans/Latinos,then Mess with India,wan "Protection Fees" from Japan,South Korea & Taiwan for their military defense equipment,Trade War with China,mess with India 2nd time for medicals,then mess with LeBron James charity,"Jeles" Obama down to earth and friendly with Citizens & anger Africa-American community.....then Blame everyones except himself..

Joe Biden will be next President

u will be amazed how many supporters still fanazed on him bruh

Like Reply 2y

Harith, I thought that you are the funniest man on earth but he is funnier.... 🤔🤔🤔🤔

Like Reply 2y

Sorry world, we're currently not a beacon of hope in this time of crisis, we're currently run by the Dumbest Incompetent Dump in the entire American History 🤔🤔

Like Reply 2y

Pm the red mask.. lol

India,wan "Protection Fees" from Japan,South Korea & Taiwan for their military defense equipment,Trade War with China,mess with India 2nd time for medicals,then mess with LeBron James charity,"Jeles" Obama down to earth and friendly with Citizens & anger Africa-American community.....then Blame everyones except himself..

Joe Biden will be next President

MALAYSIA – HARITH ISKANDER VIDEO 3

All 15K 13K 186 More

- 64
- 58
- 39
- 19

MALAYSIA – ISKANDER VIDEO 3: COMMENTS

if you dont know what to say or talk please don't, unless your brain is in your knees. say or talk which is logical, if you think smoking is good for health, 23

Like Reply 1y

Most Relevant is selected, so some replies may have been filtered out.

Author Harith Iskander WHO thinks smoking is Good for the Health? 23

This is hilarious 😂 You presented very well, sir. And yes, it's confusing too, why liquor but not cigarettes? Oh my GOVERNMENT 35

Like Reply 1y Edited

Author Harith Iskander I also dunno 13

Like Reply 1y

Condoms is not an essential product, but still can sell to avoid social problems 29

Like Reply 1y

Most Relevant is selected, so some replies may have been filtered out.

Author Harith Iskander how is condom non essential? 18

Like Reply 1y

honestly if government banned the cigarette I totally agree. Because the addicted ppl keep smoking by no wearing a mask properly, this is a fact you can see outside. 165

Like Reply 1y

Most Relevant is selected, so some replies may have been filtered out.

Author Harith Iskander Bro, I watched this video when eat my maggie mee. Then, my monitor semua maggie soup. 34

Like Reply 1y

Good point

Most Relevant is selected, so some replies may have been filtered out.

Author Harith Iskander I was applying to join Mensa International but was rejected - because IQ not high enough. But, I feel much better after hearing the speech of my deputy minister of domestic trade Rosol Wahid on the essential of alcohol and cigarettes during the FMCO. 30

Like Reply 1y

Author Harith Iskander He's a joy bringer

I don't drink alcohol, but as far as health is concerned, cigarette is more harmful than alcohol, not only bad for the smokers, is even worse for the innocent people around the smokers to breathe in second hand smoke. 74

Like Reply 1y

Most Relevant is selected, so some replies may have been filtered out.

Author Harith Iskander U r absolutely right! But the D minister thinks differently. 15

MALAYSIA – ISKANDER VIDEO 3: COMMENTS

Due to the warped practice of non-meritocracy whose products have ascended to the top echelon of the national leadership, embarrassing scenes such as this would soon be a norm. Very soon we would need interpreters for our not too distance future PM. Such policy is not tenable anymore in this highly competitively global environment. Put out the best to lead just as we select the best athletes to represent us in the Olympics. 133

Like Reply 1y

Author Harith Iskander thanks for the doses of laughters 😂😂😂 to keep us sane in this trying times n for you, lovely wife, Jezzamine n team for the HOPE branch initiative for those affected by the pandemic. Stay safe at all times!! 🙏 10

#GBU

Like Reply 1y

You are definitely more than a comedian! Thanks for the sketch, reflecting the standard of our lawmakers 24

Like Reply 1y

Alcohol is banned because later mabuk. When mabuk, will forget the SOP. The SOP is non-confusing enough as it is. 10

Like Reply 1y Edited

You nailed it. It not matter of alcohol vs cigarettes. It is matter of how our politicians thinking mentally which assume what ever they tell, rakyat will accept it. 78

Like Reply 1y

Rokok when blow the smoke it's help distancing .. 1meter of smoke .. so every where also can smoke now ... if ask why say for distancing purpose ..SOP ... 78

both should be listed under essential items, smoke can suffocate the covid virus in lung & alcohol can sterilize the lung from becoming the breeding ground for the virus 133

Like Reply 1y

The best thing about this sketch is, you didn't even have to make it up 20

Like Reply 1y

Author Harith Iskander Right!! 9

A clear explanation in a joke format. Only you can do this kind. 20

Like Reply 1y

Author Harith Iskander thank you for your kind WORDS 9

MALAYSIA – HARITH ISKANDER VIDEO 4

MALAYSIA – ISKANDER VIDEO 4: COMMENTS

- Great one luv it.. He he he.. Spanish FLY..spks volume abt our Health minister n ooops he got d date wrong..n he got d date wrong.. Ooouch🤔🤔🤔..
- Harith Iskander **Well ... anyone can make a mistake , unfortunately his mistakes are recorded**
- Wow..whatta a setup you really look like a tok penghulu lah ..hope the fly didnt get into you yah ..tks for the laugh..jia you
- My take on this subject, religion is a private matter Please do not bring it into public scrutiny and policy settings. 😊
- Harith Iskander **Glad to be of service!**
- One of the best you have done. Well done ! 🤔🤔🤔
- Comedians' jobs at stake... politicians seem to be getting funnier and funnier without even trying these days.
- Harith Iskander **Thank YOU 😊**
- Harith Iskander **It's strong competition!**

MALAYSIA – ISKANDER VIDEO 4: COMMENTS

- You really SuperFly lahhh Harith Iskander I really like your tone. Thank you and all your super buddies Douglas Lim Dr Jason Leong Comedy We are really feeling that wonder.... But next time tell the fly not to join any of us for soup.... always sibuk only.
- Lately too many politikus berlawak...good laugh for us during this hard time!! 🤔
- Was wondering what u getting at until in the end u said Spanish fly 🤔🤔🤔
- Harith Iskander **We need to be able to laugh at**
- Only Malaysia have such uneducated doc and minister...
- MB PAS should be more understanding about the rakyat due to COVID-19 not make their under one standing .. 🤔
- Harith Iskander **Thanks for watching till the end!**
- Bravo bro... Spanish Fly is crossing border from Thailand to Malaysia 🤔🤔🤔
- our malaysia is running by donkey government, and sheep rakyat who dunno how to wear facemask properly.
- Harith Iskander **other countries also got ... we are not essential**
- I was sad with the numbers hitting 11K when you made me laugh again with the Spanish joke 🤔🤔🤔
- Harith Iskander **a good one, sir!**

MALAYSIA – HARITH ISKANDER VIDEO 5

MALAYSIA – ISKANDER VIDEO 5: COMMENTS

Why is your songkok so weird sayang ku..
Like Reply 51w 34

songkok and his cuteness matches his statements said...
Like Reply 51w 2

I don't see how it would slow things down. Not like you have to set up a tripod and flood lights.

Hehe... i myself am not the recording type but i certainly make sure they know i am alertly observing their sops with a smile. I keep it friendly and stay observant.

Just dont chat long ... that ... would certainly slow things down. Usually ultra seniors may need just a bit more time. Young ones need to keep it snappy.

Like Reply 51w Edited 3

We don't need to go to the extent of recording everything, get that culprit out, punish him or her severely. He or she is the black sheep. I trust most of our frontliners are working tirelessly with dignity and integrity. Thank you frontliners.

Like Reply 51w 8

In my opinion, the photo and video taking can delay the vaccination process. So by not taking a photo or video during vaccination, we are doing a favour to all those waiting. So in short, if the centre is not crowded, then take it, but if you see that it is busy and crowded, it's a favour if you skip it.

And healthcare worker must be responsible in ensuring the patient receive the right vaccine and the correct doses, and not empty syringes or water. It's all about being responsible and considerate. All parties including healthcare workers and public must have it

Like Reply 51w 3

As my experience working in pusat vaksin, we have about 3200+ vaccinees per day.. for 12h operation... means per hour around 260 jabs.. if 10 rooms operating per time, 26 people to be injected per hour each room...

how if everyone takes 5 min each to fulfill all kehendak.. we will stuck..

please just be considerate.. you can just ask the injector to see the syringe, if anything you're not satisfied. you can complain on the spot...

MALAYSIA – ISKANDER VIDEO 5: COMMENTS

They are all in a state of confusion, that's why the Rakyat are as confused as them
Like Reply 51w 4

Leong Ky
Great explanation. Now we're no longer kompose.
Like Reply 51w 4

They are not in confused state...they are already in COMA
Like Reply 51w 4

Solus Shu Huh
Soon, our country will get famous for one thing - gostan. We gostan everything, nothing is reliable
Like Reply 51w 4

I tell u boss this Baba fly is not fit to be kkm minister.he is not educated for medical line.he should get out
Like Reply 50w 4

Is our government bipolar?
Like Reply 51w 4

Imagine the ongoing clown show
Like Reply 51w 4

cause the ministers themselves are not sure of their responsibility
Like Reply 51w Edited 4

Haha. No Komposion, I like the explanation given. Unfortunately, I finish taking both my doses so cannot choose whc session to go Harith.
Like Reply 51w 4

Pokie Boo
boss, u going out of job soon lah !!!
The Msia ministers, deputy Ministers, etc etc is more clown and cartoon than you lah !!!
Like Reply 51w 4

Well done, Harith. Its 'lets say something/anything to justify our fat salaries'.
Like Reply 51w 4

Top fan
Ravi Thiaga
Harith, 2 different menteri.. 1 menteri says cannot and another says can
Like Reply 51w 4

MALAYSIA – HARITH ISKANDER VIDEO 6

MALAYSIA – ISKANDER VIDEO 6: COMMENTS

- Malaysia should bring a woman as a prime minister. Young and energetic minded person. I vote for women. Definitely will changes will come.
Like Reply 47w 29
- I want to make sure that Malaysia is no 1? # 1 as most corrupt? # 1 as most racist? # 1 as most number of COVID-19 cases per capita? I hope not. There is too much that needs to be fixed in this beautiful country ...to much damage caused to our economy, education and cultural fabric that cannot be erased in a short period of time. A country with entrenched racist policies, even under the 'right'
- Lame
Like Reply 47w 138
- This is going to further be additional justification for middle class parents advising their children to study smart and migrate elsewhere. Hmmm sad reality....
Like Reply 47w 6

MALAYSIA – ISKANDER VIDEO 6: COMMENTS

- COVID-19 cases per capita? I hope not. There is too much that needs to be fixed in this beautiful country ...to much damage caused to our economy, education and cultural fabric that cannot be erased in a short period of time. A country with entrenched racist policies, even under the 'right' government, will take time to heal.
Like Reply 47w 21
- MALAYSIA's is now Corrupted country. all ministers greedy power, no dignity, Corruption ministers not punish.... what is happening?
Like Reply 47w 7
- No matter what or who going to be PM there will be always people who not satisfy and say this and that.. I don't even know who to choose bcoz no one on list can be trust.power and money can make people change and blind.not all people ya but a lot.
Like Reply 47w 14
- It's a joke... A mess.. How embarrassing!!!
Like Reply 47w 9

MALAYSIA – ISKANDER VIDEO 6: COMMENTS

- That what you want right? 😊 so we have to wait for your party to choose the the new PM. Although they also don't have the majority
Like Reply 47w 10
- Spot on.. the psychological effect of this skit. Funny and depressing at the same time.. money politikus at the very best! Thank you for this
Like Reply 47w Edited 5
- As Loyal Malaysian we just follow what our King has agreed.
Like Reply 47w 4
- Malaysia is always No. 1... But from behind... Anyway, **congrats** to all Malaysian Politicians who care only themselves as it still is No. 1 🙄🙄🙄🙄
Like Reply 47w
- So what your suggestions Mr Harith, just do condemnation and trolling..
Like Reply 47w Edited 1
- Good one Sir... Try doing one together with Douglas and Hindra.. Let's ignore those got triggered..
Like Reply 47w
- Pray the wisdom king to do what is needed. Return to the Rakyat what was stolen in Feb 2020.
Like Reply 47w

MALAYSIA – ISKANDER VIDEO 6: COMMENTS

- so many foreigners are getting vaccine shot but many Malaysians are on the waiting list...so nothing wrong here as usual in boleh land..
Like Reply 51w 1
- pfhffff...they say quarantine can make u soft eaah...give u 3 out of 10...armmm...nahhhh make it 2...anyway thanks for wasting my time here...pfhffff
Like Reply 47w 2
- Hahahaha I love your suggestions la Harith Iskander 🤔. but unfortunately I had completed my 2 doses already, first in the morning and 2nd one in the afternoon.. without any photo or video to prove that I had actually received the real vaccine. 😊
Like Reply 51w
- Desmond and Harith have been brightening our days during the pandemic. Thanks to both of you.
Like Reply 47w
- U don provoke provoke eh🤔🤔🤔 u where u from?? Msia kini,Mgazet..? ...🤔🤔🤔🤔
Like Reply 47w
- tq sir. we need some laugh after daily dose of politics antique.
Like Reply 47w

MALAYSIA – ISKANDER VIDEO 6: COMMENTS

- Better make him "caretaker" Pandemic Morgue...
Like Reply 47w
- He can have curry mee with his adviser.
Like Reply 47w
- It's sad to know you probably bought the songkok and batik shirt just to make fun of malays. If one have go to low to be funny better not be a comedian
Like Reply 47w 2
- He still got work from PM to AM Caretaker.
Like Reply 47w
- why do I sensing some Douglas Lim's tone of jokes... go be authentic lah why copy copy?
Like Reply 47w

JOB VACANCY

PRIME MINISTER OF MALAYSIA
Location: Malaysia

- Ability to maintain racial harmony.
- Drive country's economy.
- Provide direction for the country and government.
- Willing to work overtime and on Public Holidays as and when required.
- Preferably able to start work immediately.

IMMEDIATE HIRING!!

MALAYSIA – NIGEL NG VIDEO 2

All 🤔 18K 👍 10K ❤️ 384 More ▾

ASIAN PARENTS AND FOOD ALLERGIES

- 🤔 54
- 😱 27
- 😬 15
- 😬 9

MALAYSIA – NG VIDEO 2: COMMENTS

Wow totally different act 2 years ago. Not only doesn't sound the same, he looks more FOB than Uncle Roger
Like Reply 7w

Omg so true! There's allergy and there's ALLERGY. If my parents hadn't actually seen me hospitalised I think to this day they would still have doubts!
Like Reply 1y Edited

My country doesn't believe in food allergies either, sadly a young woman died in a restaurant because she requested the desert which had dairy in it and the restaurant said it didn't serve anything with dairy and the waiter who took her order didn't believe her
Like Reply 1y

Uncle Roger he is smxy when he is talking normally haha ~ haiya ~
Like Reply 1y

Uncle Roger from my view here is kind of a good looking -- minus the swearing a lot. Well, that's just part of the show & he's just keep roasting food culture left & right. I'm entertained
Like Reply 1y

This is sooo true. Asian parents don't believe in those things.
Like Reply 1y

I have an allergic to few food items but my mom never believe me.
Like Reply 1y

Asians and Africans are so alike, from culture to food to tradition, everything is almost the same
Like Reply 1y

Oh Yes! Just take a bowl of wild ginseng soup, chicken feet and oolong tea, and you are cured of all illnesses
Like Reply 1y

Hahahaha... i agree with this. My husband worked as a chef in an international school and i was surprised with his list of dont's because of food allergies - dairy, gluten, peanut, fruits, etc. i mean like...in ASIA.. we eat anything cuz if not, mom would hit us with a broomstick.
Like Reply 1y

MALAYSIA – NG VIDEO 2: COMMENTS

Why do Asian comedians need to speak with an accent? Surely he doesn't speak this way in his daily life. Apparently, no jokes are funny if you do not pepper it with vulgarities.
Which is why I truly respect Gabriel Iglesias.
Like Reply 1y

But my parents believe food allergy. Im allergic to Shrimp and other seafood
Like Reply 45w

allergic to shellfish and preserve food. everything has some form of preservations, fish sauce, belacan, dried shrimp, budu.
all asian noodles have it. stir fry veggies too.

if my allergy is acting up, d only thing i can order, vegan fried noodle at mamak.
Like Reply 42w

I don't know anyone who is allergic to peanut and peanut butter. I am a Filipino. I know people who are allergic to alcohol, to shrimp and crabs, chicken, or beef. But peanuts? Maybe he is right that it is not common among Asians.
Like Reply 1y

He seems different now and with a thicker accent which I'm sure is part of his act
Like Reply 1y

when i have fresh water lobster allergy, my parents ask me to eat more of it.. to build resistance they said.. i still have that allergy
Like Reply 42w

This is so true in Asian families
Like Reply 19w

I don't even know a gluten allergy exist, until i watched it on US series.
Like Reply 1y

Uncle ROGER without his iconic orange polo shirt looks incomplete
Like Reply 1y

Dont make joke of asian culture tho , even tho we're asian ..it will gave other false impression.n make them feel thats its ok to make it as a joke too
Like Reply 1y

What he said ... yup! He left out the part about introducing what you're allergic to into your daily life so your body can build up tolerance for it.
Like Reply 1y

MALAYSIA – NG VIDEO 2: COMMENTS

You have some good material, if you drop the use of "fuck" it may be worth listening
Like Reply 1y

Not to mention they be like 'you're allergic to seafood? Here! Eat more seafood! It'll make u stronger against it over time!'
Like Reply 1y

He's really right when uncle roger says nigel and uncle Roger are two different people now i really see, the accent of uncle Roger is different with nigel
Like Reply 1w

Okay..this is the handsome version of Uncle Roger!!!!
Like Reply 1y

Hiya I can't remember it was Uncle Roger
Like Reply 19w

When u tell Asian parents that u have allergy to that specific food they say then eat more and be strong
my mother said that to my sister
Like Reply 1y

Yess is truly true...asian parents not believe such thing with peanut allergies
Like Reply 1y

"There are STRONG people...and there are WEAK people" - Imaooo literally Asian parents
Like Reply 1y

I have eczema on my hands since i was recently pregnant. I've been eating rice with fork and spoon instead of hand (which i enjoy btw) and my mom kept asking "until when you have to eat with fork and spoon?"
Like Reply 51w

Some people have too much money and not enough sense Uncle Roger.
Like Reply 45w

Uncle Roger, I love your Asian accent as much as i love your real voice.
Like Reply 19w

MALAYSIA – NG VIDEO 2: COMMENTS

True, we Malaysian don't buy the food allergic idea. Doesn't happen here
Like Reply 1y

I read this in uncle Rogers voice
Like Reply 1y

Yeah, and then they will say "only one piece, won't kill you." Lol
Like Reply 3w

Haiyya I have a allergy of msg
Like Reply 27w Edited

Haiyaa. Jamie Oliver's chilly Jam better than stand up
Like Reply 8w

same with Nigerian parents they don't believe in that...
Like Reply 8w

Asians wash off the starch and eat the gluten... that's how badass...
Like Reply 42w Edited

Oh man you are so handsome. I am from shoutheast Asia. I dont want to call uncle. Gogo.
Like Reply 43w

Young Uncle Roger, perhaps before his wife Helen left him
Like Reply 1y

Ah did you inspire Ronnie chieng's Chinese wedding dinner gig..haha
Like Reply 1y

Parents : allergies? You're no child of mine !
Like Reply 1y

Now i know that East-Asian are the same as West-Asian parents
My father thinks the same way about antibiotics.
Like Reply 47w

Bro. I would love to see more stand up. You kill it on stage. Not that I don't love Uncle Roger
Like Reply 1y

No haiyaa? not real uncle roger, where ur cute Asian accent gone
Like Reply 1y

This is not funny at all, why ppl laugh so hard? This is not asia way dude
Like Reply 1y

MALAYSIA – NG VIDEO 2: COMMENTS

I rarely saw indonesian people with food allergies. Especially peanut allergy. That's a thing that I only found out after watching American tv show. The worst most indonesian would say of their eat too much peanut is that they'll grow a pimple
Like Reply 1y

Ronnie chen copy uncle roger.... Or the other way around
Like Reply 1y

Hey guys! That's just your parents! Not all the Asian parents! And you need to learn to respect your parents who raised you!
Like Reply 1y

Yeah but aren't most Chinese lactose intolerant
Like Reply 1y

Netflix where's this man development deal already the world needs more Uncle Roger
Like Reply 1y

How huge is Asia? Not huge enough to not relate to Nigel's jokes about it
Like Reply 51w

Hilarious but no need for the swearing!
Like Reply 1y

Ouch it's so true it hurts
Like Reply 1y

Ripped off joke from Ronny Chieng.
Like Reply 1y

Dont believe in them Until you die.
Like Reply 1y

And thats the truth...
Like Reply 1y

Because food allergies are mostly happens to people who carry Caucasian DNAS
Like Reply 50w

It's true for Asian. My parents believe that only spoiled children have food allergies. If you can't eat it now, then try to stuff in your mouth until you like it. Also, antibiotics, my parents don't allow me to have them when I was sick because if I use them too much, my body will get used to the antibiotics and it will not work properly any more
Like Reply 1y Edited

Relate
Like Reply 1y

MALAYSIA – NG VIDEO 3: COMMENTS

Tried Uncle Ben's rice only twice, because I forgot I'd ever tried it before lol.
Result ... 🤢.
Disgusting food. They should sack their tasting department.

Like Reply 1y

That stuff is horrible

Like Reply 1y

"so horrible, Taste like sad" - uncle roger.

Like Reply 1y

Hilarious! I went to a Swiss Hotel School and they served uncle ben's rice. Really disgusting, truly horrible. Yuck.

Like Reply 1y

Wonder why his wife left? 🤔

When you realize he speaks fluent english better than you

Like Reply 1y

I'm white and that's definitely not my favorite rice lmao

Like Reply 1y

I could have told you before you ate the Uncle Ben's that it's disgusting.... Had it once when I was 12... never again. I'm used to getting boiled rice from a Chinese restaurant right down the road from my paps house no way was that crap gonna beat it.

Like Reply 1y

↳ 1 Reply

An mexicans Love you 🤔🤔🤔

Like Reply 1y

I make mine.
Wash rice till water is clear
Cook rice 10 minutes
Mix rice
Cover with lid / don't lift the lid
Turn off the pot
20 minutes it is done
I was taught by my Chinese boss!
My white friends are jealous 🤔🤔🤔

Like Reply 1y

Oh my goodness, how can you wash the rice inside the bowl provided by the rice cooker? Don't you know the coating will be scrapped away? Oh my goodness! Every housewife knows to wash the rice in another plastic bowl before transferring into the rice cooker bowl.

Like Reply 1y

They need to replace Gordon Ramsey with this guy

Like Reply 1y

MALAYSIA – NG VIDEO 3: COMMENTS

The way he pronounced in prolonged way of the first three letters and second to the last letters of every word makes me laugh 🤔

Like Reply 1y

↳ 2 Replies

Actually the way he talks is the funny part 🤔🤔

Like Reply 1y

Oh my GOD, not spicy not Mexican, totally agreed 🤔

Like Reply 1y

↳ 1 Reply

Tastes like sad. Lol! ❤️❤️❤️

Love at first rice. 🤔🤔🤔

Like Reply 1y

Damn dude. Can we get a break from the "white people" bullshit. It's played out and rooted in fear of the Other

Like Reply 1y

Okay that pre made rice looked disgusting xD i can't disagree u can just cook the rice why buy premade

Like Reply 1y

I love your video! I think you should keep viewing videos like the rice egg fried rice! So people like me, knows how to do it properly! Keep up with the good work and the amazing positive vibe! You've made my last two days so much better! I've watched sooo many times! So natural, you can't fake and I personally love that!

Like Reply 1y

Yh and you Asian people like bats with your rice at least with uncle Ben you can't catch anything.

Like Reply 1y

Why did your wife left, uncle roger? Did she fall out of love?

Like Reply 1y

Taste like sad 🤔🤔

Like Reply 35w

Looks like shit but still better than his attempt at trying to make rice himself.

Like Reply 1y

Oh no you gave Uncle Bens rice a bad review. He looks very angry and might track you down. Make big wall using bags of rice for protection. hahaha

MALAYSIA – NG VIDEO 3: COMMENTS

It reminds me when I see people eat durian and do over reactions lol

Like Reply 1y

In pakistan most people get 20 kg sack of rice

Like Reply 39w

Cook over stove top much better microwave food is nasty by it self 🤢🤢

Like Reply 1y

Eating one plate rice with some onions is way better than this(asian boiled rice)

Like Reply 1y

Us whiteys don't eat that shit. We boil are rice from scratch and make it right. Oh wait my dad eats uncles Bens rice. He don't know any better though. So we let it slide.

What is this uncle roooooooger. Another torture to us Asian? They need to stop making this kind of rice.

It's a joke. Leave dislike button if you found this comment unfunny

Like Reply 1y

Do you think Uncle Ben is married to aunt Jamima?

Like Reply 1y

No body notice he spit it out and ate it again?

Boy that kind of freedom to criticize must be nice, do that here in india you could get all kind of law suit from the companies. Criticize someone in power you could be branded anti-nationalist and imprisoned for life. I simply envy your freedom

Like Reply 1y

Nigel. Pls.. don use that accent. Its really embarrassing & discriminating to Asian. U can say Haiyaa, lar, ler, for all u wan, but plss.. not that accent

<https://www.theguardian.com/.../uncle-bens-to-get-revamp...>

They renamed the brand to Ben's Original now due to the current wave of BLM.

THEGUARDIAN.COM

Uncle Ben's rice to get revamp after criticism over racial...

Is reviewing white people the easiest to get away with without repercussion and that's why you bash white people?

Like Reply 1y

Need some Chili jam 🍌🍌

Like Reply 1y

Where is "Hiyaahh" ...

Like Reply 1y

MALAYSIA – NG VIDEO 3: COMMENTS

The biggest rice sack we had in Philippines was 50 kilo

Like Reply 1y

Uncle Ben rice taste like plastic yuk

Like Reply 1y

Come on, we can find microwaveable rice everywhere in asia XD

Like Reply 1y

Typical malaysian love slap slap rice packaging lol 🤡

Like Reply 1y Edited

↳ 1 Reply

10kg noob

Most Indians stock for whole year 200kgs plus 🤡🤡

Like Reply 1y

even first or an let's start out with a few things here we have Uncle Ben's rice that a lot of people believe is a black owned company when it indeed is White owned that has a black man slapped on the front of the package so anything made and seasoned is seasoned to their taste.

Like Reply 1y

↳ 1 Reply

He's annoying and condescending...who cares how people eat rice as long as they love it !!

I def always slap big sacks/bags of rice 🤡🤡

Like Reply 1y

Stop it Its Not As Bad As You Put On ...
Be Honest Nigel

Like Reply 46w

It's ok all you do is add a little all purpose seasoning on it.

Like Reply 1y

Hi you are Malaysian right? But which part of Malaysia talk like this? I thought you are Vietnamese!

Like Reply 1y

Nothing like Vietnamese. He sounds more canto HK, but is able to roll his "R"s

Like Reply 1y

Yes Hong Kong as I listen more. ...

Like Reply 1y

Stick to math bro not comedy.

Like Reply 1y

MALAYSIA – NIGEL NG VIDEO 4

MALAYSIA – NG VIDEO 4: COMMENTS

- my grandma would cook rice in a sauce pan, but she grew up during the great depression and without even a hs education, so probably never had the luxury of a rice cooker. Her rice always came out perfect for sushi rice, but it definitely was not over flowing the water then draining it later lol
- Thank goodnesssssss. If you use rice cooker you don't really need to use your finger even. They have the measurements on the side of the pot. Maybe the only time you need to use finger is if you're like my dad and he can't see the numbers without his glasses.
- I have to stuck a fork on my rice cooker to force it to cook as it has been serving rice since the jurrasic era
- Lol. here at philippines we make rice by measuring the rice by hand and measure the water at the same level. then we make fire with charcoal and we even put plastic or salt at the top of it. hahahaha. BASIC!
- : waiting for Pinoy version of cooking rice where you put salt on top of the lid
- poor Asians use casserole to cook rice
- Haha this is so satisfying but proper Asian no need to use finger to measure the water... Stone age is over, use a cup!
- But, but Uncle Roger the markers in the pot will tell you how much water the rice needs for it to be cooked. No need to measure it with your finger when you cook it in an electric rice cooker.
- Well you can use saucepan..but still not like that in BBC.. My mom can cook rice with saucepan and still create fluffy rice..hahahaha
- Uncle roger, you forgot you got to wipe the bottom of the pot before putting into the rice cooker

MALAYSIA – NG VIDEO 4: COMMENTS

- Sorry Uncle Roger, I'm a year 61 year old Chinese Uncle who has gone through a few rice cookers in my time. Always wash your rice in a plastic container several times before transferring to the rice cooker pot. I found out after my first non stick Teflon rice cooker pot got all the Teflon scratched from me washing rice in it.
- I need to know what rice cooker specifically that is. Uncle Roger needs to get a kickback from them.
- I got my rice cooker. I don't even use the lines. At this point it's judgment and it still comes out pretty good!
- The best is to cook over the stove and once the rice is cooked, pour out the water. Its healthier cos we are pouring the starchy water out.
- Here in Philippines we cook rice using pot. Rice cooker are just for those who can't judge rice if it's properly cooked or not HAHAHAAAA
- Uncle Roger can you please slow down and do another video for the white people that doesn't invest in rice cooker cuz they don't cook rice everyday? Door-chair ahh!
- Interestingly is our finger long not equal, but the rice still good after using this technique.

MALAYSIA – NG VIDEO 4: COMMENTS

- wah uncle roger your rice cooker so nice i only got Cuckoo no music but make my rice so nice also. can lah.
- But, World War 3 is coming.
- I use "finggah" to measure wutah --- uncle roger
- I am Thai and all my flatmates are Scottish. When they saw me using rice-cooker, they were impressed and said " Wowww!! I have never seen that item before" ..lol
- Uncle Roger, you forgot to pour the washed water away and fill new water. What a disgrace to the rice cooking! Hai la...
- World War 2 is over HAHAHAAAAH
- WORLD WAR 2 IS OVER HAHAHAAAAH
- Fra Olalem Cinco "Use technology!" ... "Use finger to measure..."

MALAYSIA – NG VIDEO 4: COMMENTS

- Actually not all asians are using rice cooker to cook rice. Other asian or almost are cooking rice manually
- Hi Nigel Ng, is the expression "haiyaa" Asian? We also have that expression in Greenlandic "hajjaaa". And it seems like the expression means the same/ is used with the same purpose
- Yeoh Chin Keong Another way of cooking rice is using steam method. That way you can prevent wastage of rice that stick surrounding the pan
- When something is irritatingly wrong
- Nigel Ng uncle Roger, are you trying to tell us that your grandparents also used to cook in a rice cooker? I'd say you'd have to explain how to properly cook rice if you can
- Uncle roger...we pour away the water twice after rinsing the rice...u r so dirty!
- There are many types of rice, there is not just one way to make rice.
- uncle Roger, once u open the Rice Cooker to looked the rice, BETTER DO NOT TALK TALK, because your SALIVA will jump into your Rice. haiyaaaaaaa.. hhhahaha
- Most Asian can't cook rice without a rice cooker yet they are laughing at someone who cook without one.
- Uncle Roger needs a guest spot on the next season of Nora From Queens!
- As the video had already mentioned. "World War 2 is over, use Technology."
- Uncle Roger you forgot to show one more thing for Western people, Wash the rice and remove the water 3x. then finger it

MALAYSIA – NG VIDEO 4: COMMENTS

- and for the fun facts behind this rice is first water u can use it for your plants Second, u can wash ur face for the first water yeah that's what my Grandma told me
- I'm reading all these comments in Uncle Roger's accent
- No salt though? At least season it a bit so it's not bland.
- You're not Asian if your not using a rice cooker, but in remote places we still use fire wood and you have to adjust the heat once it boils, if not your gonna burn it, then your mother is gonna slap you for not watching the rice...
- But can you really cook rice manually like the real asian way?
- Guys, we only need to wash the rice ONE TIME. The cloudy water contains so much vitamin B1 and other nutrients. Washing rice only for removing dust -- don wash too many times. There is nothing left. No nutrients, no tasty!!!
- A Filipino Jokoy has been showing the world on how to make perfect rice before you did <https://www.facebook.com/jokoy/videos/329640497958466/>

MALAYSIA – NIGEL NG VIDEO 5

All 🍔 173K 👍 76K ❤️ 3.9K More ▾

🤔 1K
😂 672
😭 569
😬 546

MALAYSIA – NG VIDEO 5: COMMENTS

Name Asian Cuisine's Worst Nightmare Below...
Like Reply 49w 🍔 806
↳ 131 Replies

Author Nigel Ng
I am still in shock haiyaaa 🤔 2.2K
Like Reply 49w
↳ 73 Replies

Author Nigel Ng
MSG = ONLY TRUE LOVE 🤔 1.3K

Author Nigel Ng
It's Jamie Olive Oil From Now On OKE?! 🍔 4.3K
Like Reply 49w
↳ 345 Replies

Author Nigel Ng
Mr Chilli Jam 🤔 2.1K
Like Reply 49w

Nigel Ng
Haiyaaa still got nightmares from this one 🍔 2K
Like Reply 42w
↳ 55 Replies

Follow Haiyaaa 🍔 1K
Like Reply 49w

MALAYSIA – NG VIDEO 5: COMMENTS

This is my first time to see someone make a green curry with mushrooms.
Like Reply 49w 🍔 869
↳ 31 Replies

More accurately chicken stir-fry mushroom in 'special' coriander paste
Like Reply 49w 🍔 603

If you serve this at your restaurant people will not just call for compensation, but will sue you. If that people go to your restaurant for eating green curry because they miss their land. Eating your green curry will make them more sad.
Like Reply 49w 🍔 918
↳ 23 Replies

Thanks uncle Roger to save Thai Cuisine 🙏
Like Reply 49w Edited 🍔 1.8K

I think those instant green curry paste is 100 times more authentic than jamie olive f*ckup thai mushroom 3 little chili skin green curry
Like Reply 49w 🍔 322
↳ 5 Replies

He's lying. I hat thing had no flavor cause i saw no seasoning whatsoever. Lol.
Like Reply 49w 🍔 630

The fake "YAVAA" thrown in from one of Jamie's previous videos killed me
Like Reply 49w 🍔 131
↳ 1 Reply

Serious to say, that's the most horrible green curry i ever saw in my whole 42 years life. He literally had molested Thais special dish. Not enough haiyaa can represent my devastating feeling. Sorry.
Like Reply 49w 🍔 312

MALAYSIA – NG VIDEO 5: COMMENTS

Jamie olive oil my Thai wife just faint
Like Reply 49w 🍔 255
↳ 4 Replies

I am Thai people and I hate his green curry very much, I can tell its taste like shit
Like Reply 49w 🍔 373
↳ 26 Replies

Jamie is just overrated, that curry looked gross 🤔 174
Like Reply 49w

I am far from a pro chef but I can make better green curry than him.
Like Reply 49w 🍔 112
↳ 3 Replies

When he said Basmati Rice, even I put my foot down from the chair! 🤔
Like Reply 49w 🍔 484
↳ 13 Replies

Uncle Roger stop stop stop my tummy hurts hahahaha

It's okay, Jamie olive Green curry meant to be "Vegetables" green curry. All green... nothing to do with Thai green curry. 🤔

Uncle Roger stop stop stop my tummy hurts hahahaha this Jamie Oliver is really trying to kill you. The level of stress I saw in that video hahahaha. Jamie Oliver bad bad boy.
Like Reply 49w 🍔 151

Saddest video video ever. 🤔 I'm so sorry you had to go through that Nigel Ng. As a psychologist, I recommend you refrain from ever looking at a Jamie Olive Oil video in the future. Too depressing. Not good for your mental health. And we need distraction from your widows. 🤔
Like Reply 49w Edited 🍔 1.4K

Jamie Oliver needs to give up with SE Asian food already! But I guess it makes good Uncle Roger content...
Like Reply 49w 🍔 2.3K
↳ 43 Replies

Now we learn how Italian think when they put pineapple on pizza.
Like Reply 49w 🍔 431

Jamie Oliver! Please stop cooking Asian dishes. You'll make us all die slowly.
Like Reply 49w 🍔 1.1K
↳ 31 Replies

You know it's a cooking tragedy when Nigel loses character and weeps bc it's so sad
Like Reply 49w 🍔 243

MALAYSIA – NG VIDEO 5: COMMENTS

- I think this is the most you've ever said Haiyaa for any of your cooking reviews!! 🤔
Like Reply 49w 211
↳ 1 Reply
- Thai ancestors are crying. Also I feel like my heart is stomped when I see half of the dish is mushroom and veggie. We order thai green curry to eat curry+pork. not fkin veggie. It tastes like sad. orzll 🤔
Like Reply 49w Edited 316
- Thai Green curry is my fave dish..that is definitely not Thai Green Curry..wow..he really fckd this one up! 🤔
Like Reply 49w Edited 306
↳ 9 Replies
- I'm from Thailand.. this chef's make me so up sad whit thai green curry 🤔
Like Reply 49w Edited 77
- That curry looks so unappetising. No wonder he had to close his restaurants.
Like Reply 49w 146
↳ 2 Replies
- All those cooking shows, they say don't call it X if you make it your own and it isn't exact. Jamie shouldn't call it Thai if it's his bullshit take on a curry
Like Reply 49w 283
- Make Thai people angry watching jamei Oliver Cook Thai green curry
Like Reply 49w 28
↳ 2 Replies
- 2 cups of rice is enough for 4 people 🤔
Like Reply 49w 104
↳ 17 Replies
- It is Thai food that does not have in Thailand. lol
Like Reply 49w 188
- Its like a vegetable salad not thai green curry hahahah
Like Reply 49w 52
↳ 1 Reply
- He meant THAI GREEN CURRY SALAD. 🤔
Like Reply 49w 14
- That's the worst thai green curry I have ever seen. I have been in Thailand more than 30 times and never seen or tasted something like that. Jamie Oliver just wasted all the ingredients and foremost... TIME 🤔
Like Reply 49w Edited 190
↳ 2 Replies
- uncle roger...i hope you and oliver get a face to face challenge so you can roast him in person. 🤔
Like Reply 49w 678

MALAYSIA – NG VIDEO 5: COMMENTS

- I can just hear "HAIYAAA, why not just use rice cooker" Jamie olive oil can't cook 🤔
Like Reply 49w 164
↳ 4 Replies
- Haiyaa ! I'm Thai and I'm sure I can't eat this !!
Like Reply 49w Edited 271
↳ 13 Replies
- Another olive oil nightmare. 🤔
Like Reply 49w 120
- I actually feel bad with Mr Chiii Jamie Olive Oil lmao
Like Reply 49w 173
↳ 1 Reply
- I would not be able to stand there and watch him cook lol. My head hurts by just watching; it might be his version of Thai green curry but def not How my mom, my thai friends, myself cook green curry.
Like Reply 49w 291
- The only British chef can make perfect Asian dishes is Gordon Ramsay.
Like Reply 49w 15
- Hahaha No wonder why his restaurant in Bangkok closed down in such short time. With this cooking skills, sorry to say but none of Thais gonna eat that..even it is for free!!
Like Reply 49w 212
- This is not the Thai green curry I used to eat... I will called the chef out of he serve me that
Like Reply 49w 78
↳ 1 Reply
- jamie oliver is the reason why my swedish class mate ate green curry in Thailand as a soup like creamy mushroom soup on its own. Though i warned her u need rice and it's not a stand alone soup she didn't listen. She ate it , cried , got upset and left.
Like Reply 49w 16
- How is Jamie Olive Oil a chef again?
Did he just watch ratatouille then think he's a chef?
Like Reply 49w 61

MALAYSIA – NG VIDEO 5: COMMENTS

So many niece and nephew comments in the original video 😂 I hope Jamie "do and don't" take it personally. "Do" is that - hoping he can do a better job in his next Asian's dish 😂 try not to let Uncle Roger's leg down again

Like Reply 49w 7
 ↳ 3 Replies

Bruh. Jamie Oliver is even making other whyte people going "haiyaaaaa".

Like Reply 49w 8

I have mixed feelings.... on one hand, what Oliver made was definitely a weird ass dish which I'm not sure classifies as Thai Curry on the other hand without his video I wouldn't get this video and wouldn't have laughed 😂 is Jamie Oliver a necessary evil ?

Like Reply 49w Edited 4

That's not what we eat in Thailand. He ruined everything.

Like Reply 49w 7

I just wish jamie olive oil would never ever try to cook filipino dish in his show 😂 im going to cut his fridge power cable 😂

Like Reply 49w 7

I think jamie put the wrong title.. supposed to be "pesto chicken" not thai green curry

Like Reply 49w 5

Haiyaaaaaaa 😂

He got it wrong from start to the end. We don't use kaffir leaves in the paste, but kaffir lime rind. And of course galangal, not ginger. As a Thai who cooks at home, I recommend that you buy Thai Green curry paste from Asian supermarket. Even you cook it wrongly, you will at least get the taste of green curry, not tropical stir-fried vegie with chicken. 😂

Like Reply 49w 11

My heart is broken since 1 cup of rice for 4 people. I can finish that much by myself....not to mention coriander and ginger in the curry paste 😂 #เซฟป๊อคนที่หมัดแล้ว

Like Reply 49w Edited 6

↳ 1 Reply

The fck is this knucklehead using hot water to cook rice. And whats with the pinch of salt. Why complicate the simple way of cooking rice. Fck this Jamie Oliver guy. Rice is simple. Rice is sacred. Stop bastardizing our staple food. Fck.

Like Reply 49w 7

As a Thai person who has lived with Thai cuisine for whole life, this video just made me cry 😭😭😭😭

Like Reply 49w 5

MALAYSIA – NG VIDEO 5: COMMENTS

If you are an asian you can definitely relate to Uncle roger's Haiyaaa right now.
 Too much pain in one video

Like Reply 49w 5

That is why i watch Ramsey Gordon, he respects the culture soo much, he studies the recipe, proper technique and gets the right ingredients...

Like Reply 49w 5

I noticed many Western chefs who would like to make Eastern dishes, they don't refer to local experts on how to make the dishes correctly. Instead they take a look at the pictures and decided to make their own recipes and called it the same name...Haiyaaa

Like Reply 49w 4

We usually in malaysia said if u want to get confident u can buy in shoppe. Perhaps British people can buy this kind of confident to cook asian food like Jamie Oliver at Amazon.

Like Reply 49w 4

It's not Thai green curry since he use ginger in galangal ,every step he cooked was shocked T people like me a lot I can't imagine how bizarre dish

Like Reply 49w

As Thai, my ancestors gonna come to Oliver be tonight and fright him because of the rage he r thai cuisine.

Like Reply 49w

Sad part is that I put more chilli in my spaghetti than he did in a chilli based dish...

Like Reply 49w 4

yea that jamie guy should just stick to his fish n chip and lay off the asian cuisine. definitely not his thing unless his fried rice and this followup thing is just a joke...

Like Reply 49w 4

Love how he has to gulp it down right after he tasted his own green curry.

Dear uncle Roger, I feel your pain, he make my ancestors cry every time he cooks italian food. Haaallllia!

Like Reply 49w 4

<https://youtu.be/3fYvN0r8izo> and this is suck gado gado , he didn't boil the vegetables and nobody in indonesia use soy sauce and fish sauce for gado gado

YOUTUBE.COM
 How to Cook Jamie's Gado Gado | Jamie Oliver

You talk so much smack about him. But when TV show or all the restaurants that you own?

Like Reply 49w

↳ 8 Replies

I'm Thai and that does not even look like green big mistake my mum will cry for this video.

Like Reply 49w

MALAYSIA – NG VIDEO 5: COMMENTS

- Unncool Rodger stop acting like bully hiiya 🙄 To be fair Jamie's Asian dishes are for the non Asian home cooks. It's a subtle entry in to oriental cooking 🙄
- Like Reply 49w
- You can just tell the difference between Gordon and Jamie, one is respectful and continuous learning, the other... does this. No wonder Gordon has no respect for Jamie.
- Like Reply 49w
- A like for your video, but Jamie Oliver broke my heart so badly. I need Maggi Curry Noodles to console myself. 🥺🥺🥺
- Like Reply 49w
- I love Jamie Oliver for cooking European dishes! When it comes to Asian cuisine... better leave it to us Asians... rice is already a headache, Thai cuisine has complex flavours and that makes it distinct so changing the procedure or technique won't yield good results- just stick to a green curry pack instead! (I love green curry btw and this is sheer abomination)
- Like Reply 49w
- Growing up in Thailand, I've never had mushroom and mangetout with Thai green curry before. You amaze me Jamie. 🤔
- Like Reply 49w
- This is a crime against green curry. All Thais are also putting legs down watching Jamie Oliver cooking green curry too, uncle Roger. 🤔 #savegreencurry
- Like Reply 49w
- I've never seen green curry like this before. His Thai might be different from the Thai I'm living in.
- Like Reply 49w
- Jamie Olive Oil, please stop cooking Asian food. If you don't know how to cook Asian food properly just stop. Or else it will look like a disrespect attitude to Asian culture. I already hate Jamie since the chili jam fried rice video. If you think you are a great chef please learn how to cook properly like Gordon Ramsay. Haiyaaaaa 🤔🤔🤔
- Like Reply 49w
- I've been eating green curry here in Thailand. It is so delicious and one of my favorites. Watching this video made me say "haiya" too like Uncle Roger. 🤔 I will show this to my Thai colleagues. 🤔
- Like Reply 49w
- im malaysian...but this clearly an insult to our neighbouring country where the origin of that magnificent food was...to jamie...dont fucked up malaysian food like this, or u will feel the wrath of our bawangrians....condolences to those green curry by jamie...deserve a toilet bowl
- Like Reply 49w
- I love how Uncle Roger says "this curry is so white". Yeah, white curry for white people who don't know what Thai green curry really looks and tastes like.
- Like Reply 49w Edited
- My eyes! My eyes!!! Very traumatized to watch! Because one of my favorite food is Thai Green Curry!!!
- Like Reply 49w
- I've been to his restaurants. He can't cook Italian food either!! 🤔
- Like Reply 49w

MALAYSIA – NG VIDEO 5: COMMENTS

- I understand the difficulty in sourcing some ingredients, hence the need to substitute some authentic ingredients for locally available ones. However, the paste, the components, and the cooking method are way too far off to justify.
- If I can only change one thing in this recipe, it would be to use only aubergine as my vegetable. The mangetout and mushrooms add a distinct and confusing flavour that ruins the already weak base of this dish. 🤔
- Like Reply 49w
- My Thai mom was crying after watching Jamie cooked Thai green curry. Too much painful to accept that it's what he called "Thai green curry". And I love when uncle Roger said that he should eat with proper Thai jasmine rice! 🤔
- Like Reply 49w
- ↳ 3 Replies
- I'm starting to wonder if Jamie Oliver does this on purpose to see uncle roger pressed.
- Like Reply 49w
- Green Curry (British version) ...
- Like Reply 49w
- ↳ 1 Reply
- I'm Thai but I never see Thai people cooking like this before. I would like to know who's teaching you how to cook Thai green curry.
- Like Reply 49w
- This feels like he tried to make a "spicy" pesto and call it curry
- Like Reply 49w
- ↳ 1 Reply
- I would say I love Jamie oliver food but this is down right insulting me in person level. You are a chef if you gonna make other country food at least get it right.
- Like Reply 49w
- That's not TGC as in Thai Green Curry..
- That's TGC in the form of Thai Gross Curry. What the hell is that?
- That's stir fry Mushroom with chicken and veggies!
- Like Reply 49w
- Now I know how the Italian feels when we put pineapple on pizza lmao
- Like Reply 49w
- British cuisine is not fit for human consumption
- Like Reply 49w
- Like I watching one cooking show and at the end of cooking some roast potatoes the lady put coriander on top and she call that dish ...Asian roasted potatoes
- Like Reply 49w
- I agree with uncle roger... that not curry, its just vege paste mushroom with chicken.. dont use Thai name on its, better with jamiey vege curry..
- Like Reply 49w

MALAYSIA – NG VIDEO 5: COMMENTS

I love you, uncle Roger. Jamie did the wrong Thai Green Curry. Thank you for saving Thai Green Curry recipe.

Like Reply 49w Edited

Where's the flavor? All of Jamie Olive Oil's food looks so bland and underwhelming.

Like Reply 49w

Jaime Olive Oil commits so many culinary crimes with his Jamie Oliver Green Curry! Hiyaa!

Like Reply 49w

seriously, without Uncle Roger reactions, this particular Jamie Olive Oil's video contains only depression and pain. if you want to torture a Thai spy, tie him in a chair and force him to watch the video, he will spill every secret he has.

Like Reply 49w Edited

Jaime olive oil is a kitchen hand not a chef!

Like Reply 49w

These are the best videos..You know Jamie Olive Oil is going to gloriously muck up any dish and just watching poor Uncle Roger watch in horror as to what sadness is being etched into his memory of these "Asian" dishes

Like Reply 49w

That's not Kang Kreaw Wann or green curry at all!!!!HE RUINS ALL THE ASIAN RECIPES// as a Thai that make me cry like an animal...

Like Reply 49w Edited

Whenever I see Jamie Oliver's restaurant here in Dubai, I always remember this video.. i feel bad for people who were eating there.

Like Reply 3w

Im From Thailand. Seriously, Uncle Roger should get more attention on how great he knows Thai green curry. Im impressed!!!

Like Reply 49w

we get it. You think Jamie is dumb. Lol. So the dish isn't authentic, but it probably still tastes good. Granted, I would prefer the authentic dish. And pardon my ignorance but WTF is mangetout?

Like Reply 49w

↳ 1 Reply

made my day. My ribs hurt from laughing so hard

Like Reply 49w

More like pesto then curry

MALAYSIA – NG VIDEO 5: COMMENTS

Uncle Roger knows south Asian food too. Yes! We use galangall!

Like Reply 49w

Never seen green curry but if I was brought that I would not try it.

Like Reply 49w

I cook Thai green curry at home, I always cook the coconut milk first then add green curry paste

Like Reply 49w Edited

We have our different style in cooking food I guess. It's not really necessary that we need to follow your way of cooking the "green curry". Just be content, at least the foreigners appreciated your food. No need to complain. He can choose a variety and amounts of ingredients he wanted to use. If that's what he wants, show respect. He didn't force you to follow his style. That's his style. Piece of advice, be appreciative instead and respect, that's what matters most. Even you is not perfect in preparing other dishes from different countries. We are not perfect. Each of us is unique and different.

I'm Thai ...and I have to say that is not Thai Green Chilli Soup.

Like Reply 49w

this is post-colonialism done right! Uncle Roger roasting Jamie Oliver making the "perfect" Asian dish.

Like Reply 49w

"He's so clueless but Confident!" this line killed me I'm not even Thai but the way he cooks the rice I know instantly this video is full of f*ck ups

Ginger and lime in green curry? Damn, if you still call that shit a THAI green curry, you've just offended the whole nation. My people are crying with uncle roger.

Like Reply 49w

↳ 1 Reply

5555 this is hilarious. I guess it's Thai green curry, Jamie style, like he said... coz he gave no shit about the curry's traditional main ingredients lol You can call it a fusion maybe even it looks more like a completely new dish to all of us Thai.

Like Reply 49w Edited

Those of us who've been watching Jamie Oliver shows since he 1st came out, know his style of cooking and food preparation are always hard to understand. I respect that, but the moment he started fusing and modifying any Asian recipes. It's unacceptable, since it's too much off compare to other chefs that's done the same.

Like Reply 49w

This curry is so white its about to book a spa holiday..i laughed

Like Reply 49w

Now I figured why Jamie Oliver makes Asian food - to give more contents for Uncle Roger... and... to cheer up our days

Like Reply 49w Edited

It's just sauted veggy with mushroom look so sad and unappetizing

Like Reply 49w

THAILAND – CHRIS RAUFEISEN VIDEO

"It even comes with straps so you can handle your failure" 555

Like Reply 1y

THAILAND – CHRIS WRIGHT VIDEO

All 2.1K 254 35 More

THAILAND – WRIGHT VIDEO: COMMENTS

Well actually, it's a creative way of teaching English to those who don't know these words and phrases. Hahaha.

Like Reply 44w

Ajarn Chris Wright อาจารย์คริส ไรท์ Totally agree krup. I like to look alike. I will look back at all when I have free time.

Hahaha This is hilarious, Art! I have to say that it's such a creative way of teaching English to adult Thai learners, especially that it puts in a few elements of communicative competence: discourse and socio-linguistics. Humor makes this less mentally stressful and draining to learn though. Man, I miss teaching in Thailand. I wish I could go back there next year.

I like it. Very funny. 🤔🤔🤔🤔

Like Reply See Original (Thai) 44w

So much fun.

Like Reply See Original (Thai) 44w

Very fun 🤔🤔

Like Reply See Original (Thai) 44w

Very creative. I like it. 🤔🤔

Yeah let it's go 🤔🤔

Like Reply 44w

Wells done. 🤔🤔

Like Reply 44w

Some people hhh

Like Reply 44w

55555 so good

THAILAND – WRIGHT VIDEO: COMMENTS

I like it. Very fun and easy to understand. Thank you teacher Chris.

Like Reply See Original (Thai) 44w

🤔🤔🤔🤔

Like Reply 11w

It's funny and I get to know the language without getting bored. ❤️❤️

When the teacher checks the name, the students will say "come here". What do the foreigners say, teacher?

Like Reply See Original (Thai) 44w

"Present"= Come. ...

Like Reply See Original (Thai) 42w

I like the video of Teacher Chris who does this. It's fun and stress-free. Happy and want to watch often. I like it very much. 🤔🤔

Like Reply See Original (Thai) 44w

+1

Both fun and knowledge. Thank you.

Like Reply See Original (Thai) 44w

I like it very much. Everyone is cute. I get knowledge in a fun way.

Now it's very fun. Haha.

Like Reply See Original (Thai) 44w

Ep2 want to see it

Like Reply 44w

I like it very much. 🤔🤔🤔

Like Reply See Original (Thai) 44w

55555555

Like Reply 44w

THE PHILIPPINES – ALEX CALLEJA VIDEO 1

All

😂 458

👍 210

❤️ 11

😞 2

😱 1

THE PHILIPPINES – CALLEJA VIDEO 1: COMMENTS

Masyadong mabilis papz ung happy b-day 😂😂😂😂

Like Reply 2y

Yong wala kang ambag sa birthday party 🤔

Like Reply 2y

hahahhahahahah!!!!!! iba ka tlg idol ...

Like Reply 2y

mali pala pag uurong ko HAHAHAH 😂

Like Reply 2y

Like Reply 2y

Kahit kailan mais joke mo, ...

Like Reply 2y

THE PHILIPPINES – ALEX CALLEJA VIDEO 2

THE PHILIPPINES – CALLEJA VIDEO 2: COMMENTS

- Out of the playing court ka na niyan lol
Like Reply 2y
- konting calcium naman.. walang kwenta mga brad..
Like Reply 2y
- laki n ng kita nyan joke mo panahon pa ni kupong kupong
- magaling ka na sana magbasketbol nagoatawa ka pa ayoko na tuloy manood sayo nakakabobong patawa komedyà MO
Like Reply 2y
- corny mo lods
- Nakakatawa grabe.
Like Reply 1y
- Joker ah
Like Reply 1y
- Tryouts po kayo sa gilas, kailangan po yung mga ganyan skills sir 😂😂
Like Reply 1y
- How to steal the philhealth fund 🤔🤔🤔🤔
Like Reply 1y
- Alex Calleja with the itak
- How to steal the ball back?
Babalik yung inagawan may dalang baril. 😂😂
Like Reply 2y
- how to escape the prison. "alex scofield"
Like Reply 2y
- I didn't see it coming
Like Reply 2y
- Hayup ka alex hahaha
Like Reply 2y
- Nice lods hehe
Like Reply 2y
- Steenless steal the ball?
Like Reply 2y
- How to flex dem jordans
Like Reply 2y
- Batang Pasay na ngayon tiga Signal VIII. Pag naman nanlaban ka pa nyan tol bigay mo na lang 😂
Like Reply 2y
- Mabuhay ang Katipunanero
Like Reply 2y Edited
- Sa ssunod yta kinakatay mo na yung assistant mo boss alex haha.
Like Reply 2y
- How to steal: maging gov't official
Like Reply 2y Edited 🤔🤔🤔🤔🤔🤔 6
- Iba ka talaga master! Hahaha
Like Reply 2y
- IDOL alex isa ka talagang Alamat
Like Reply 1y
- galing idol dudut
Like Reply 1y
- laki n ng kita nyan joke mo panahon pa ni kupong kupong
Like Reply 2y
- Corny mo d ako matawaA sau lol
Like Reply 2y

THE PHILIPPINES – ALEX CALLEJA VIDEO 3

THE PHILIPPINES – CALLEJA VIDEO 3: COMMENTS

- Literal na miserable. ...
Like Reply 1y
- Haahahahahah
Like Reply 1y
- Idol .
Like Reply 1y
- ayaw talaga makinig nung madinig naman nanghamon ng rebolusyon! agad agad!
- Mas okie pa to kesa sa original song 🤔
Like Reply 1y
- hahahaha ang lupet mu lods,
Like Reply 1y
- AHAHAHAHA 🤔
Like Reply 1y
- The best!
- Wait...di ako masatisfied sa react lang ih...BWAHAHAHAHAHAHAHAHAHA HA
Like Reply 1y
- Napatawa ako neto... Godbless keep safe.
Like Reply 1y
- Nkktuwa ka tlg sir alex. Hehehe 🤔
Like Reply 1y
- Tahimik sila pag government issue 🤔
Bingi bingihan 🤔
Like Reply 1y
- LT idoll
Like Reply 1y
- Di niyo ba naririnig ang nakawan sa Philhealth 🎵🎵🎵🎵🎵🎵🎵
Like Reply 1y
- ga, baka pag nagdodota ako di ko marinig ah... 🤔
Like Reply 1y
- 1 Reply
- HAHAHAHA tangina laughtrip 🤔
Like Reply 1y
- Bentahaha pinagsasaing o paglalabatin???
- Benta! Hahaha ...
Like Reply 1y
- Maglalaba pala 🤔
- Takot ka pala Papi. Haha 🤔
Like Reply 1y
- Bakit nga ganun kahit anong tapang ng lalaki pag sumigaw si misis ganyan itsura ng lalaki 🤔
Like Reply 1y
- Bad trip. Ito na maaalala ko pag narinig ko tong kanta na to
Like Reply 1y
- Epic
Like Reply 1y

THE PHILIPPINES – ALEX CALLEJA VIDEO 4

All

😂 24K

👍 5.2K

❤️ 268

More ▾

😂 40

😱 22

😭 19

😡 10

THE PHILIPPINES – CALLEJA VIDEO 4: COMMENTS

Happy Father's Day Alex!

Like Reply 1y

↳ 1 Reply

Happy Father's day po!!

Like Reply 1y

hahaha...🤣🤣🤣🤣 lodi petmalu....happy fathers day..po..😂

Lodi super tlga anag tawa ko wala kang kupas boss sana masaya mo lahat ng tao sa mundi para kahit pandemic chilax and happy lang ang lahat 🙌😂🤗

Like Reply 1y

Happy fathers day po 😊

Like Reply 1y

Hanip ka talaga sir Alex, happy father's day!

Like Reply 1y

Tapang ikaw Papa [redacted] ??? 🤣🤣🤣 Advance Happy Father's Day... 🥰❤️🤗🤗🤗🤗

Like Reply 1y

Happy Father's Day Alex! ...

Like Reply 1y

THE PHILIPPINES – ALEX CALLEJA VIDEO 5

All

😂 14K

👍 6K

❤️ 255

😱 62

More ▾

😱 50

😡 24

😞 7

THE PHILIPPINES – CALLEJA VIDEO 5: COMMENTS

Alex Calleja

<https://m.facebook.com/story.php...>

Like Reply 17w

San nakapark yan dati? 🤔

Like Reply 1y

The myth, the legend ford everest, finally nakita narin kita.

Like Reply 1y

Yari ka nanaman sa asawa mo Idol! Pati sa mga kumare nya! Hahaha

Like Reply 1y

Fix Or Return Daily thats the meaning of FORD 🤔

Like Reply 21w Edited

I seen this guy sa ads "meron k bng mga product sa china kmi ang bahala magpadala dito sa pinas" i wonder kung open p yung business n yun

Yare ka sa missis mo... 🤔

Like Reply 1y

hahaha mukhang sa Civic ka matutulog boss 🤔

Like Reply 1y

Supper hambog m0 naman? 🤔🤔🤔🤔🤔

Like Reply 21w

Hahaha nakita na!! 🤔

Like Reply 39w

Eh drive mo na yan at sundoin na yung amo mo.. mamaya sisantihin kapa mag hanap ng bagong driver yun..

Like Reply 22w

wala nmn tlga kwenta mga joke! kaw lang natatawa sa mga joke mo!!!

Like Reply 26w

Sana inalis mo emblem Ng ford ginawa mo Toyota or Nissan Yun pwde pa katawa tawa

Like Reply 29w

Uhoh utot mu

best way to flex 🤔🤔🤔

Like Reply 49w

Kung ayaw nyo sya makita or mapanood, wag nalang po kayo mag click sa vids nya, wag nlang din mag comment ng makaka sakit . Tao din yan nasasaktan sa mga masasamang nababasa. Ako isa ako sa natatawa, ibig sabihin may iba rin sya na napapasaya. kung hindi masaya yung iba tumahimik nlang po sana.

Like Reply 31w

FORD - full of rattles and defects 🤔

Like Reply 29w

Tarantado ka talaga lagi mo kame pinaglolo-loko 🤔

Like Reply 1y

THE PHILIPPINES – JAMES CARAAN VIDEO 1

THE PHILIPPINES – CARAAN VIDEO 1: COMMENTS

BREAKING: Sec. Nograles natagpuang TANGA!

Like Reply 1y

[Redacted]

Like Reply 1y

[Redacted] ...
Cringe fest nograles

Like Reply 1y

[Redacted] nakaka proud maging pilipino tlga 😊

Like Reply 1y

Wala na talagang matino sa mga nanunungkulan ngayon sa gobyerno puro may mga sayad amputs.

Like Reply 1y

[Redacted]

Favorite ko yung song nyan na Yeye Bonel. 😂 4

Like Reply 1y

[Redacted] ...
Ang creepy di nakurap. Hahahaha

Like Reply 1y

Batibot 😂

Like Reply 1y

[Redacted]

Like Reply 1y

[Redacted] Inner Pinky Webb 😊

Like Reply 1y

THE PHILIPPINES – JAMES CARAAN VIDEO 2

All 😂 637 👍 40 🤔 2 ❤️ 1

THE PHILIPPINES – CARAAN VIDEO 2: COMMENTS

Tama ka. Tama ka. 😂 2

Like Reply 1y

HAHAHAHAHA! Legit! ...

Like Reply 1y 👍 3

That's why you are my favorite person in social media right now HAHHAHAHA

Like Reply 1y

Covid deniers vs. Flat Earthers = it's a Tie. 😂😂

Shots fired 🔥🔥🔥

Like Reply 1y

Natataon to ...

Like Reply See Translation 1y

Naalala ko ung usog joke ni GB eh hahah. Bawat usog may laway sa paa ung bata eh hahaha

Like Reply 1y

Boset ka James 😂

Si Dr/wRONG ba ito? Hahahaha 😂😂😂

Like Reply 1y

Top fan

Bagong pagkatao ba ulit ito? Haha ...

Like Reply 1y

ayan na pulube bars mo bingaw 😂

haha tamaaaaaaaaaa ...

Like Reply See Translation 1y

Sakto talaga kahit spoof pero totoo talaga nangyayare

Like Reply 1y

tama

Lawayan mo daw! 😂😂

Like Reply 1y

THE PHILIPPINES – JAMES CARAAN VIDEO 4

All 😂 1.6K 👍 41 ❤️ 5 😱 3

THE PHILIPPINES – CARAAN VIDEO 4: COMMENTS

tray tapos piniritto, nilaga tapos binati? Di ba dapat na gayahin mo itlog? Hahahahahah ooppss

Like Reply 1y

Author James Caraan
 [redacted] ikaw naman masyado ka technical, alam mo na yun 😂
 Like Reply 1y

Intayin ko to sa koolpals episode 😂😂😂

Like Reply 1y

[redacted]
 Justice para sa tray ng itlog at ecobag 😂😂😂

Like Reply 1y

[redacted]
 Hustisya para sa Ecobag!!!!

Like Reply 1y

[redacted] good laugh

Like Reply 1y

[redacted]
 Magaling ba mag bate si marites? 🍷

Like Reply 1y

[redacted]
 panalo.

Like Reply 1y

Like Reply 1y

Like Reply 1y

Like Reply 1y

Egul ginawang lecheflan

Like Reply 1y

[redacted]
 "Bro alam mo palamunin ka bro. Alam ko na yan eh!"

Like Reply 1y

[redacted]
 Um to sa crw ah

Like Reply See Translation 1y

[redacted]
 Gago ka tga james. 😂😂😂😂😂

Like Reply 1y

Like Reply 1y

Wallah, tawang-tawa akoooo 😂😂😂 (ang late kong magreact 😂...months)

Like Reply 46w

[redacted]
 Wala Po bang community party?? 🤔

Ba naman yan, na-saboy ko yung sopas na kinakain ko.

Like Reply 1y

[redacted]
 AHAHAHAHAHA IBA KA TALAGA NOTPA.

Like Reply 1y

[redacted]

Like Reply 1y

THE PHILIPPINES – JAMES CARAAN VIDEO 5

THE PHILIPPINES – CARAAN VIDEO 5: COMMENTS

- Hail Satan!!!
Like Reply 1y
- Hahahahahahaha tangina mo talaga James Caraan!
Naputol ng pwet ko yung jebes ko sa kakatawa 😂😂
- pucha tagal nag update ni satan, hullng kita ko sa kanya medyo mahaba pa buhok
- Satan nyo naawa na, puro kademonyohan na daw nangyayari sa pinas eh. 😂
- billion intel fund is shaking 😂
- Laki kasi ng intelfund nabuking ka rin satan..
- Walastik James naibuga ko iniinom ko sa paandar mo. 🍷🍷🍷
- I stan Satan!
Like Reply 1y
- Nice one! 🙌
Like Reply 1y
- Motivational speaker na din sa Santanas.
Like Reply 1y
- naalala ko yung bitoy's world na show, every week bagong character.... James Caraan may potential ka
- Another personality Unlocked!
Like Reply 1y
- Real James
Like Reply 1y
- Demonyong Matulonging,
Demonyong may Puso.
Like Reply 1y
- Mavin Catbagan
Saang stage sa Tekken ma-uunlock si Devil James?
Like Reply 1y
- Lakas ng "intel" kahit sa impyerno nakakaabot.
Napilitan tuloy umamin si Satanas.
Like Reply 1y
- billion pa naman ang intel funds kada taon
Like Reply 1y
- hindi ka ba nabastos doon, boss satan? kasi kinompara ka sa may naitulong
Like Reply 1y
- grabee ang crispy naman niyan 🍷
Like Reply 1y
- Kelvin John trigger na naman mga dds neto 🍷
Like Reply 1y
- Ahahahahahahaha bat mo kasi binigyan ng apple
Like Reply 1y
- Haha nadamay pa nga
Like Reply 1y
- Stan Satan
Like Reply 1y
- Devil James
Like Reply 1y
- Natural na. Natural hahaha
Like Reply 1y
- Mag hasik tayo ng tulong hahahaha
Like Reply 1y
- tanigna yung hey hey hey hahaha
Like Reply 1y
- Parlade tutal mahilig ka sa komunista bakit di ka sa WPS maghanap? Doon surely makakahanap kang hinayupak ka.
Like Reply 1y
- Hail Satan, Chost!
Like Reply 1y
- Hahahaha haycp
Like Reply 1y
- Galing. 🍷
Like Reply 1y

THE PHILIPPINES – JAMES CARAAN VIDEO 6

THE PHILIPPINES – CARAAN VIDEO 6: REACTIONS AND COMMENTS

James Caraan
Tama kayong lahat! (para isahan na lang) 😂😂😂
Like Reply 48w 1.1K

James Caraan
FYI lang po. Kung ayaw nyong panoorin yung video, pwede kayong hindi mag-comment na ayaw nyong panoorin yung video.
Panoho lang yan ng ayaw nyong kumain sa Jollibee, tapos pumasok kayo sa Jollibee para i-announce na ayaw nyong kumain sa Jollibee.

James Caraan
Yung mga mesaya ka-bonding cayan, follow nyo kami sa Spotify, **The KoolPals**:
www.spotify.com/KoolPals... See more

Pangit ka bonding ng ibang Pinoy, di gets ang satire mga NASsexuals amputa.

Like Reply 48w 291

Mga NAS LOVERS. Mga Baby Bra Warriors ni Nas hahaha

Like Reply 48w 34

Just say "Mabuhay Philippines" and then filipinos will forgive you 😊

Like Reply 48w Edited 77

Di kpa talaga sikat James. Di pa nila alam na komedyante ka wahahahahaha

Like Reply 48w 84

Nakiki ride daw wow, so wala na talagang saysay ang satire sa atin, di na uso joke kasi 2021 na lahat offended gagi

Like Reply 48w 381

Silent fan here. Galing Idol kuhang kuha lahat every second counts. So far ito ang best video para sa akin

Like Reply 48w Edited 239

Because not everyone will appreciate what you have done to them, You have to endure the pain of pangangilo.

So now, I am using Sensodyne.

Like Reply 48w 632

I really like your Country (Philippines). People the are so funny and they're all having great sense of humor and hospitable. Wishing to visit there soon again. Greeting from Seoul.Secul-tan Kudarat.

Like Reply 48w 31

Hahaha..kahit kailan di ako naging fan nyan ni Naz ...kahit yung isa pang ungas na si project nightfall...utak krudo din yun.

Like Reply 48w 24

No wonder why I rarely watch Filipino Vloggers simply because of these trash content.

Like Reply 48w 164

Trash "daw" pero nandito at nagcomment pa nga

Ang dali talaga manloko ng sarili 😂😂😂

Like Reply 48w 54

Everyone see's a single mistake of Nas Daily and they have already forgotten the good deeds of a person, how toxic filipinos can be, Nobody is perfect, not even you, everyone has the right to say their opinion relating to the issue, but also remember that everyone makes a mistake and Nas is just like us, a human being who makes mistakes, so let's not judge one another, spread kindness not toxicity.

Like Reply 106

I love this hahaha, many social media people using Philippines because Philippines is a social media country in the world, they do there best to fool the Filipino for the sake of money, you guys here do not pretend, i know many of you are already aware to this, not only the Philippines,

Like Reply 48w 95

Philippines is more than this. Hope we could stop this.

Like Reply 48w 57

you just cured the philippines with your comment lol

Like Reply 48w 14

Why am I hearing Dora's accent 😂😂

Like Reply 48w 5

THE PHILIPPINES – CARAAN VIDEO 6: COMMENTS

:Saludo ako sa mga taong ganto kahit may kapansanan kaya parin nila ipakita ang kanilang kakaibang talento sana wag mona uuliten

Like Reply 48w 45

Yung boses Nas Daily pero yung kamay pang Ben Tisoy

Like Reply 48w 378

Not the whole Philippines because most Filipinos did not know Nas...we dont bother what he's going through simply we have to focus on our own struggle like covid...Some people what to recognize so Nas merely the best subject of their recognition or popularity.....

Like Reply 48w 64

Nas Daily apology video while eating Jollibee chickenjoy

Like Reply 48w 551

Imitation is the highest form of flattery...just saying

Like Reply 48w 378

Nas Daily exploits the Philippines, now James Caraan is exploiting Nas Daily's controversy are all content creators ex.....?

Like Reply 48w 7

sana sumikat kana para tigil mo na tong kalokohan na to..

Like Reply 48w 189

Most Relevant is selected, so some replies may have been filtered out

It's a parody, can't you be happy and laugh for a minute?

Like Reply 48w 378

Siguro gawa gawa nyo lang yan para makalimutan namin ang sinabi ni Allan Peter Cayetano na kada pamilya may sampong libo

Like Reply 48w 4

Madami pala talaga ang hindi nakakagets ng sarcasm. Nas apologist. Lol.

Like Reply 48w 7

Author James Caraan sana pray lang po tayo

Like Reply 48w 395

Mga pilipinong galit Mai content ang Pinas for possible exploitation pero mga clout chaser din naman. Hay nako. The hypocrisy.

Like Reply 48w 4

Using Nas Daily to make a Content in a Vlog is a shame..Well money is life

Like Reply 48w 230

Most Relevant is selected, so some replies may have been filtered out

For those who know this is just a joke i applause you guys, and for those who took this seriously or hate naz for unknown/reasons just being crab... Have a good day.

Like Reply 48w Edited 27

Hindi naman kalbo si Nas Daily

Like Reply 48w 18

Author James Caraan

Like Reply 48w 710

it's no use mga peenose yan puro narrow-minded

Like Reply 48w 7

Na forgive nga ng pilipinas sina marcos, estrada at bong revilla. Si nas daily pa kaya

Like Reply 48w 36

daming nakikisakay sa issue para magkaroon ng views

Like Reply 48w 75

1st thought ko 'ay wala ng content kung anu lang mapost' .. then un pinapanood ko sya grabe halakhak ko un nagflashback saken si nas daily sa utak ko..gayang gaya hahah

Like Reply 48w 7

Why do we blame those foreigners who are "milking" from us eh choice naman nating i-patronize sila? tayo naman may kagagawan kung bakit nila tayo "napeperahan"? Just saying.

Like Reply 48w 33

this video is just for fun bat andaming galit na nag eenglish ? para ba mag mukhang tama nasaan sense of humor niyo ? keep it up James Caraan

Like Reply 48w 69

Palitan mo ng "I", wag mo kaming isali.

Like Reply 48w 7